

ISSN:
2750-6274

**EUROPEAN
MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL
OF MODERN SCIENCE**

www.emjms.academicjournal.io

No	Paper Title	Author Name	Page No
1	The Role of Women in the of a Healthy Lifestyle	Gulbaxar Tulepova	1-3
2	Why is Learning Foreign Languages Important?	Dilnoza Nazarova, Zafar Nurmatovich Abdusamadov	4-6
3	Problems of the Development of the Health Care System of Our Country	Urokov Firdavs Ortikniyozovich	7-9
4	Medical of the Population of Sirdarya Region Insurance Transition Experience	Urokov Firdavs Ortikniyozovich	10-11
5	Developmental Approach to the Formation of Antimonopoly Policy in the Digital Economy	Shakarov Davron Ulashboyevich, Xoliqulov Anvar Nematovich	12-16
6	Linguistic Analysis of Uzbek Virtual Communication	Guli Toirova Ibragimovna, Yusupova Alfiya Shavketovna	17-21
7	Environmental Problems of the Modern Conditions	Bekniyazova Dilfuza Bazarbay qizi, Uteniyazov Azizbek Sarsenbay uli, Nurtaeva Dilnaz Xojabaevna	22-25
8	Mechanisms for Blurring Pedagogical Processes Aimed at Creative Thinking of Students	Abdrimov Inoyatbek Akhmedovich	26-32
9	Methods of Temperature Management and Control at the Interface of Technological System Applications	Yo'ldoshova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi	33-39
10	Challenges in Teaching English as a Second Language to Adults, Multilingual Settings and Teaching Methods	Azimova Mahfuza Abdusamatovna	40-43
11	Content, Form and Means of Formation of Basic Competences in Primary School Students	Ortiqova Ziyodaxon Otajon, Isomiddinova Sayyoraxon Nematovna	44-47
12	Didactic Possibilities of the Formation of Competencies in Students	Davletov Erkaboy Yusubovich	48-51
13	Working With Various Methods and Approaches	Dusbayeva Nazira Narimanovna	52-54
14	Gender Policy in Practice	Marjona Tinicheva Gulomjon qizi	55-57
15	The Importance of Innovative Technologies in Teaching a Foreign Language	Kho`janova Mastura Ibodullayevna	58-61
16	Artistic Ideological Education of Future Music Teachers through the Epic of Khorazm	Yakubov Zafarbak	62-64
17	Modern Composer Creativity and Variety Art, Interaction Issues	Nazarov Khushnud Irkinovich	65-67
18	Work on a Small Polyphonic Cycle in the Class of Special Piano	Madina Fayziyeva	68-72
19	Expression of Education in the Family in the Karakalpak Language	Berdimuratova G. A	73-76
20	Issues of Increasing Population Level and Welfare	Sh. S. Sharifov, D. E. Rashidova	77-81

Table of Content - Volume 18 (May 2023)

No	Paper Title	Author Name	Page No
21	A Comprehensive Review of the Fishes of the Aral Sea: Past, Present, and Future Perspectives	Jamila Jiyenbaeva	82-84
22	Research on automation of gas meters and introduction of technological mobile application system in the Republic of Uzbekistan	Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi	85-90
23	Digital technologies in the educational system	Asamatdinova Mexribanu Muratbay qizi, Ayapbergenova Saltanat Shinpolatovna	91-95
24	Selecting a proper method for teaching grammar as a skill for adult students by conducting a detailed research	Sayfullayeva Fayozaxon Tohirovna	96-98
25	Features of designing knitwear	Matjanova Parwaz Baxitovna	99-100
26	PEDAGOGICAL VIEWS OF THE JADID ENLIGHTENMENT ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF GENDER CULTURE	Ochilova Gulnoza Asrorovna	101-103
27	A Treasury of British Folklore	Tosheva Dilbar Muzaffar kizi	104-106
28	Enhancing Problem Solving Skills in Trainee Teachers through Constructionist-Based Teaching Approach	Ugochi Peace Ibeh Jaja, Prof. Eunice C. Victor-Ishikaku	107-116
29	Theoretical Principles of Aesthetic Education of Students Based on the Music of Makom Instruments	Boltayev Umidbek Rustamovich	117-120
30	The Level of Salinity and the Dynamics of Change in the Irrigated Soils of Dostlik Massif, Furqat District, Fergana Region	Jabbarov Odil Abdimalikovich, Sodikova Maftunakhan Olimjon qizi, Makhkamova Dilafuz Yuldashevna	121-123
31	The Place of Abu Ali Ibn Sina (Avicenna) in Present Times	Hakim Darmonov Orif o'g'li	124-126
32	Innovative Technologies in Teaching Vocabulary in Foreign Languages	Jalalova Sevara Janabay kizi	127-129

The Role of Women in the of a Healthy Lifestyle

Gulbaxar Tulepova

Basic doctoral student Nukus State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract: The article serves to emphasize full support of women and the promotion of their status in the family and society as one of the top priorities of the state policy. It also provides scientific conclusions on the content and essence of the ongoing reforms to ensure the strength and well-being of the family.

Keywords: State policy, top priority, reforms, society, women, gender equality, family strength, well-being.

INTRODUCTION

During the years of independence, the process of dealing with women's issues has been systematized in Uzbekistan which serves to ensure their active participation in the society. Over the past period, the conditions created for the further enhancement of the role and status of women in the society have laid the foundation for them to take their social activity seriously. In particular, the adoption of the Law "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men" and the Law "On Protection of Women from Oppression and Violence" has strengthened the legal framework in this regard.

However, despite the fact that a number of measures have been taken in the interests of women, the following problems hinder a number of systemic measures such as full support of women, the organization of targeted work with them, strengthening the spiritual and moral environment in families and creating effective mechanisms for the improvement of women health were noted in the Presidential Decree: First, there is no targeted support system for women in need and in difficult social situations, there is no practice of individual work with unemployed and socially inactive women, inefficient organization of employment promotion and entrepreneurship development among women;

Second, there is a lack of targeted work to prepare young people for family life, to form a modern model family, to strengthen its spiritual and moral foundations and traditional family values and the effectiveness of measures to prevent early marriages, family conflicts and divorces still remains low etc.

Third, women's reproductive health activities are not sufficiently organized, and there is no effective system for the prevention and treatment of maternal and perinatal diseases, especially in remote rural areas;

Fourth, there are no effective measures for the prevention of delinquency and crime among women and the mechanism of improving the legal culture of women, providing them with legal advice does not meet modern requirements;

Fifth, the wide-ranging functions of women's committees do not allow them to fully mobilize their efforts and capabilities to address the most pressing issues of women due to the absence of the necessary competencies and personnel; Sixth, the uncertainty of the organizational subordination of the Republican Research and Practice Center "Family" and the lack of

necessary funding impedes the effective implementation of its tasks e.g. to study family problems and develop practical-scientific proposals for their solution;

Seventh, there is absence of work for training and retraining of young people for family life, family strengthening, conflict and divorce prevention. "On measures for radical improvement of activities in the field of support of women and strengthening of the institute of the family" has brought the committee system to a new level. The decree sets out a number of measures to radically improve the activities in the field of support for women and strengthening the institution of the family.

This decree was passed to introduce the measures which ensure the rights and interests of women, social and moral support, political engagement, women's role in building society and the state leading them to a new level; moreover, it aims at demonstrating women potential, creating new opportunities for further development of their activities.

Also the decree sets out a number of measures aimed at enhancing the socio-political activity of women, ensuring their legitimate interests, realizing their abilities and potential, strengthening the institution of the family, protection of motherhood and childhood. In particular, the chairman of the Women's Committee and the heads of its regional branches are in charge of the following tasks:

- to timely identify women in difficult life situations, including women with disabilities, organize individual and targeted work and support them;
- to implement practical measures to ensure the employment of women, the development of family and private entrepreneurship and crafts among them;
- to organize effectively the prevention of delinquency and crime among women, increase their legal culture and strengthen their spiritual and moral values.

Involvement of the representatives of the Women's Committee and the "Family" Center in meetings and other events not related to their responsibilities and activities is strongly prohibited. The main tasks of the Republican Scientific and Practical Center "Family" organized under the Women's Committee are, first of all, to implement the conceptual idea of "Healthy family - healthy society". Another achievement in this field was the establishment of the medal "Honorable Woman" which is awarded for women who have shown potency and initiative in the life of society and the state and who have made a worthy contribution to the formation and strengthening of the family, protection of motherhood and childhood.

Over the years, women have made an important contribution to the formation of the spirituality of the society, both in the socio-spiritual and educational spheres. The introduction of the position of a specialist in working with women in all neighborhoods, strengthening the spiritual and moral values in families was another privilege in this field which has given a chance to study the families closely and serves to ensure the effectiveness of targeted solutions to existed problems. In particular, under the responsibility of such specialists a large-scale of work has been carried out in each neighborhood in order to prevent delinquency and crime among women. A great attention was paid to solving the social problems of women released from prisons, as well as 2,587 members of religious denominations, who were deregistered last year and found their own place in the society. Address lists of vulnerable and disabled women have been compiled to work with them individually and systematically.

It is known that further strengthening and development of the family, especially increasing the role of the family in educating the younger generation as physically healthy and spiritually mature individuals, focusing on the role of women in building a strong, healthy family are recognized as main priorities of today's state policy. As President Sh. Mirziyoev noted: "High respect for women who are the "pillars" of the family and society, the grace and

beauty of our lives, has always been and will remain a great value for our people". As an evidence and performance of the high respect and care for women, in recent years more than 80 national and international documents have been adopted to strengthen the role and influence of women in society and protect their legal, social, economic and spiritual interests. Achieving the efficiency in family upbringing in the conditions of rapid exchange of information, the formation of free, independent thinking, initiative young people with organizational skills is the guarantee of the preservation of national identity, upbringing of harmoniously developed generation, ensuring family stability, increasing its wellbeing, creating healthy and spiritual environment in family.

CONCLUSION

The Presidential Decree of February 18, 2020 "On measures to improve the social and spiritual atmosphere in society, further support of the mahalla institute, as well as raising the system of work with families and women to a new level" has played an important role in the support of women's social activism, strengthening their place in society and the guarantees of protection of their rights and legitimate interests, the organizational and legal right to ensure a healthy and stable socio-spiritual environment in society and the family, as well as peace, harmony and tranquility and radically reforming the mechanisms and bringing the system of working with families and women to a new level.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoev Sh. Congratulation of Women's Day // Khalk Suzi, March 8, 2019.
2. Speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev in the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 22.06.2019.// Khalk Suzi, June 2019 //uza.uz
3. Djuraeva N. The social status of women in the history of Uzbekistan. -Tashkent: Nodirabegim, 2020. – p195-196.
4. Buribekova D. The dependence of society on women`s activism
5. wcu/uzTog'ayevaMuattarBahodirqizi student of Uzbekistan state world language university
6. Салохиддинова, Н. И. (2020). Вопросы поэтического образа в поэзии. ББК: 71.01 К 90, 203.
7. Salokhiddinova, N. I. (2019). EXPRESSION OF A PASSION FOR POETRY BY ZEBO MIRZO. Theoretical & Applied Science, (12), 227-230.
8. Salohiddinova, N. (2019). Zebo Mirzo's poetry and image. International Journal on Integrated Education, 2(6), 115-118.
9. Mahametova, D. B. (2019). Specificities English Language Non-Academic Hours. Eastern European Scientific Journal, (1).
10. Dilnavoz, M. (2019). Peculiarities of teaching foreign languages with Moodle-based E-learning courses. Academy, (7 (46)), 62-64.
11. MAHAMETOVA, D. B. (2018). PROJECT METHOD IN DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENT'S PRACTICAL SKILLS AT NON-ACADEMIC HOURS OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE. Иностраннные языки в Узбекистане, (2), 165-170.

Why is Learning Foreign Languages Important?

Dilnoza Nazarova

2nd stage student of Uzbekistan State University of World Languages

Zafar Nurmatovich Abdusamadov

Dean of the 3rd Faculty of English Language of Uz DJTU, f.f.f.d., PhD

Abstract: This article discusses the importance of learning foreign languages in human life. In today's fast-paced world, knowing a foreign language is extremely important, because every sphere of life, business, education relies on a foreign language.

Keywords: foreign language, distance learning, social networks, modern technology, language specialist.

Learning a foreign language is very important for everyone today. The world is becoming more and more globalized, and bilingualism is not a passing fad but a need of the time. Learning a foreign language is a life skill for learning how to truly communicate and connect with others. Why should we learn foreign languages? Today we will discuss about this topic. I will write about why you should learn a foreign language.

1. Learning a foreign language makes your brain grow. Research shows cognitive benefits of learning another language, regardless of age. These studies show that bilingual people have bigger brains, better memories, greater creativity, better problem-solving skills, and more. These advantages make it easier not only to learn more languages, but to learn them all. The ability to quickly switch between tasks is especially important in today's busy multitasking world. Bilinguals can switch between tasks much more quickly than their monolingual counterparts while completing many other tasks.

2. Learning a foreign language makes traveling cheaper and easier. Of course, many people travel consciously. Knowing the language is very useful when traveling to a foreign country. I can easily describe what I want to eat when I go out to eat. ask the locals for directions. You can request it without any problem. It will be higher if you add a guide.

3. If you learn a foreign language, the world of job hunting will expand. It's no secret that learning a foreign language improves your job prospects. With more companies than ever before operating in multiple countries, sometimes dozens, around the world, he must employ employees who can understand at least one foreign language. you can't do that. Even for a small local business, the ability to speak a second language can set you apart from other potential employers.

4. Make new friends while learning a foreign language. Meeting new interesting people and developing lifelong friendships is certainly a goal worth pursuing, and learning another language is a sure way to speed up the process. It helps you express your feelings and desires, connect with people around you, and build meaningful relationships.

5. Learning a foreign language broadens your mind. Learning a foreign language and immersing yourself in a whole new culture and worldview is the surest way to become an open-minded, understanding, tolerant and absolutely valuable person. And understanding

where you and others come from is an eye-opening experience.

6. Learning a foreign language helps you understand your own language and culture better. Learning a foreign language puts you in a paradoxical state and allows you to better understand your native language and culture. This is one of the most unexpected benefits of learning a foreign language. You will gain a better understanding of not only cultural conventions, but also the grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation patterns of your native language.

This probably explains the improvement in listening, reading, and writing skills that a foreign language gives formerly monolinguals. The benefits of learning a foreign language make you successful in nearly every aspect of your life. have the ability Learning a foreign language is very important and there are countless reasons for learning a foreign language. Learning a foreign language helps break down language barriers and bring people together on a deeper level of mutual understanding. Now let's talk about why learning a language is important for non-language teachers. Especially these days, teachers are required to have knowledge of English. why do you need this? I would like to share my thoughts on this. As we all know, English is recognized as the language of the world. She is one of the two young people learning English. At least I'm interested in this language.

Also, knowing English is a great opportunity for teachers to broaden their knowledge. The secret is that most scientific papers are written in English. Feel free to read the original. Another important aspect is that knowledge of English will make it easier for you to use today's latest technology and social networks. English is also called the language of technology. Almost all social networks are easily covered in English. Distance learning has only just begun during the well-known pandemic. This created difficulties for many teachers. Not all teachers know the latest techniques and how to use social networks. Knowledge of English puts an end to these problems.

In summary, knowledge of English is the key to new opportunities for industry representatives. Knowing your field opens one door. Knowing English opens another door. In fact, knowing one language can open doors to the whole world.

REFERENCES

1. expanc.ru
2. UzNE. The first volume. Tashkent, 2000
3. https://www.google.com/search?q=ong+borliqning+ma%27naviy+shakli&source=lmns&bih=657&biw=1366&hl=ru&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEwj4m9Sxq-X9AhXOuyoKHW5PAFsQ_AUoAHoECAEQAA
4. Kenjayev, F. (2022). Interpretations of the Image of Jaloliddin Manguberdi in the Literature of the Independence Period. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 4, 42-45.
5. Xusanova, M. R. A. (2021). The Use Of Expressive Phonetic Means In Farida Afroz's Works. *THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE* Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука,(9), 642-645.
6. Oglu, I. N. K., & Ogli, F. K. I. (2021). Level of study of one mastic ethnologies. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(6), 487-493.
7. Matyakupov, S. G., Kenjaev, F. I., & Razzakova, M. N. (2021). Interpretation of images and expressions in the form of communication. *Academicia: an international multidisciplinary research journal*, 11(1), 967-974.

8. Салохиддинова, Н. И. (2020). Вопросы поэтического образа в поэзии. ББК: 71.01 К 90, 203.
9. Salokhiddinova, N. I. (2019). EXPRESSION OF A PASSION FOR POETRY BY ZEBO MIRZO. Theoretical & Applied Science, (12), 227-230.
10. Salohiddinova, N. (2019). Zebo Mirzo's poetry and image. International Journal on Integrated Education, 2(6), 115-118.
11. Mahametova, D. B. (2019). Specificities English Language Non-Academic Hours. Eastern European Scientific Journal, (1).
12. Dilnavoz, M. (2019). Peculiarities of teaching foreign languages with Moodle-based E-learning courses. Academy, (7 (46)), 62-64.
13. MAHAMETOVA, D. B. (2018). PROJECT METHOD IN DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENT'S PRACTICAL SKILLS AT NON-ACADEMIC HOURS OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE. Иностранные языки в Узбекистане, (2), 165-170.

Problems of the Development of the Health Care System of Our Country

Urokov Firdavs Ortikniyozovich

*Assistant, Department of Economic Analysis and Statistics,
Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service*

Abstract: This article talks about the changes in the healthcare system of our country in recent years and the main problems that arise in the development of this system.

Keywords: health care system, private sector, information and communication technologies, socio-economic development, quality of health care, financing system, estimated financing, human capital.

Changes in the health care system are covered in "Sihat-salomatlik" magazine, "Medicine Journal of Uzbekistan" and magazines related to medical fields. In our country, the organization of a high-quality health care system, which allows to maintain and improve the health of the population, and create conditions for raising a healthy generation, is the priority of the state policy.

As a result of the measures taken in our country, the efficiency, quality and convenience of providing medical services to the population have been increased, the main parameters of the UN Millennium Development Goals have been achieved. Each service group has its own characteristics¹.

During the years of independence, the achievements of our country in the field of health were positively evaluated by the international community. For example, the life expectancy of the population increased by 4.6 years from 69.1 years in 1995 to 73.7 years in 2017.

Maternal mortality decreased by 3.1 times to 21 cases per 100,000 live births, and infant mortality decreased by 3.1 times to 11.5 per 1,000 live births. formed a situation. The level of coverage with vaccination and preventive measures against the most common diseases in children remains firmly at 96-98 percent.

The introduction of comprehensive prevention, anti-epidemic and sanitary-hygiene measures to fight against infectious diseases prevents the occurrence of extremely dangerous infectious diseases (plague, cholera), poliomyelitis, diphtheria, infant tetanus, local malaria, measles and rubella. provided full protection. Certificates from the World Health Organization were received on the eradication of wild poliomyelitis (2002), measles and rubella (2017), and malaria (2018).

At the same time, there are still some problematic issues and negative situations in the organization of health care that prevent the effective resolution of tasks related to the further improvement of the citizens' health care system.

¹Ortikniyozovich U. F. The Significance of Theoretical Concepts of Services and Service Activity //American Journal of Economics and Business Management. – 2022. – T. 5. – №. 6. – C. 43-45.

In particular, the absence of comprehensive legal regulation of the network, the excessive number of legal and departmental documents in the field of prevention of diseases with a high probability of causing death and disability and social protection of the population from them, ensuring the stability of the health care system does not allow. The lack of regulation of areas in high demand such as transplantology, assisted reproductive technologies, and telemedicine causes the national healthcare system to lag behind the modern achievements of medical science and practice.

To date, conditions have not been created for the introduction of the mandatory medical insurance system. As a result, the financing of the health care sector is still carried out mainly at the expense of budget funds. In the republic, there are no clinical cost groups that are inextricably linked with clinical recommendations (protocols) and standards of medical services.

The effectiveness of prevention, patronage and timely treatment-diagnosis of the primary healthcare system, including the completion of outpatient treatment, remains unsatisfactory. As a result, expensive inpatient care takes the main place in the public health care system. It is noted that the level of patronage service to the population, especially children and women of childbearing age, is low (72-77%), the level of knowledge and skills of general practitioners does not allow providing full medical care to mothers and children.

Obstacles to the active involvement of the rapidly developing private sector of health care in cooperation with state medical organizations do not allow the effective use of additional financial resources for health care.

At the same time, the slow implementation of modern systems of training and retraining of medical personnel and, as a result, the insufficient level of professional knowledge of doctors and paramedics have a negative impact on the quality of medical services.

The low level of social and material protection of medical workers, the fact that their social and legal status does not correspond to the level of responsibility imposed on them creates conditions for the exit of qualified personnel from the system and the occurrence of corruption.

Inadequate implementation of information and communication technologies in the health care system, the large volume of medical documents in paper form does not allow for quick monitoring of the execution of decisions and effective implementation, and also causes excessive bureaucracy and high costs. .

The above-mentioned shortcomings do not make it possible to meet the ever-increasing demands of the population for the quality of health care, to respond quickly to the problems that have accumulated in the areas, and to achieve positive changes in the field of medical services.

In this regard, there was a need to create a conceptual new model of health care through the successful implementation of the concept of development of the health care system in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2025, which includes the following goals, tasks and main directions.

The implementation of regulatory legal documents issued within the scope of the Ministry's authority is mandatory for state agencies, enterprises, institutions, organizations, and in general for all public associations and individuals located in the Republic of Uzbekistan, regardless of the form of ownership. The Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the agencies operating in the field of health in the region and the city of Tashkent, their departments in cities and districts are the only health management in the republic. forms the office system.

The Ministry is a legal entity and has the right to manage its own property, income and expenses, bank accounts and own a seal with its name and the image of the coat of arms of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The health sector is one of the factors that directly affect the socio-economic development of the country. Because it is important for the country - it is a sector responsible for human capital and public health.

In the conditions of the market economy, no sector, including healthcare, can develop without an effective financing system. The estimated financing system in the health sector is based on outdated mechanisms that do not correspond to international practice. Because it leads to inefficient use of financial resources and chronic underfunding of the sector. The limitation of financial resources, increasing the efficiency of their use is one of the important problems of the health sector that needs to be solved.

Medical of the Population of Sirdarya Region Insurance Transition Experience

Urokov Firdavs Ortikniyozovich

*Assistant, Department of Economic Analysis and Statistics,
Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service*

Abstract: It is known that in recent years, under the leadership of the President of our country, within the framework of measures to improve the primary link of the healthcare system and create a healthy lifestyle among the population, the primary link of medicine problems in the industry were analyzed and specific tasks for radical reform of the industry were defined. This article provides detailed information about the experience of the residents of Syrdarya region in transitioning to medical insurance.

Keywords: healthcare system, medical insurance, insurance mechanisms, electronic registry, qualified personnel, medical personnel, insurance market.

Improving the efficiency of spending the allocated funds, in turn, requires reforming the system of financing medical institutions. Each service group has its own characteristics¹.

Last year, at the initiative of the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, WHO experts, in cooperation with local experts, developed a technical and economic basis for the introduction of mandatory medical insurance in our country. The process of reforms based on this is ongoing.

In particular, the concept approved by the decree of the President "On comprehensive measures for the fundamental improvement of the health care system of the Republic of Uzbekistan" includes the fundamental reform of the financing of the health care sector, medical insurance this year the tasks of adopting the law, using this system as a trial in the Syrdarya region from 2021, and gradually transitioning to the health insurance system at the national level by 2025 were determined.

Under the leadership of the President of our country, within the framework of measures to improve the primary link of the health care system and create a healthy lifestyle among the population, the problems in the primary link of medicine were analyzed and the field specific tasks for radical reform were defined. In order to finance packages of medical services and medicines guaranteed by the state, it was mentioned that it is necessary to introduce mechanisms of state medical insurance and to establish a separate fund.

In the decision of the head of our state, adopted on November 12, 2021, "On measures to introduce a new model of the health care system and mechanisms of state medical insurance in the Syrdarya region", system information, primary medical and sanitary care institutions, medical Tasks such as evaluation and promotion of employees' activities, development of a state-guaranteed package of medical services and medicines at the level of each medical institution were defined. In the decision, the task of establishing the state medical insurance

¹Ortikniyozovich U. F. The Significance of Theoretical Concepts of Services and Service Activity //American Journal of Economics and Business Management. – 2022. – T. 5. – №. 6. – C. 43-45.

fund, introducing and managing medical insurance, financing the medical services provided under the guaranteed package, and monitoring the effectiveness of the allocated funds is entrusted to it. At the moment, the fund has been registered as a state institution, and now the process of forming it with qualified personnel and technical equipment is underway.

From July 1, 2021 to the end of 2022, it is planned to introduce state medical insurance mechanisms in all cities and districts of the Syrdarya region, analyze the results of the experiment, and gradually introduce its positive results in other regions of the republic from 2023.

The main goal of the introduction of the state medical insurance system is prevention of diseases, early detection, provision of qualified and high-quality services at the primary level of medical care, health level of the population, average life expectancy. is to increase the duration. The introduction of this system with the wide use of information and communication technologies allows to ensure the exchange of information between the participants and to obtain the necessary information for medical workers and patients.

In the project, it is planned to create an electronic register of the population, to enter the information about the patient's referral, his illness, which doctor he saw, diagnosis and treatment conditions into the electronic database. This, in turn, makes it possible to prevent diseases, forecast, and evaluate the performance of doctors.

Due to the fact that the current system does not provide for the population to pay deductions (contributions) for medical insurance from their income, and this system is not mandatory and is implemented at the expense of the state budget, it is called State Medical Insurance was designated as system. The main goal of this system is to cover all layers of the population of our country with quality and qualified medical care.

In the new system, "brigades" consisting of a family doctor and his five assistant nurses will be organized in primary medical and sanitary care facilities, each "brigade" is planned to provide services to up to 3,000 residents. A package of medical services and medicines guaranteed by the state will be developed. Expanding the authority of family doctors, providing referrals for free treatment to patients, and giving prescriptions for free medicines is aimed at increasing their prestige.

The introduction of state health insurance requires full information of the health care system. As a result of this, an electronic list of the attached population will be created, a medical database will be created for patients, connecting medical organizations in the system to the national unified information system of health care, ensuring mutual information exchange, and limiting the amount of free and paid medical care for the population. it is possible to determine.

The involvement of private medical organizations in the state medical insurance system is aimed at developing a competitive environment in the medical services market and improving the quality of services provided to the population.

Developmental Approach to the Formation of Antimonopoly Policy in the Digital Economy

Shakarov Davron Ulashboyevich

Graduate student of Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Xoliqulov Anvar Nematovich

Associate Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service, Candidate of Economic Sciences

Abstract: This article describes in detail the way to prepare for the formation of anti-monopoly policy in the context of the digital economy. Also, the main tasks of ensuring the implementation of the territorial aspects of the formation of anti-monopoly policy, carrying out interrelated financial, anti-monopoly and price policies, creating a competitive environment and developing market relations are indicated.

Keywords: Competition, economics, monopoly, perfect competition, imperfect competition, oligopoly, pure monopoly.

It is no exaggeration to say that competition is a special "center of gravity" of the system of market relations. This "center of gravity" reflects the mutual relations aimed at determining the price of market participants and the amount of supply of goods, and also applies to determining the price and market demand of consumers and producers. Competition means to compete. Competition is a mutual struggle between market participants for the sale of goods and the best production. Competition entered people's lives as soon as personal society appeared. Throughout the development period, mankind has been looking for natural resources, bright and warm place, comfortable living and working conditions for unlimited use of limited resources. Competition manifests itself differently in different periods at different times and under different conditions.

There are positives and negatives to competition. The positive aspects of competition are that it leads to an efficient distribution of resources and develops entrepreneurial activity. In competition, consumer demand takes the main place, therefore it serves to direct resources to production areas with high consumer demand. Competition encourages entrepreneurs to attract new technologies. One of the most important features of competition is that the main attention is paid to the independence of entrepreneurs, economic activity is not built on the basis of administrative control, and this gives an opportunity to fully satisfy the interests of entrepreneurs.

The negative side of competition is that competition can create or distort market equilibrium. Because the constant change of prices depending on the changes in supply and demand does not allow the subjects in the market to maintain their position at the same time. The presence of competition forces an entrepreneur to use such methods to make a profit and maintain his position in the market, which in turn can lead to unwise use of natural resources, discrediting his competitor, and misleading consumers.

In the market system, competition can be divided into perfect and imperfect types.

Perfect competition is competition in which the number of sellers and buyers in the market is so large that they cannot independently influence the purchases in the market and use their monopoly position to lead the market participants in their footsteps. In addition, in this situation, the scope of the struggle is very large, and the freedom to enter and leave the network and to receive information about this network is guaranteed. In this case, all participants produce the same type of products and goods, and market purchases are formed on the basis of supply and demand. But it is very difficult for us to meet this form of competition in this life.

- The characteristics of perfect competition are:
- The number of competitors in the market is very large and it is not possible to combine them, all participants participate in the market at the expense of their own opportunities and risks;
- The product is the same variety - there are no differences in terms of standard, quality;
- Small enterprises produce a very small amount of products and independently do not affect the production capacities of other participants;
- There will be no legal-organizational, financial-technological restrictions on entering the network;
- Since it is a standard product, it will not be possible to change the competition without buying, because the product will not have significant differentiating signs to demonstrate its quality.
- Imperfect competition is the reverse of perfect competition and is either monopolistic in nature or somewhat restricted in nature. Basically, companies with a large market share compete here. Monopoly, oligopoly, pure monopoly and monopolistic competition are forms of competition.
- In monopolistic competition, a small but large number of producers offer identical but similar goods. The difference between this competition and pure monopoly is that the number of producers will not be very large, and as a result, they will not be able to collude with each other.
- Characteristics of a monopolistically competitive market:
- The number of firms will not be large;
- There is no opportunity for firms to negotiate secretly and control prices;
- Each firm can conduct its own policy without the participation of other firms;
- Quality differentiation: raw materials, quality, design, production, durability;
- The firm's market share is not very large and they significantly affect the formation of the price;
- Products are not classified;
- Advertising, trademark and brand of the product are different;
- It is easy for new enterprises to enter this system;
- There are forms of price and non-price competition;
- Commonly found in retail trade and light industry.
- Oligopolistic competition usually occurs on a narrow scale, in which a few but large manufacturing firms participate and control the majority of production. In an oligopoly, it is difficult for new firms to enter the industry, because a large investment is required to

compete with a large firm. In industries dominated by oligopoly, differentiated and standardized goods are produced.

- Features of oligopoly:
- The number of firms is not very large;
- Products are standardized and differentiated;
- Network access is limited and price control is high;
- In the formation of the price, the attitude and reaction of competitors is studied, due to which it is coordinated.
- Examples of oligopolistic competition are mobile communications, cotton processing and metallurgical industries. But these firms face competition from larger firms abroad.
- A pure monopoly is a firm or organization that has absolute dominance in the market, can influence the market price, the volume of goods and services. Monopoly markets exist in all countries, including those with strong antitrust regulations.
- The characteristics of a pure monopoly market are:
- A single firm operates in the network;
- Control over the price is in his hands and he can set the price as he wants;
- The product is extremely unique or cannot be replaced by another type;
- There is no opportunity for new participants to enter the network, which is due to economic, financial, legal, political and technological barriers;
- It is not possible to organize a market without a price tool.
- An example of a pure monopoly can be given in our republic: public utilities, plastering enterprises, "Shortangazkimyo", etc.
- Above, we studied the forms of competition and monopoly: In conclusion, it can be said that both perfect competition and imperfect competition have their own positive and negative aspects. There is no economic development without competition, but monopoly cannot be completely eliminated, because some industries are monopolistic, so if we take railways as an example, if a company wants to compete by building another railway, it will take a long time and a lot of money, and this will affect society and the economy. there is no use or need.

I think it depends on strong state policy to keep these in balance. The state must control everything. In order to speed up the formation of the anti-monopoly policy in the digital economy, it is advisable to implement the following first of all:

- to transform the system of competition protection and development and to create a completely new advanced model of antimonopoly regulation that meets the high requirements of the structural changes and processes taking place in the national economy and the world economy;
- introduction of flexible means and methods of analysis of commodity and financial markets, including those based on the principles of behavioral economics;
- introduction of preventive means for the protection of competition, including the mechanism of antimonopoly compliance - the system of ensuring compliance with the requirements of the competition law, first of all, among business entities that occupy a dominant position in the commodity and financial markets;

- radical improvement of the system of state regulation of prices (tariffs) of goods (works, services) due to the introduction of new highly effective methods of forming incentive tariffs, which have a strengthening effect on competition, and mechanisms for controlling their use;
- creating effective means of antimonopoly regulation of the digital economy, including in order to prevent cross-border forms of competition law violations;
- strengthening enforcement measures for infringements of competition law requirements and simultaneously abolishing discretionary powers;
- strengthen mutual cooperation with law enforcement agencies in order to identify and put an end to complex types of anti-competitive actions, such as "cartel" agreements and collusions;
- Implementation of the most important performance indicators (KPI) of the Anti-Monopoly Committee using the indicators of the development of the competitive environment in the commodity and financial markets according to the methodology of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development;
- introduction of innovative developments and information technologies in the activities of the Anti-Monopoly Committee in order to increase the speed of determining cases of restriction of competition and taking measures against them;
- Systematic increase of personnel capacity of the Anti-Monopoly Committee, introduction of special courses on training of personnel in the field of competition policy and competition law into educational programs of higher educational institutions;
- improving the efficiency of the Anti-Monopoly Committee and preventing various factors that cause corruption, taking into account social guarantees in terms of adequate financial support and social conditions.
- In the conditions of the digital economy, the main tasks of ensuring the implementation of the territorial aspects of the formation of anti-monopoly policy, conducting interrelated financial, anti-monopoly and price policies, creating a competitive environment and developing market relations are:
 - Coordination of formation and implementation of unified anti-monopoly and pricing policy in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, creation of a stable basis for social protection of consumers from monopolistic competition and unjustified increase in prices and tariffs;
 - development and introduction of proposals for improvement of antimonopoly and price legislation;
 - to stimulate the activities of parallel productions in monopolistic industries and in the field of circulation, to form a multi-system economy, to support free competition and to develop market infrastructures, to implement specific measures to regulate the prices of monopolistic enterprises;
 - to take measures to prevent the activities of certain economic entities that lead to restriction of competition, prevent the normal functioning of the market, discriminate the interests of other enterprises, organizations and citizens, artificially create deficits and provide excessive monopoly profits;
 - implementing measures aimed at gradually reducing the area of administrative regulation of purchase, wholesale, retail prices and tariffs, expanding the area of contractual free prices together with measures for social protection of the population;

- control over reasonable formation of prices and tariffs of republican corporations, associations of concerns, enterprises and organizations, regardless of the form of ownership;
- the free price setting in the national economy of the republic, price analysis and operational assessment in the Commonwealth countries and the world market are defined.

Linguistic Analysis of Uzbek Virtual Communication

Guli Toirova Ibragimovna

Doctor of philological sciences, professor, Bukhara State University, Uzbekistan, Bukhara

Yusupova Alfiya Shavketovna

Doctor of philological sciences, professor of the Department of General Linguistics and Turkology at the Kazan Federal University, Russia, Kazan

Abstract: The article takes into account the fact that communication between people occurs verbally and non-verbally, and virtual communication takes the form of direct (PC, chat) and indirect (email, forum, teleconference). The virtual conversation consists in the following: mass communication; communication direction: from long to long; synchronous connection; average recipient notification rate; such features as the absence of strict requirements for the form and content of the message. Factors shaping the process of communication in virtual space, the analysis of Internet communication, the virtuality of computer communication, mediation, the computer form of speech, the integration of all kinds of sentences, specific computer ethics, the creativity of computer texts. The article emphasizes the need to study on the basis of a communicative-pragmatic approach to virtual communication.

Keywords: virtual speech communication, communicative process, communicative space, forum, global and regional network, audiovisual communication, Internet, chat, virtuality, cyberspace.

I. Introduction.

In world practice, special attention is paid to the fact that the development of information and communication technologies increases the competitiveness of countries in all aspects, collects and summarizes a large flow of information, and creates wide opportunities for organizing management at a strategic level. In particular, development puts the problem of speech discourse in the virtual communicative space on the agenda, in which it is important to distinguish the components of the communication model, to study the sociocultural and pragmatic features of the speech discourse in the virtual communicative space.

In world linguistics, extensive work is being carried out in the areas of pragmalinguistics, cognitive linguistics, especially linguistic analysis of speech realities in anthropocentric paradigms, checking of lexical units in cyberlinguistics, aimed at researching these problems. In particular, due to the fact that speech communication in cyberspace is carried out using natural language, special attention is paid to the semiotics of Internet conversations, the psycholinguistic and socio-cultural features of communication texts, and the development of pragmalinguistics.

Literature review

In European linguistics, in the second half of the 20th century, attention to the study of cyberlinguistics increased. In this regard, among others, S. Haring, A. Dijk van Teun, J. Baudrillard, N. Fanyan, Yu.M. The scientific research of Skrebnev deserves special recognition. The field of computer speech analysis in Russian linguistics, N.D. on the theory of computer speech representations. Arutyunova, E.N. Galichkina, V.I. Karasik, A.G. Baranov, M.M. Bakhtin's studies should be cited. In Uzbek linguistics, Sh. Safarov, S. Mominov, M. Hakimov, N. Turniyozov, S. Muhamedova, S. Boymirzaeva studied problems

such as statistical analysis of text composition, pragmatic features of text, text syntax, and its grammatical construction.

II. Analysis

Distinguishes two main types of speech communication: personal (person-oriented) speech communication and collective speech communication. In the first case, the speaker appears as a person with a rich inner world, and in the second case, as a representative of a certain social institution. Therefore, collective speech is defined as communication within the framework of relationships according to its established status. It distinguishes the following types of speech in modern society: political, diplomatic, administrative, legal, military, pedagogical, religious, mystical, medical, business, advertising, sports, scientific, theatrical and public information.

However, V.I. According to Karasik, this list can be expanded again, because community-based institutions are fundamentally different from each other and cannot be considered the same phenomena, moreover, they are historically variable, merge with each other and appear in one form or another. can be Collective speech is divided into types based on two system-forming features: goals and communication participants. For example, the goal of political speech is to gain and maintain power, pedagogical speech - to socialize a new member of society, medical speech - to provide qualified assistance to the patient, etc.

V.I.Karasik emphasizes the contrast between individual and collective discourses, and that each type is characterized by its own dimension of the relationship between its status and individual aspects. For example, the share of personal components in pedagogical speech communication is very high, and in scientific and business speech communication, the personal component is slightly less. In determining the status of a certain type of speech communication, it is important to interpret it in the direction of "individual/community"

We can also observe personal (person-oriented) speech communication and collective speech communication when communicating over a computer network. When using a computer as a data transmission channel, the following tasks are performed: 1) solving practical computing problems; 2) any set of texts and their storage in computer memory; 3) coding of non-textual information (output to media, audio, graphic and video files).

The remoteness of the communicants and the specific technology of modern computers are the characteristics of indirect communication. It has the following characteristics: virtuality, that is, the ability to communicate with a conditional, unfamiliar interlocutor; globality, that is, the ability to communicate with any user on the network; hypertextuality, i.e. the complementarity of transmission of messages in applications in different writing modes (text and multimedia).

The Uzbek virtual communicative dialogue unanimously reflects the characteristics of the Uzbek people's mentality. Conversation based on moral and psychological support and free communication in the style of conversation is embedded in the dialogue mode. Here, emotional communication, mini-stories, jokes, anecdotes are typical aspects of dialogue. In some cases, it is expressed through "emojicons"[3].

The first sign of Uzbek discourse etiquette in the virtual communicative space is related to the unwritten requirements of society. For example, if you want to be in this group, big or small, national or social, you must obey certain rules of communication. That is, you need to answer the question (using words or some symbol). This is reflected in the communicative field as follows: Erkin: Do you want Ranogulli tea? Farhad: Thank you, but I don't like tea very much. Free: If you don't want to, you don't have to.

With the help of the word "thank you", it is seen that people have positive feelings, joy and love for each other, and there is a culture specific to the Uzbek people.

The second sign is the maintenance of etiquette, in which the performance of behavioral signs by the addressee of the etiquette is perceived as a social "push". For example: Hello - Be healthy; Thank you - Good day; I'm sorry - I admit my guilt; Like thank you. Virtual communicative discourse is written without paying attention to punctuation and spelling. For example: Hello!, Thank you (hard and soft "h" are not distinguished) or various emoticons are represented by emoticons.

As the level of thinking of a person is reflected in the speech of culture, we believe that it is necessary to observe the norms of literary language in virtual communication as well. Violation of literary language standards in virtual communication damages the purity of the Uzbek language.

The third sign is to observe the rules of etiquette. The utterance of an etiquette expression is called a speech act or a speech act, that is, a specific action is performed with the help of speech. For example: I give advice, I promise, I thank you.

The fourth sign is the observance of etiquette standards. In connection with the third, concepts such as "I" and "you" are clearly defined thoughts.

In the virtual communicative space, Uzbek discourse is symmetrical. It is based on equality and "own" attitude. This is a special kind of communication. In such communication, one can visually identify "ones". The position is different. Here the main role (task) belongs to the admin, that is, the manager. It monitors compliance with computer communication standards and has the authority to take action against violators[5,8].

As we mentioned above, written text is the basis of Chat communication. All messages are typed on a computer keyboard, which excludes the use of graphology in the linguistic study of Chat. Communicators do not have any influence on the graphic display of letters (fonts) on the communicator's monitor. Although handwritten text and human speech can differ significantly depending on the author, the printed text in a Chat communication does not convey any non-verbal information about the communicator.

For this reason, women around the city of Samarkand used to greet men with "assalam" in a shortened form of general greeting. According to Sh. Iskandarova, who conducted a study on some features of Uzbek women's speech, women's words such as "aylanay", "orgulay", "tokandik" are lexical tools that express the subtlety of a positive meaning, they are used more often by older women in various situations of speech habit[14].

The lexical and phraseological characteristics of Uzbek men's and women's speech are more evident, especially in cursing and cursing.

Conclusion

The active development of information technologies and their use in everyday life created problems between the computer and man, which became the basis for the analysis of symbolic, traditional and indexical classification of signs and their interaction in the language system (paradigmatic, syntagmatic). In the virtual communicative space, a sign is performed by opening the encrypted meaning in a sign message, i.e. decoding, it performs the communicative and pragmatic functions of language.

Its expression through language differs from ordinary written text, with the use of numbers through numbers, symbols and idiomatic letters instead of words. In the process of Uzbek virtual communication, such differentiation serves as a sociocultural and pragmatic factor.

Initial phatic tools actively used in chat include non-speech prompting tools in addition to greeting initials. Among the initial replicas, replicas with a pragmatic function aimed at finding a communication partner: a) by gender and age; b) by regions; c) according to the parameters of a person's character; g) replicas on the discussion of a specific topic stand out.

References:

1. Toirova, G., (2019). The Role of Setting in Linguistic Modeling. *International Multilingual Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(9):722-723, available at: <http://imjst.org/index.php/vol-4-issue-9-september-2019/>.
2. Toirova, G., (2020). About the technological process of creating a national corpus. *Foreign languages in Uzbekistan*, 2(31):57-64, available at: <https://journal.fledu.uz/uz/2-31-2020>.
3. Toirova, G., (2019). Importance of Interface in Creating Corpus. // *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)* ISSN: 2277-3878, Volume-8 Issue-2S10, September 2019. –P.352-355..
4. Toirova G., Yuldasheva M., Elibaeva I. Importance of Interface in Creating Corpus. // *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)* ISSN: 2277-3878, Volume-8 Issue-2S10, September 2019. –P.352-355. (scopus)
5. Toirova G., Jurayeva O., Abulova Z., Norova M., Norova F. Application of Innovative Technologies in Teaching Process. // *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, Vol. 24, Special Issue 1, 2020. ISSN: 1475-7192.–P.386-390. (scopus)
6. Toirova G. Establishment of a national corpus the uzbek language is a requirement of a new era. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR)*. Vol 10, Issue9, September, 2021 (Impact factor)
7. Toirova G, Abdurahmonova N., Ismoilov A., Applying Web Crawler Technologies for Compiling Parallel Corpora as one Stage of Natural Language Processing. 2022 7th International Conference on Computer Science and Engineering (UBMK) Sep. 14 - 16, 2022, Diyarbakir /Turkey pp. 73–75. (scopus)
8. Тоирова Г.И. Халилова Р.Р. Нуткий мулоқот ва виртуал нуткий мулоқот имкониятлари. // Таълим ва инновацион тадқиқотлар. Халқаро илмий-методик журнал. –2020 йил, – № 2. – В.76-80.
9. Бубнова Г.И., Гарбовский Н.К. Письменная и устная коммуникация. Синтаксис и просодия. - М., 1991.
10. Телия В.Н. Коннотативный аспект семантики номинативных единиц. - М., 1986.
11. Шмелев А. Д. Дискурсные слова как отражение этнокультурных стереотипов поведения // Речевые и ментальные стереотипы в синхронии и диахронии: Тез. конф. - М., 1995.
12. Шейгал Е.И. Компьютерный жаргон как лингвокультурный феномен // *Языковая личность: культурные концепты*: Сб. науч. тр. Волгоград - Архангельск, 1996.
13. Мўминов С.М. Ўзбек мулоқот хулқининг ижтимоий-лисоний хусусиятлари. Филол.фан.доктори ... дисс. - Т., 2000. - Б.235 .
14. Искандарова Ш. Ўзбек нутқ одатининг мулоқот шакллари. НД.-Самарқанд, 1993-Б.67.
15. Yusupova, A.S., Mugtasimova, G.R., Zakirzyanova, G.Z., Khisamitdinova, F.G. Functioning of Tatar Medical Vocabulary in Bilingual Dictionaries of the Xix Century. *Res Militaris*, 2022, 12(3), pp. 289–296

16. Kasemu S., Yusupova A.S., Denmukhametova E.N., Khisamitdinova, F.G. Synonyms in explanatory dictionary of Turkic languages. *Journal of Research in Applied Linguistics* this link is disabled, 2019, 10(SpecialIssue), pp. 1025–1032, 518
17. Ashrapova, A.H., Yusupova, A.S. Language and national identity in linguistic dictionaries (on material of bilingual dictionary of the tatar language of the 19th century and the turn of the 20th century) *Journal of Language and Literature*, 2015, 6(1), pp. 318–321

Environmental Problems of the Modern Conditions

*Bekniyazova Dilfuza Bazarbay qizi , Uteniyazov Azizbek Sarsenbay uli , Nurtaeva Dilnaz Xojabaevna
Karakalpak State University*

Abstract: Throughout human activity environmental problems rose in all growth and always demanded acceptance of urgent measures for their decision. Proceeding from that the mankind has learned essence of these problems in some degree has learned to overcome them to create optimum conditions for accommodation. However despite scientific ensuring greening of all spheres of human life, many of earlier existing, and again arising environmental problems still haven't found rather full scientific justification for the purpose of their prevention. Environmental problems are today, environmental problems of the surrounding environment and in general environmental management requires the attentive and urgent solution as human activity, losing the naturalness everything more gains social character.

Keywords: nature; wednesday; ecology; safety; territory; environmental management; natural resources; quality; pollution; desertification; dryness.

Nature is a complex constructive mechanism for regulating the entire process life within the framework of the system "man - nature - nature management". In this complex system, human activity acquires a nature-transforming character, where a person manifests himself as an active, interacting subject within environment, he, as K. Marx noted, mediates, regulates and controls the metabolism between himself and nature. Such a complex interaction of man with the natural environment has a significant impact on the nature of man in essence.

At the same time, the negative manifestation of negative factors in the environment the natural environment is caused, first of all, by insufficient knowledge of the ongoing processes, as well as the incorrect use of scientific and technological achievements, designed to ensure the formation and development of rational nature management. Thus, when it comes to the influence of natural factors on society, then it is important to distinguish between aspects that affect society, regardless of the needs of its development, and those conditions that are used by people and are included in system, but at the same time remain natural elements. However, during the impact natural elements on the social system, contradictions arise, bearing outward character. Their role is very significant in the development of society. They can generally lead to the cessation of this development, to the destruction of society as a system.

The interaction of man and nature has always depended on the state of the environment. Natural habitat throughout the evolutionary development of mankind. However dependence did not remain constant, but changed dialectically contradictory way. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the ongoing deep processes in the environment, which have a diverse content and quality influence on all human life, transforming it, changing its character and view of the phenomena occurring in nature. As a result, the surrounding natural the environment is subject to change not only through the fault of natural catastrophic phenomena, but also through the fault of directly human activity, for example, not entirely reasonable cutting down of green spaces, the destruction of grassy cover without appropriate remedial measures, which ultimately leads to the depletion of the natural environment. In

addition, there is ill-conceived disposal and use of household and industrial waste, ineffective measures are being taken to combat wind and water erosion of soils, desertification of arid lands, which leads to a decrease in soil fertility, lowering groundwater levels and ultimately climate change in respective territories. All these negative changes in the natural environment have a direct negative impact on the nature of man himself, on his natural character. These changes are the cause of the emergence of new diseases, changes in the genetic content of the human body and so on.

The evolutionary development of the natural environment had an impact on the natural climatic state of the environment, prompting living organisms, including human, adapt to all kinds of changes in temperature, humidity on separate territories. At the same time, man, as a higher natural being, changed places dwellings, built dwellings, and so on. In modern conditions, man has acquired sedentary lifestyle and is active in the use of natural resources and the natural environment, based on their needs, as well as simultaneously engaged in the reproduction or restoration of individual natural plots. However, such activities, as practice shows, are not fully ensures the restoration of the natural balance necessary to increase the intensity of life on planet Earth. At the same time, transboundary knowledge about the impact of the environmental factor on the state of the environment, as well as the formed ecological thinking do not allow to adequately assess the entire volume of that ecological load, which has a negative impact on the entire natural activity. Therefore, increasing the level of scientific research in the field of formation of the process of greening natural, socio-economic, organizational, legal, technological and information systems in modern conditions, i.e. under conditions of high intensity of nature-transforming and nature protection actions, becomes very relevant both for the conservation nature itself, as well as for the protection of human health.

The growth of scientific research in areas of ecology and nature management in recent years indicates a large positive shifts in the development of productive forces in all spheres environmental activities, on the one hand, and on the other hand, a decree Occurring processes in the natural environment, in the intensification of science and technology are commendable, because it is in this that the social and scientific and technical nature of the system "man - nature -nature management". The analysis shows that the most application of those high technologies in the field of nature management, which have environmentally sound nature due to their focus on carrying out high-quality human activity, all these projects and their structural parts provided, as a rule, with an environmental component, which ultimately predetermines the formation of an environmentally safe situation in the developed areas of the earth's surface.

In general, as practice confirms, scientific approaches to solving urgent environmental problems in the field of socio-economic policy is not fully ensure the preservation of the natural potential of individual territories, i.e. arises the need for new scientific and technical, high-tech developments information and development of rational environmental management in all areas industrial and intellectual activity. Thus, the use of natural resource potential, taking into account ongoing changes in its structure and content should increasingly to attract the attention of scientists and specialists to the development of high technologies for environmental protection in order to create the most favorable conditions for the existence of the animal and plant world.

To confirm the above conclusions, it can be said that accelerated desertification has reached a scale that goes far beyond the traditional approach to solving this problem. Desertification has become spontaneous and social disaster affecting many humanitarian aspects requiring close attention attention and immediate action.

At last count, in areas under immediate threat desertification, live 230 million people. Total desertification on the globe covered 3.5 billion hectares, and every year 21 million hectares

come to the state complete or almost complete disrepair. Thus, desertification is threat to humanity, since this process reduces the base life support on earth.

Desertification is the result of a long historical process, during which natural phenomena and human activity, reinforcing each other, lead to change in the characteristics of the natural environment. Desertification control and restoration of desert areas - long-term process, it requires the development and implementation of the necessary measures to combat this ailment. Desertification requires strategic decisions that would include specific short-term and long-term actions aimed at to address the structural causes of this phenomenon. To ensure that desertification is taken into account in the development of national plans development, the main actors should be clearly identified. These include government and policy-making institutions in the drylands, major landowners and companies involved in the cultivation of cash crops and animal husbandry, peasants and pastoralists, international organizations operating in these areas, the international community as a whole and, finally, scientists and professionals dealing with desertification issues.

Ultimately, the only real means to combat desertification is sustainable development. Desertification is a social, not a natural process -this was the concept adopted by the UN Conference on Desertification. However, in research and projects, the primary focus is on the physical aspects of this problem, while humanitarian ones are ignored. Social disintegration intensifies the physical process of desertification, which in turn increases the vulnerability of dryland populations and undermines its social and economic security. Thus, the social aspects associated with desertification create complex problem, which is a combination of specific conditions, types of behavior, values and beliefs, as well as organizational measures. The combination of such factors, combined with existing economic structures and policies, such as land use policies and lending tends to exacerbate the situation.

Finally, the integration of dryland populations into the international system entails new difficulties due to the need to compete in the world markets, as well as due to the emergence of new patterns of consumption. In the fight against desertification, all these factors were often ignored. Desertification, however, does not exhaust the whole depth of the economic problem, which today appears before mankind in extremely diverse manifestations. And they testify that in the face of the environmental problem worth all mankind, regardless of the international division of labor, since this problem is becoming global. In addition, it can be clearly noted that severe, unfavorable the fate of Baikal, the Aral Sea and the Caspian Sea, pollution by industrial and agricultural production of these and many other water bodies, emissions into air pool of harmful products of industrial enterprises and vehicle exhaust gases, excessive use of pesticides, herbicides, mineral fertilizers, serious changes in climatic and water regimes in the month areas adjacent to large hydraulic structures are just some of the sad consequences of thoughtless human intervention in the environment.

Today, however, our society is becoming more and more aware that to continue along this path it is impossible that the environmental problem is one of the most important problems that must be resolved in the course of revolutionary perestroika. And here it appears that the change in man's attitude to nature is mediated by deep social transformations in human life. In this regard, the stormy activity of the public, broad segments of the population in various regions of the country who oppose the construction and operation of environmentally polluted industries. This coming "from below" unprogrammed activity indicating that it is a real force in our country, has already become a factor that cannot be ignored.

Reference

1. Cheshev A.S., Vlasenko, T.V., Shevchenko, O. Yu. Ekologo-ekonomichesky mechanism of ensuring efficiency of use of urban areas. – M: High school book, 2012.
2. Cheshev A.S., Karpova, N.V., Shevchenko, O. Yu. The strategy of an organizational economic case of nature protection activities in city conditions. – Rostov-on-Don; Moscow: High school book, 2014.
3. Polyakov, V.V., Sukhomlinova, N.B., Cheshev, A.S., Ampere-second. Land and property complex of the municipality: sotsio-ekologo-economic aspects. – Rostov-on-Don: Prod. SKNTs VSh, 2015.
4. Vagin, V.S., Cheshev, Ampere-second. Greening of nature protection activities in the territory of municipalities. – Rostov-on-Don: CJSC Kniga, 2015.
5. Ганиева, М. ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ АБДУРАУФА ФИТРАТА. СЪЗ САНЪАТИ ЖУРНАЛИ JOURNAL OF WORD ART ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА, 12.

Mechanisms for Blurring Pedagogical Processes Aimed at Creative Thinking of Students

Abdrimov Inoyatbek Akhmedovich

Deputy Director of the Khorezm academic lyceum of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan for educational affairs

Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the ways and stages of development of creative abilities in students and the mechanisms of designing pedagogical processes in the educational process.

Keywords: creativity, pedagogical mechanism, creativity, will, attention, thinking.

It is known that creativity is a complex psychological process related to a person's creation and discovery of socially significant innovations in science, technology, production, culture, and other fields. Human thinking, memory, imagination, attention, and will are active. participates, knowledge, experience, talent are shown in creativity. One of the great thinkers, Abu Nasr Farabi, described that "creativity is such a great quality in the process of knowledge that a person must use all his other qualities to acquire it." In fact, in the process of creation, a person searches, observes, conducts research, analyzes the results and draws logical conclusions. Whether the conclusion is correct or incorrect is tested in an experiment.

Creative thinking is the most basic and active form of manifestation of independent thinking qualities in a person. Despite the fact that all tariffs differ sharply from each other, it is possible to point out some common aspects. First, the quality of the product obtained as a result of creative thinking should be innovative; secondly, that these aspects were not present in the initial foundations of Creative thinking; and thirdly, any creative thinking activity is determined by the fact that it requires intellectual research.

Creative thinking activity in students can be classified according to the following signs:

- *type of creativity (technical, technological, organizational, economic, social, spiritual, pedagogical, didactic, among students, mixed);*
- *level of creativity (mono creativity, multi creativity, mega creativity);*
- *scope of creativity (field of knowledge, interdisciplinary, national, regional, interregional, international);*
- *duration of creativity (short-term, medium-term, long-term);*
- *form of creativity (innovative, educational, investment, mixed);*
- *according to general aspects (implementation of new ideas; promotion of new solutions in principle; practical application of innovation);*
- *According to the meaning and complexity of the created creative product (rationalization proposal; invention; discovery).*

The analysis showed that the student's creativity is manifested by his independent thinking in problem situations related to solving problems, writing essays, experimental work, and

completing educational assignments. In our opinion, the student's creativity is the ability to relate the acquired knowledge to evidence and events in practice, to correctly evaluate and analyze the obtained results, and to be able to generalize with the previously acquired ones.

Creative activity is complicated by insufficient psychological preparation of teachers and students for this process. Relying on a certain method, form, and means on a regular basis leads to the inability to adapt to new situations and the inability to work in unexpected situations. As a psychological condition, this can be manifested in various forms, including: not accepting the opinions and opinions of others at all; strict defense of the generally accepted point of view; applying old methods to new content and tools; preservation of old methods in new methods; such as using traditional methods to solve a completely new problem.

Students should take into account two interrelated tasks when organizing creative thinking activities. The first of them is the development of students' independent thinking in the activity of creative thinking, their desire to acquire knowledge, and the formation of their scientific worldview; the second is determined by teaching to independently apply acquired knowledge in education and practical activities.

The following indicators were proposed as criteria for the formation of creativity competence in students: independent decision-making; confidence in one's own abilities; active research; speed of thinking; flexibility of thinking; originality of the idea; perfection of the idea; positive orientation of the idea; ability to process and target information; imagination; being able to connect distant thoughts; to be able to evaluate the weight of an idea; the elegance, grace and simplicity of the solution; to be able to generate many ideas; validity of the idea. Tests, problem assignments and experimental methods are used to evaluate these quality indicators.

One of the important aspects of pedagogical technologies focuses on the formation of a stable orientation to the activities of future students of the whole group. These activities are mainly carried out in the form of trainings, and the organization of practical activities on this basis has confirmed the development of students' skills to solve problematic situations related to activities. Our goal was to justify the effectiveness of pedagogical technologies developed on the basis of the methods of learning and evaluating creativity competence in students, as well as determining and applying the criteria for the formation of creativity competence.

As a result, the following tasks were successfully solved:

- *based on the analysis of the content of the continuous education system, theoretical information on the formation of students' creative thinking during the educational process was studied and summarized;*
- *The methods of learning creative thinking, as well as the criteria for the formation of creativity were determined;*
- *with the help of questionnaires, the level of students' mastery of the main concepts of creative thinking was determined;*
- *the recommendations developed in the research work on the development of creative thinking qualities in students were tested;*
- *Didactic conditions necessary for the formation of creative thinking of students of general secondary educational institutions and the effectiveness of the didactic model of the system of formation of important qualities of a creative person in students were evaluated.*

Similar criteria and methods were selected for creative, educational and problem-situation tasks developed on the basis of the educational content in forming the level of students'

creative thinking. The procedure for evaluation and monitoring of mastery indicators of the process of formation of creative thinking among students was determined and tested. The analysis of the obtained results showed that training sessions based on pedagogical technologies in the process of forming important qualities in students have achieved high effectiveness in forming creative thinking in students. Theoretical and practical exercises, knowledge that serves to form important qualities of students in the performance of tasks with problematic situations, and to strengthen skills. ensured that.

Creative thinking is a type of activity that serves to ensure the strength and perfection of students' acquired knowledge, to form active and independent thinking personality traits in them, and to develop their mental abilities. This situation is especially important in mastering the fundamentals of science for future specialists, and then introducing approaches based on creative thinking in students while directly leading this process. From the point of view of research, we clarified the concepts of creative thinking knowledge, skills, and abilities specific to the personality of the student. Including: Knowledge of creative thinking - a systematic reflection in the human mind as a product of cognitive activity of concepts and imaginations required for the development of a new solution; It was determined that creative thinking skills represent a person's level of rapid and complete implementation of mental process stages in goal-oriented creative activity. Creative thinking skills mean the level of a person's ability to perform creative activities in a partially automated manner, understanding only the first stages of the mental process.

Factors for the development of students' creative thinking should be the basis of educational activities in every subject and every lesson. As the activity of creative thinking covers all aspects of teacher and student activity, we believe that its effective organization serves to ensure the quality of the entire educational process. Acquaintance with scientific and technical information plays an important role in the development of creative thinking. It serves as an important resource to provide readers with newsletters, information on scientific terms, and information on invention and patent science materials. Close cooperation with experts in the field of information technology and patent studies, regular familiarization with periodicals related to these fields will give positive results.

It requires the formation of an important source of innovative ideas and technologies in qualified students, along with the training of creative specialists. In this work, the concept of creative thinking was adopted as an activity process aimed at creating a product of creative thinking as an intellectual property based on the integration of knowledge, skills and abilities of students with scientific and technical knowledge and education-science-production.

In our opinion, general secondary school students should be prepared for innovative activities on the basis of creative thinking, master the mechanisms of updating production and industry technologies, imagine the dynamics of their future activities, understand the importance of acquiring practical knowledge, It creates opportunities to clarify the direction of one's further activities, gain experience in active practical work, and develop skills for working with scientific information. In the process of interaction with students, the teacher must take into account their value system, their desire for creative self-development in students, and their level of consciousness. As long as a person is not based on high values and ideas, he does not understand the importance of personal qualities and the processes of developing students' creativity, as a result, the creativity of the teacher and the student in mutual cooperation may not be fully realized.

One of the important factors of individual development of a person is his age-related characteristics. Because each age stage of development has its own development factors, laws and changes, which have a direct impact on a person's character, temperament, abilities and cognitive processes. Adolescence is the most complex and at the same time important stage of development among the young periods of a person. The new conditions of the life and

activities of schoolboys and girls, their active educational, social and labor activities will have an impact on the formation of future specialists. Limiting attention to only one, the most basic feature in the organization of personal creative thinking does not allow to achieve the set goals. For this reason, it is necessary to look at the activity indicators of the adolescent in all areas as a general set, and pay the main attention to increasing the weight of the required characteristics.

Based on the analysis of psychological research, it was determined that the problem of creativity was studied mainly in four directions, namely: creativity as a process; creativity as a result; creativity as a skill; creativity as a personality trait. Systematicity and consistency in the acquisition of knowledge is ensured by the unity of theory and practice, the gradual introduction of State educational standards into the educational process. According to the analysis, it can be considered that the strategy of preparing students for creative thinking activities is implemented in the following directions:

- *draw students' attention to the generality and comprehensiveness of the method used to solve the problem;*
- *teaching students creative ways of thinking is considered not as the goal of the lesson, but as a new way, an opportunity aimed at more effectively solving the task set in the lesson;*
- *new ideas that students draw their own independent conclusions should be considered as the main product of creative thinking classes;*
- *collection, analysis and interpretation of information should be considered as an important aspect of establishing creative thinking;*
- *The cultivation of creative thinking qualities of an individual should be considered as an important issue of the activities held in educational institutions, which in terms of scope goes beyond the lessons and extracurricular activities.*

Design and standardization of educational content in the formation of students' creative thinking qualities, didactic conditions for the development of students' creative thinking, creative pedagogical technologies for the organization and development of students' creative thinking, intellectual activities for the organization and intensification of students' creative thinking it is appropriate to develop training systems. Teaching hours allocated for subjects based on ensuring the integrity of the educational content, paying special attention to the effective use of time by students and teachers, departments that develop the ability of young students to think independently and learn independently , problems and tests should be reflected.

In addition to the creation of guidelines and recommendations, the introduction of innovative approaches aimed at increasing the creative activity of a person in the educational process is important in ensuring the integrity of students' creative thinking. Person-oriented education first of all changes the paradigm of education. Until now, teaching has been considered a priority in the existing education system, but at the same time, in the era of information society, the priority is directed to teaching to read.

Pedagogical technologies based on the person-oriented approach in the educational process have been developed by pedagogic scientists, which consist of the following: person-oriented education; cooperative pedagogy; pedagogical adaptive technology of adaptive communication; game technology; motivational teaching technology; problematic teaching technology; differential education; technology of individual education. At the modern stage of development of pedagogical foundations in the formation of creative thinking, it is shown that there is a need to develop teaching technologies based on a new approach in determining the methodological requirements and didactic conditions for ensuring the competence of students of a general education school. In this case, the didactic conditions for the

development of students' creative thinking are based on the following: the priority of passing theoretical knowledge to practical skills and qualifications; the unity of the educational, educational and developmental environment; encouraging positive motivation for education and creative activity; problematic; the combination of individual and differential approaches; the fact that education is aimed at ensuring personal activity; educational content and didactic materials aimed at developing the student's personality.

A creative problem is not an algorithmic problem, it is similar to a standard problem and not a simple problem, but a non-standard problem aimed at developing a solution that needs to be found. The ideological side of the problem depends not only on finding its solution, but also on the attitude of the subject that satisfies the requirements of a creative approach to the problem. To understand the idea of a problem is to add this problem to the group of problems to be solved. The motivation of the educational process aims to encourage students to be active, cooperative, and participate in all stages of training with a high level of interest. The ability to arouse motivation is considered an important component of the skills of creative teachers.

Motivational pedagogical technologies ensure that students quickly enter the educational process, and on the contrary, the complexity of the assignments given beyond the standard, the abstractness of the obtained results lead to the instability of motivation. Agreeing with the opinion of M. V. Klarin, we approve the distinction between strict and flexible pedagogical technologies. Rigorous pedagogical technologies are characterized by diagnosticity and reproducibility both in relation to the process and in relation to educational results, and it reflects strict requirements for achieving educational goals. In contrast, flexible pedagogical technologies require reproducibility in relation to the implementation of the educational process, but do not require diagnostic determination of teaching results. The specific aspects of the proposed creative pedagogical technology are explained as follows:

1. Not only the entire pedagogical system, but also the orientation of each of its components: the goal, content, organizational forms, methods and educational tools, pedagogical personnel and internal educational environment to the development of individual creativity.
2. The fact that creative pedagogical technology has a systematic description both in the overall educational process and at the local pedagogical stage.
3. Independent determination of the trajectory and content of solution development by students in the performance of creative educational tasks.
4. By guiding students to creative thinking, it is aimed at forming the qualities of flexibility, mobility and a desire to develop an innovative solution in students.

Cooperation and cooperation in the introduction of creative pedagogical technologies, priority of autodidactic; principles of developmental education are followed. ***Two-way approach to the proposed technology:***

- *research approach based on practical knowledge;*
- *Can be implemented on the basis of the research approach based on theoretical knowledge.*

Creative pedagogical technology is based on the idea of a four-stage productive didactic cycle.

The 1st stage is to acquaint students with new educational material on the basis of problem-based learning, to form a creative motivation in them to learn new material, and to introduce them to the procedure for performing creative educational tasks.

The 2nd stage is the organization of creative thinking activities among students related to the development of the main features of students' creative educational assignments and their solutions.

3rd stage - the student sets independent educational tasks for himself.

The 4th stage is to start the student's independent creative activity. In this, the student learns to justify the product of creative thinking activity designed by him.

It will be possible for them to get to know different fields of labor through practical work, and they will be taught the technologies of production of consumer goods. It should be noted that social humanitarian, natural and concrete sciences mainly prepare for the choice of the field of study in academic lyceums, and technology mainly serves to prepare for the field of vocational field in general education schools.

Modeling the processes of ensuring the continuity of students' creative thinking allows for the development of scientifically based recommendations for optimizing the organization and management of these processes. Accordingly, a didactic model of the system of forming important qualities of a creative person in students was developed. It defined the goals and objectives of the system of forming important qualities in students. Also, the model reflects the process of formation of important qualities in creative students based on motivational, meaningful-informational, operational-activity and control-evaluation levels.

In turn, the didactic conditions corresponding to the motivational, meaningful-informational, operational-activity, control-evaluation levels of the implementation of these tasks were substantiated. The existing qualities were divided into the following groups depending on which students are directly related to the aspects and their influence on the personality of the student: individual-typological qualities; sensory and perceptual properties; attention features; psychomotor properties; mnemonic properties; imaginative features; features of thinking; volitional characteristics. The creative pedagogical technologies developed within the framework of the research are aimed at forming important qualities in students based on the development of creative thinking of students.

The theory of "intellectual limit" proposed by G. Perkins is widely popular, and as a result of many correlative studies, he emphasizes that a necessary and sufficient intellectual level is required to master any type of activity. If an individual's level of intelligence is below the required level, he will not be able to fully engage in this type of activity. Differences in the productivity of people with an intelligence level above the "threshold" are explained by motivation, personality traits and other similar factors, but this difference does not represent a difference in the level of intelligence.

Scientists consider creativity as a general ability of a person, regardless of the field of activity, as a factor that has a great impact on creative productivity. When including intelligence, creativity and learning in the structure of general abilities, we were based on the three-component model of cognitive processes. According to this, any cognitive process should embody the acquisition, application and modification of cognitive experience. The ability to acquire experience can be explained by learning, the efficiency of using experience by general intelligence, and its change by creativity.

In researching the effectiveness of pedagogical technology, attention was paid to the inclusion of pedagogical observation elements in the pedagogical system, that is, the implementation of this educational technology is aimed at forming important aspects in students. Because pedagogical technology based on pedagogical observation determines the limits of possibilities that must be achieved based on its correct implementation. More effective organization of the formation of important qualities in students required the introduction of new exercises and trainings into the educational process. In addition,

pedagogical observation made it possible to eliminate some defects in educational technology.

In the process of using pedagogical technologies, attention was paid to the following aspects in the implementation of pedagogical observation: defining pedagogical observation technologies; determining the effectiveness of the proposed pedagogical technologies; developing recommendations for educational institutions in order to optimize the implementation of pedagogical monitoring; development of a program for the development of important qualities in students.

REFERENCES:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. New Uzbekistan strategy. -Tashkent.: Uzbekistan. 2021. -p. 238
2. Developing the integrity of educational programs - serves to increase the quality of education. 14.09.2020 <http://marifat.uz/marifat/ruknlar/umumii-urta-talim/4889.htm>
3. Azizkho'jaeva N.N. Pedagogical technology and pedagogical skills. Tashkent. TSPU named after Nizomi, 2003 – 176 p.
4. Alimov N.N. The method of preparing vocational college students for technical creativity (in the example of teaching general vocational subjects). Ped. Science. Dissertation written to obtain a candidate's scientific degree.- T.: 2009.-233 p.
5. Lerner I. Ya. Didakticheskie osnovy metodov obucheniya. Moscow: Pedagogy, 1981. - p.48.
6. Tahirov O'O. The methodology of introducing the state educational standard and curriculum of the educational subject of technology into educational practice. // Methodical recommendation. - Tashkent.: RTM 2017. -p.65.

Methods of Temperature Management and Control at the Interface of Technological System Applications

Yo'ldoshova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi

Student of Nukus Mining Institute

Abstract: It is becoming increasingly necessary to control temperature through the automated interface of a technological system, be it in industrial, commercial or residential environments, temperature balance is important. Likewise, technology has become a common tool in everyday life. So, technologies need to be approached in modern ways and creates, changes, improves, accompanies progress in process management in many areas and works on the basis of a technological system an application interface must be created that can be used alongside these processes on mobile devices. Therefore, through this article, we suggest environmental temperature monitoring and Bluetooth wireless connection and mobile phone interface display we use an application developed in MIT App Inventor. This is when executing commands through the program hardware and software used room temperature reduction procedure vai the room temperature balance is ensured through the ventilation system. Data is collected through system-based applications and temperature sensor and wireless communication through the app. Bluetooth module both will be connected to the Arduino development board. The refrigerator can be conditioned to operate according to a preset temperature. The range is set using its IDE (Integrated Development Environment). So that's it the project is a cheap and useful alternative to temperature control and A technological system can be a monitoring method supported by development.

Keywords: Temperature control, temperature display sensor, innovation in temperature control, mobile application in the system, development boards in the system, use of wireless communication tools in the technological system.

Introduction

Temperature control is usually carried out in a technological system and used in process, object inspection and evaluation of specific conditions. A monitoring system is an action it is based on the results of the processes done to find out something about the actual planning or information recovery system. This monitoring provides information on the status and trend of repeated observations and shows the values of the assessments over time. Monitoring is usually done to check the process, object and evaluates certain conditions. This system is also used to take corrective action for all provisioning and resources are used as effectively and efficiently as possible. The monitoring process is routine implements the process of collecting data and measuring progress toward program or activity goals. Previous studies have conducted research using Internet of Things (IoT) technology for tracking and studies were conducted to ensure the temperature balance in the egg incubator. In this study, the temperature data is obtained from the sensor and then assembled into a microcontroller and then sent to the internet. Test results show that the temperature value can be read in real time using the IoT platform Blynk and can be monitored through applications on a smartphone. The Internet of Things (IoT) is a concept in which an object has the ability to transmit and creates the ability to access and create information across a network without requiring human-to-human or human-to-computer interaction. IoT is it a concept that aims to extend the benefits of a seamless internet connection that connects machines, equipment and other

physical objects with network sensors and actuators for data acquisition and regulates its activities (independently). This is a study looking at the problems of microclimatic conditions on the basis of the system it is designed to make a tool that has the ability to make microclimatic conditions. Where this tool is able to monitor the temperature if the temperature does not match, the system application temperature control indicator results will change. These are with the help of the blynk application; devices can be monitored and controlled remotely via a smartphone Accessible using IoT technology. In relation to the industrial metallurgical sector described in the previous paragraph, It was reported that mechanical, electrical and electronic systems are used process control options are shown as examples, which are used in industry. sensors such as contact thermocouple, infrared thermometer, contact pyrometer and digital or analog in cases where thermometers are used, the effectiveness of these control methods can be compromised large product requirements or specific process performance eg: controlled Temperature control of 100 tons of liquid steel volume or temperature with rod the speed is 200 m/s. The need to develop control and innovate with technological development production processes in many industries have made the creation of mobile communication a necessity forms application management. Simply put, a mobile app is purpose-built software entertaining, facilitating and connecting the user intuitively and easily becomes an access platform. On various devices, for example, smartphones and Android and IOS tablets and smart TVs, these programs help people. Informed advantages provided by wireless communication, the possibility of mobile communication The program to control the temperature was an alternative. Data communication can be done in many ways by radio, satellite, microwave ovens. infrared, 4G, 5G, Wi-Fi and bluetooth are used. The last wireless connection is, transmits the necessary data between devices, if there is a distance between them short means it depends on the proximity of the devices.

Materials and methodology

The research proposal is to monitor the temperature using a mobile application and Development boards and bluetooth communication are improved. Programming It uses Arduino and its open source IDE (Integrated Development Environment) and software is created. A monitored object temperature monitoring system is designed to help people determine temperature creates opportunities to control temperature conditions in the system. So it becomes easier for people in the process. Where there is other activity or other work, breeders are not needed. For example, the fear of leaving livestock in the pen because with this tool the breeders can control and maintains the temperature conditions in their livestock. Measurement of cage temperature parameters using the DHT22 sensor, the program is processed by the microcontroller. The temperature value is determined. Then to activate the on or off option the interface system application is also generated and connected to the NodeMCU module, so it can be configured. These are parameters are displayed on the smartphone screen through the blynk application and system communication is controlled using the Internet. Tool components are manufactured in-house so that the tool performs optimally. Placement the number of components is adapted to the use of these components. The sensor module components, relay module and power supply can be housed in a custom housing. This is for several technological processes creates conditions. After the components are arranged, the circuit for the temperature is drawn and a monitoring system is installed in this technological process. The schematic design of this circuit is an important part because it The components used in the microcontroller, such as DHT22, will be wired. As for the schematic image of the system, the module is created as follows.

Picture 1. Complete system structure

Blynk is a platform for mobile operating system (OS) applications that aim to manage Arduino and similar modules control over the internet. This the application can be used for hardware control, display of sensor data, data storage, visualization, and more. The ability of this application can store data and display numbers, colors or information visually and Graphics are generated remotely using Internet or intranet data communications. The Blynk app does this, it is possible to create interface projects with various input and output components that send and support and can receive data and provide data according to the selected component. Blynk server a cloud-based backend service entity responsible for managing communication between smartphone app and hardware environment are managed. The ability to manage dozens of things hardware devices at the same time facilitate IoT system developers. For the innovative development of the project described in the previous topic, an the interface was created using the MIT App Inventor platform. So the visual parts of it application is defined, button layouts and response boxes are set and formed in sensors. Meanwhile, a new screen appeared for aesthetic and organizational purposes created, this button is activated and its purpose is to select bluetooth and a device is found to connect to. Once the required elements for the application were identified, the code could be generated, to apply and establish its relationships with project components, It is presented in the flow chart in Picture. 2.

Picture 2. Processes built into the system interface

Conclusion

These technological processes have developed a low-cost system consisting of an electronic mobile application and devices and development boards used for temperature control are shown. Because of its low price application is viable in many commercial areas, logistics chains and industries and processes, transportation of products, and scientific research conducted in laboratories. Despite its combined innovative functionality, the project can still be improved therefore; it is more accessible, covers wider areas and is more developed functions are being improved. The highlighted innovation is described in the literature as starting stages already through the rapid development of individual parts to create new products existing infrastructure. About the developed system, Wi-Fi or Ethernet connection, in this way the necessary proximity can be built between the devices provided via bluetooth connection, no longer needed. Therefore, the project benefits from a system based on the IoT (Internet of Things) structure for control and electronic devices are controlled through a smart system. In addition, implement new commands to the application, such as increase and Temperature reduction with new buttons via IoT interface structure and ventilation facilities enrich the current project. That would be it becomes another system with remote temperature control easy-to-access interface, monitored and used in real time. Otelbayev Azizbek, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute under the Navoi State University of Mining and Technologies, is currently conducting scientific research on the optimization and automation of technological processes in mining processes, and the use of robotization processes in mining enterprises. Azizbek's interest in the technological activities of mining enterprises is very high. Otelbayev Azizbek's many articles about processes in mining enterprises were published in international magazines. Currently, Azizbek is promoting the use of the development stages of technologies in mining enterprises. which can further increase performance indicators. I wish Otelbayev Azizbek, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute,

good luck in his work and scientific research. Azizbek's articles on technologies and technological processes in mining enterprises were published in international magazines. He is very interested in technological processes, currently studying computer systems management, applications used in mining enterprises. Azizbek is a 4th year student and has been following the processes in mining enterprises for a long time. He is interested in mining and loading processes, flotation and beneficiation processes, and the structure of metal melting furnaces in mining enterprises.

References

1. Qizi, Y. H. B. . (2023). Setting the Time Mode in the Process of Automating Robots. *Pioneer : Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress*, 2(4), 37–46. Retrieved from <https://innosci.org/jarsp/article/view/1133>
2. Qizi, Y. H. B. (2023). Use of Wireless Technologies in the Automation of Technological Processes. *International Journal on Orange Technologies*, 5(4), 7-16. Retrieved from <https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJOT/article/view/4256>
3. Qizi, Y. H. B. (2023). Use of Wireless Technologies in the Automation of Technological Processes. *International Journal on Orange Technologies*, 5(4), 7-16. Retrieved from <https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJOT/article/view/4256>
4. Yo'ldoshova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi. (2023). AUTOMATION OF WORK WITH E-MAIL AND ROBOTICS SYSTEM CONTROL SYSTEM. *INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 3(3), 394–404. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7776607>
5. Yo'ldoshova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi. (2023). MANAGEMENT OF THE SYSTEM SCHEME OF AUTOMATION OF ROBOTIZATION PROCESSES. *INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY*, 3(3), 183–193. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7776593>
6. qizi, Y. H. B. . (2023). Stages of Modern Technological Development of Automation of Robotization Processes. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 33, 284–293. Retrieved from <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1233>
7. Yeshmuratova A. MINE BLASTING PROCESSES OPTIMIZATION STAGES OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY OF DETONATORS //Scienceweb academic papers collection. – 2023.
8. Eshmuratova A. A. MATCAD DASTURIDAN FOYDALANIB IKKI VA UCH OLCHOVLI GRAFIKLARNI QURISH //Journal of Integrated Education and Research. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 5. – С. 534-539.
9. Yeshmuratova A. et al. ENSURING COMPUTER DATA AND MANAGEMENT SYSTEM SECURITY //International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology. – 2023. – T. 3. – №. 4. – С. 282-287.
10. Yeshmuratova A. TECHNOLOGICAL METHODS OF ENSURING INFORMATION SECURITY IN TECHNICAL SYSTEMS //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 188-192.
11. Утемисов А. О., Юлдашова Х. Б. К. СИСТЕМЫ АВТОМАТИЧЕСКОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ //Universum: технические науки. – 2022. – №. 5-2 (98). – С. 45-47.
12. Kaipbergenov A. T., Utemisov A. O., Yuldashova H. B. K. STEADY OF AUTOMATIC CONTROL SISTEMS //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 918-921.
13. Kaipbergenov, A., & Jumamuratov, R. (2019). The methodology of teaching chemistry

based on the use of computer programs.

14. Bekturganova, Z., & Jumamuratov, R. (2017). МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНОЙ РАБОТЕ УЧАЩИХСЯ НА УРОКЕ ХИМИИ.
15. Aynazarova S. KIMYONI O'QITISH VOSITALARI TIZIMI VA UNING DIDAKTIK IMKONIYATLARINI O'RGANISH //Scienceweb academic papers collection. – 2021.
16. Саидова Л. Ш. и др. АНАЛИЗ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ ПО ПОДЪЕМУ ГОРНОЙ МАССЫ ИЗ ГЛУБОКИХ КАРЬЕРОВ И ВЫБОР ГОРНОТРАНСПОРТНОГО ОБОРУДОВАНИЯ ДЛЯ ОТКРЫТЫХ ГОРНЫХ РАБОТ //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 811-816.
17. Xolmatov O. M. et al. MURUNTAU KONI OLTINLI RUDALARINI UYUMDA TANLAB ERITISH USULIDA O'ZLASHTIRISHNING GEOTEKNOLOGIK SHAROITLARINI O'RGANISH //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 790-797.
18. Saparov A. B. et al. Analysis Of the Effect of The Physical Properties of Liquids on External Forces (Factors) //Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2022. – Т. 5. – С. 111-114.
19. Jumabayeva G., Allanazarov B., Joldasbayeva A. STAGES OF OPEN PIT MINING. MINING METHODS AND THEIR PROCESSES //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. A1. – С. 236-240.
20. Allanazarov B. GEODETIC DIMENSIONING STUDIES AND POINT-DIMENSION LOCATION COORDINATE SCHEME CREATION PROCESSES //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 4 Part 2. – С. 21-25.
21. Djaksimuratov K. et al. Comprehensive monitoring of surface deformation in underground mining, prevention of mining damage //Modern technologies and their role in mining. – 2021.
22. Djaksimuratov K. et al. FACTORS INFLUENCING THE CONDITIONS OF OPEN PIT MINING //ORE MASS AND DEFORMATION, PROCESSES THAT LEAD TO IMBALANCE DURING EXCAVATION. – 2021.
23. O'telbayev A. STRENGTH PROPERTIES OF ROCKS AND FACTORS INFLUENCING THEM AND THE PROCESS OF CHANGING THE PROPERTIES OF ROCKS.«BEST INNOVATOR IN SCIENCE-2022» Organized by Innovative Academy. – 2022.
24. Ravshanov Z. et al. EVALUATION OF THE STRENGTH OF ROCKS IN OPEN MINING PROCESSES IN MINING ENTERPRISES //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. A4. – С. 96-100.
25. Ravshanov Z. et al. METHODS OF DETERMINING THE SAFETY AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF DUST AND EXPLOSION PROCESSES IN MINING ENTERPRISES //International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 4. – С. 415-423.
26. Mustapaevich D. K. Ravshanov Zavqiddin Yahyo o'g'li, Ergasheva Zulxumor Abdaaliyevna, O'razmatov Jonibek Ikromboy o'g'li, & O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li.(2022). Underground mine mining systems and technological parameters of mine development //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN. – С. 2277-3630.
27. Arzuev, H., Najmova, N., Sharipova, A., Seytnazarova, O., & Abdikamalova, A. (2023). INVESTIGATION OF THE ADSORPTION ACTIVITY OF A MICROSPHERE -

WASTE FROM A THERMAL POWER PLANT.

28. Najimova N., Utepbaeva G., Urazbayeva A. WATER ELECTROLYSIS STUDIES AND CHEMICAL TECHNOLOGICAL DESCRIPTION //International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 4. – С. 509-513.
29. Najimova N. GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT CHEMICAL PROCESSES AND REACTORS //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 3 Part 3. – С. 28-37.
30. Bazarbaevna N. N. GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT CHEMICAL PROCESSES AND REACTORS. EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH, 3 (3), 28–37. – 2023.
31. Paxratdinov , A. D., & Abdiramanova , Z. U. (2023). ELEKTR ENERGIYA SAPASIN ELEKTR ENERGIYA ISIRAPINA TÁSIRIN ÚYRENIW HÁM HАRАKTERISTIKАLAW. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(1 SPECIAL), 233–236. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/1793>
32. Хайитов О. Ғ. и др. ЧУҚУР КАРЬЕРЛАРДА КОН ЖИНСЛАРИНИ АВТОМОБИЛ ТРАНСПОРТИДА ТАШИШ ИШЛАРИНИ ҲИСОБЛАШ //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 798-803.
33. Yo'ldoshova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi. (2023). Use of energy-saving operational technological systems in automation processes. The Peerian Journal, 16, 60–70. Retrieved from <https://www.peerianjournal.com/index.php/tpj/article/view/515>

Challenges in Teaching English as a Second Language to Adults, Multilingual Settings and Teaching Methods

Azimova Mahfuza Abdusamatovna

Tashkent University of Applied Sciences Teacher of Department of Foreign Languages and Literature

Abstract: In this article contains comments on the methodology of teaching English for older people.

Kalit so'zlar: General English, education system, teaching, TESL, culture, strategical, pedagogical technology.

Do you struggle with vocabulary words that have multiple meanings? Have you ever come across a word that you know (as you thought) but is used in a totally strange way? English vocabulary is especially difficult because many words have different meanings and can be confused. After all, it is not easy to remember different definitions for each word. Take the word date for example. The word can refer to a specific day of the month, a time when two people spend romantically with each other, the only way to correctly determine which value is being used is to look at the context. This means that it is necessary to use the surrounding words and sentences to understand which definition of an obscure word is appropriate here.

Even if you don't know the meaning of a difficult word, contextual clues will help you understand it! Can you identify the meaning of the word date in the following sentences? When is the first day of school again? Do you want to go on a date with me? In the first sentence, someone asks when day school starts. This is not a romantic meeting between the two. The first definition fits here.

The second sentence is trickier, but you can understand that someone is asking for a specific, single day. You are asked to spend time with them. The second definition fits here. Another trick is to pay attention to the part of speech (ie noun, adjective, etc.). Usually, different definitions of the same word refer to different parts of speech, so it is very easy to distinguish between them.

Let's get to the point. It means: To refer to a place, direction, person or thing (verb). The sharp end of an object (noun) Look at the part of speech to find which definition best fits the sentences below. Can you show me the way out? I can't find it. He tapped me with the tip of his pencil.

In the first sentence, the word period is used as a verb, so it can be concluded that the first definition applies to it. In the second sentence, the period is a noun and the second definition is used. If you're looking for more tips on learning polysemantic words in English, this video has more examples and more explanations!

Students admitted to SEEU are of various nationalities. The Language Center operating within this university offers English courses to all students of the general SEEU faculties, from general English skills to academic and ESP. Having this mix of teachers and students, teaching and learning English in this environment is challenging for both parties. The most difficult issue in teaching a foreign language (in our case English) is the question of whether

teachers should use the first language of the student or not. This article focuses on the question of whether or not L1 is used in ELF teaching in SEEU, Language Center English classes. If yes, to what extent and in what circumstances is it used? This article explores and develops the methodological strategies that English language teachers use to meet and support students who are raised and educated in multilingual settings. The data collected for this article were analyzed using quantitative and qualitative methods. In conclusion, the results emerging from this study show that the proportionate and careful use of L1 in English classes does not seem to affect students' exposure to the target language.

Macedonia is a very small, but multicultural, multi-ethnic and multilingual country. While in primary and secondary school students are placed in classes based on their nationality, at the university level they are grouped together. This diversity in classrooms, especially in foreign language teaching, sometimes creates many complications in the use of L1. Poudel, P.P. (2010: 121) define multilingualism as "the condition in which more than two languages are used for similar purposes in the same setting". The challenge of teaching in such diverse settings arises from the fact that a teacher has to manage a classroom full of students from different linguistic, cultural and religious backgrounds. Using L1 learners in such a setting can actually waste time that is meant for teaching and learning. However, another concern arises if the teacher does not speak all of the students' languages in the classroom. On the other hand, if L1 is used, teachers should provide equal opportunities to all students so as not to discriminate against any of them.

English teaching methodology, because the builders of the Tower of Babel spoke different languages, the society needed translators. Translators were appreciated everywhere. Until recently, a foreign language was more of a hobby than a harsh reality. Knowing a foreign language means being an esthete, belonging to a certain circle, or (the most harmless option) - being called an eccentric. But times are changing.

Any house you know starts with an architectural plan. Now we are more and more afraid of the huge fortress called "Foreign language", on top of which the flag (mostly British) flies proudly. And in this case, knowledge of modern teaching methods serves as a necessary plan. Recently, when the educational technology market is filled with suggestions for different methods of learning English, the question "What method do you use to teach?" is becoming more and more relevant, which indicates that the culture of consuming intellectual products has increased. A confused applicant, student or businessman (and a student at that) is increasingly stuck in front of the language shelves with linguistic literature and media or pondering a long list of advertisements. One of the selection criteria is the price, but the main one is ... "English in two weeks", "Communicative methods of teaching English", "English with English in Moscow", "Effective express method", "English under the level of consciousness" finally. So much is new and unknown! And it raises doubts about the results. Can you trust modern technology? Or well-established, like "Bonk", "Eckersley" or "Headway", which is gradually moving into the category of stylistic classics. Prioritize brands"?

Indeed, at the end of the 20th century. A "revolution" has occurred in the methodology of teaching English in Russia. Previously, all priorities were given to grammar, mechanical acquisition of almost verbatim words, reading and literary translation. These are the principles of the "old school", which (to give it its due) still paid off, but at what cost? Language acquisition was done through long-term work. The tasks were very monotonous: reading the text, translating, memorizing new words, repeating and practicing the text. Sometimes, for the necessary change of activity - essay or dictation, and the rest are phonetic exercises. When reading and working on "topics" was given priority, only one function of the language - the information function - was realized. It is not surprising that only a few people know the language well: only very purposeful and hardworking people can master it at a high

level. But in terms of grammar they could easily compete with Cambridge graduates! True, they received good compensation for their work: the profession of a foreign language teacher or translator was considered very prestigious in our country.

Progress and fundamental changes in language learning methods are undoubtedly associated with innovations in the field of individual and group psychology. Now there are significant changes in people's minds and the development of new thinking: the need for self-awareness and self-awareness, announced by A. Maslow, appears. In learning foreign languages, the psychological factor is rising to a leading position. The authenticity of communication, proportional demands and claims, mutual benefit, respect for the freedom of other people - this is a set of unwritten rules for establishing constructive relationships in the "teacher-student" system.

The fifth, but in no case, the most important element of this system is not selected. This comes from the student taking the course that best suits his needs. In the classroom, the student is no longer limited in the choice of speech tools and specific speech behavior. The teacher is not limited in the choice: teaching methods and techniques - from games and training parts to simultaneous translation; in organizing lessons; in our selection of textbooks and study guides - from many local publications to products from Oxford, Cambridge, London, New York and Sydney. Now the teacher can select, create, combine, change.

The basic technique is really the oldest and most traditional style. It was in this way that the students of the lyceum learned Latin and Greek, and French was acquired naturally, by the strict suggestions of the governors and communication with Amman and the pope. The classical method, like no other, corresponds to the definition of the "plan to capture the castle": phonetic ciphers, visual representations of syntactic constructions, forced vocabulary ... The student clearly understands: Sir Calme, Monsieur Gallantry or Herr Sanity, he: a) is ready to spend 2-3 years; b) be patient (learning starts from the beginning); c) I remember how topics, adverbs can be expressed by local, "great and mighty" words and what they are related to - syntax.

Fundamental methodology is strongly believed in language universities. The translator is never sure that he knows a foreign language; he perfectly understands the unpredictability of emerging speech situations. Studying according to the classical method, students not only work with different lexical layers, but also learn to look at the world through the eyes of a "native speaker" - a native speaker.

Perhaps the most famous representative of the classical method of teaching a foreign language is N.A. Bonk. His English textbooks, written in collaboration with other authors, have long become classics of the genre and have withstood the competition in recent years. The classical technique is otherwise called fundamental: no one promises that it will be easy, that you do not need to study at home, and the experience of the teacher will save you from mistakes in pronunciation and grammar. But the prize develops the metaphor of the castle, the subjunctive mood, or the case of a real native who knows how not to get lost in the labyrinth of the past. And after that. The basic methodology is your favorite question "why?" He assumes that. You are ready to enter the interesting, complex and very logical world, whose name is the language system, not content with explanations that "should be like this".

Classical approach to learning a foreign language In this regard, the classical approach to learning a foreign language has also changed somewhat, but the incomparable principles of the "classics" of Russian language methods have been preserved. Sometimes they are actively used in schools of other methodological directions. The classical course is designed for students of different ages and often involves learning the language "from scratch". The teacher's tasks include the traditional but important aspects of forming the grammatical base of pronunciation, eliminating psychological and linguistic barriers that interfere with

communication. "Classic" has not changed its goals, but the methods are already different due to the new approach.

REFERENCES:

1. Aitchison, J. (1972) *General Linguistics*, English Universities Press.
2. Aitchison, J. (1978) *Linguistics*, Hodder & Stoughton, 2nd edn.
3. Alexander, L.G. (1971) *Guided Composition in English Teaching*, Longman.
4. Allen, J.P.B. and Corder, S.Pit (eds) (1974) *The Edinburgh Course in Applied Linguistics, Vol. 3, Techniques in Applied Linguistics*, Oxford University Press.
5. Allen, J.P.B. and Corder, S.Pit (1977) *The Edinburgh Course in Applied Linguistics, Vol. 4, Testing and Experimental Methods*, Oxford University Press.
6. Anderson, W.L. and Stageberg, N.C. (1966) *Introductory Readings on Language*, New York: Holt, Rinehart & Winston.

Content, Form and Means of Formation of Basic Competences in Primary School Students

Ortiqova Ziyodaxon Otajon

Primary teacher of the 29th secondary school of Fergana city

Isomiddinova Sayyoraxon Nematovna

Primary teacher of the 29th secondary school of Fergana city

Annotation: In selecting learning technologies for the formation of core competencies in students, the science teacher identifies the core competencies identified for that class in the calendar theme plan. After that, the method of teaching is chosen, taking into account the topic to be studied and the competencies to be formed. This article discusses the content, form, and means of developing core competencies in primary school students.

Keywords: primary school students, basic competencies, development, content, form, means, higher education, pedagogical principles, interactive methods, interactive lessons.

The study of pedagogy today and the relationship of time to it is becoming a separate scientific problem. A person, as an independent creative activity and a skilled expert in his field, must be able to influence the development of the nation's social thinking. Independent creative activity, creativity serves as a criterion for ensuring the level of preparation of students for social life on the basis of social knowledge and consciousness. The system of higher pedagogical education is an important step in this direction, especially in pedagogical faculties, where the formation and development of professional skills, ethics, etiquette and necessary qualities of future primary school teachers is a priority.

Interactive approach. Teachers create a comfortable environment for better organization of the teaching process. Students are given the opportunity to exchange ideas. They discuss and resolve the issues that need to be resolved together. They find a solution together to get out of the situation. They demonstrate their knowledge to each other based on the information they receive.

Design method. The design method is a system of teaching in which students acquire knowledge, skills, and competencies in the planning, construction, and execution of a practical task that is constantly becoming more complex. Students carry out a wide range of problem-solving (creative, information, communication and problem-related) projects. For this method to be highly effective, it is necessary to have a high level of motivation in the project. Personal competencies are formed:

- Teamwork;
- Feelings of responsibility;
- Self-confidence;
- Fast thinking;
- Be able to see the progress of the process;

- Ability to observe;
- Motivation.

The problem-based modular teaching method involves the practical application of theoretical knowledge. This method forms the didactic basis of various models of teaching and differs in the use of teaching aids and pedagogical techniques. It refers to the division of the subject into relatively small parts - modules. The main purpose of education aimed at the development of the student's personality is in fact the development of additional competencies such as thinking, mastering, writing and arithmetic of children from the primary school. A person who enters into social relations and actively participates in social development is called a person. A person who is born as an individual then becomes a person. In the notion of the individual, a person's lineage is embodied.

The design method is a system of teaching in which students acquire knowledge, skills, and competencies in the planning, construction, and execution of a practical task that is constantly becoming more complex. Students carry out a wide range of problem-solving (creative, informational, communication and problem-related) projects. For this method to be highly effective, students must have a high level of motivation in the project. The following personal competencies are formed: teamwork ; activity; sense of responsibility; self-confidence; teaching; quick thinking; ability to see the process; ability to observe; foresight; diagnosis; accelerates the activation of knowledge; helps to attract new and interconnected ideas freely and openly.

Communicative competence - adherence to etiquette in communication; to be able to listen to the opinion of the interlocutor, to express one's opinion; self-control adherence to the culture of communication in communication; including elements such as respect for the opinion of the interlocutor in the conversation, which is manifested through the study of the proverbs related to language. National and multicultural competence - continuous self-development of physical, spiritual, mental, intellectual and creative development, striving for perfection, independent learning throughout life, continuous improvement of cognitive skills and life experience it involves acquiring the skills to go, alternatively evaluate one's own behavior, and make independent decisions.

National and multicultural competence refers to the ability to find, sort, process, store, use, secure, and develop the capacity for media culture to obtain the necessary information from media sources.

Complete a variety of problem-solving assignments in a variety of academic disciplines, such as reporting, writing test questions, and more. Students will be able to complete a variety of challenging assignments independently in a variety of disciplines at several stages of the education system. For example, in general secondary education, time is allocated for practical training. As students participate in these hands-on activities, they will develop the basic skills to participate independently in production. In later stages of education, such as lyceums and vocational colleges, they are in a variety of internships, completing problem-solving assignments independently, compiling reports, and writing essays. In higher education, students participate in industrial, graduate and pedagogical internships. Pedagogical internships are organized for 14 weeks for final students in the fields of music, fine and applied arts, labor education, primary education and psychological education, where the field of education is the humanities.

During the internship, students organize and observe a variety of lessons and extracurricular activities, analyze, write conclusions. During the internship, they prepare for lessons independently, initially under the supervision of a teacher, and during the main period, independently develop lesson and extracurricular activities and implement them in the educational process. At the end of the internship, reports will be prepared and presentations

will be made.

And when faced with a difficult situation, they are constantly looking for solutions. Here are some suggestions on how to look or get an appointment for hair extensions. The following are the names of independent creative works that can be effectively used in the training of future primary school teachers in higher education. They can be successfully implemented taking into account different regional, regional, local characteristics.

- Production of various shapes, toys, objects from paper, cardboard, wires and fabrics, as well as various natural and artificial materials on the basis of the subject of labor education methods; - to draw and describe various processes, landscapes, objects and objects in fine and applied arts classes;
- Participate in the development of methodological developments in the education system, the educational process and the organization of educational work (during the internship);
- Development and implementation of electronic trainings;
- Presentation of articles, lectures, theses in scientific, practical, methodological, pedagogical and psychological content in thematic conferences and conferences in magazines, newspapers, collections;
- Participate in the preparation of scientific reports (for research on the basis of economic contracts);
- Participate in the development of methodological recommendations, developments for the improvement of individual parts of the curriculum and program of the educational institution (preschool, general secondary, secondary special, vocational education);
- Design, development, construction of didactic tools of education. Preparation of technological and perforation maps, creation of slides;
- In the development and implementation of guidelines for improving the organization of various activities of students (games, games, labor, sports, health, creativity, production, community, etc.) to participate; - Participation in various pedagogical, psychological, didactic, methodological and scientific research and observation, experimental work;
- Participate in tests, questionnaires, interview questionnaires, observation cards, interviews, discussion and editing;
- Participation in science olympiads, competitions, various contests, scientific-methodical conferences and seminars.

Active participation of the educational institution in various cultural, spiritual and educational events, hashars, etc. with representatives of public organizations, mahallas, authorities. In general, the following suggestions and recommendations can be made for the successful organization of independent creative work of future primary school teachers at the level of modern requirements. The diversity of independent creative work plays an important role in preparing future primary school teachers for professional pedagogical activities, as the more creative tasks students complete during their studies, the more diverse aspects of independent pedagogical activity become. Particular attention should be paid to the continuity, continuity and continuity of the organization of independent creative activity of students. Because in such cases, it is advisable to follow the principles of "simple to complex" and "easy to difficult" in the performance of problematic tasks. Students are encouraged to keep copies of independent creative work done during extracurricular and classroom activities, spiritual and educational activities, and internships, as they can also be used as direct examples in independent pedagogical activities.

In conclusion, in order to effectively address the issue of ensuring the acquisition of

professional skills and abilities of students, special attention should be paid to the forms of organization of independent practical creative activity. This will help alleviate the problem of training an aspiring creative elementary school teacher. In general, primary school students need to use interactive methods with the content, form, and means of developing core competencies.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. Jurayev Z. H, Tolipov O., Sharipov Sh .. Scientific and pedagogical bases of vocational guidance of students in the system of continuing education. - T.: Fan, 2004, 120-p.
2. Haydarov IA The purpose, tasks, methods and means of continuous professional orientation. // "School and Life" magazine, 2012, № pages 7-8, 5-6.
3. Pronina E. N., Lukashevich.V. V. Psychology and pedagogy. Textbook for university students. - M.: Elit, 2004.
4. Full article: Global teaching competencies in primary education. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/03057925.2020.1869520>
5. Speech Competence of Primary School Students: Cognitive Approach. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342823728_Speech_Competence_of_Primary_School_Students_Cognitive_Approach

Didactic Possibilities of the Formation of Competencies in Students

Davletov Erkaboy Yusubovich

Urganch State Pedagogical Institute Acting associate professor of the "Pedagogy, primary and preschool education methodology" department

Abstract: This article reflects on the development of cognitive, social and sexual competencies of students in order to form new knowledge, skills and competencies in the formation of general learning actions in students, serves as a programmatic for pedagogical scientists, teachers, authors of programs and textbooks, researchers.

Keywords: cognitive competencies, heuristic, life competencies, base competencies, communicative, information, Social, national and universal, personal self-development, stichian, tolerance.

In order to work with communicative, information in primary students, self-development as a person, the formation of socio-emotional and civil competencies, it is initially necessary to develop cognitive competencies in them. Today, the state and society have a strong need for young people who are enterprising, responsible, competent, communicative, able to establish interpersonal relationships. To do this, the requirements for the competency of students embody not only a high level of fundamental knowledge, but also knowledge at the level of functional literacy. Within the requirements of state educational standards based on a competency approach, the development of the universal, personal and cognitive spheres of primary students is envisaged. As a result of the development of these areas, the basic skills of Primary School students such as learning, mastering knowledge are developed.

E.A.Romanova noted that in state educational standards of primary education there are certain types of competencies that need to be formulated in students. They are:

- *cognitive competencies;*
- *social competencies;*
- *personal competencies [1].*

To generate these competencies, it is important to develop the cognitive activity of students. The importance of initially developing their cognitive activity in order to form competence in primary school students is explained by a number of factors. They are:

- the imbalance between the level of knowledge of Primary School students and the ability to apply them in practice;
- insufficient opportunities to eliminate conflicts in the educational system with the social order of the state;
- limited opportunities for students to accelerate the development of the universal, social, cognitive spheres with the need to improve the educational process, as well as insufficient conditions for all students to achieve such success;

- the need to ensure inter-phase continuity in a single educational space;
- non-predictability of student development levels and stichial selection of educational content without taking into account pedagogical-psychological foundations; including insufficient attention to students' adaptation to school life; low level of preparation of children for school learning; insufficient orientation towards the goal of general educational efforts; incomplete realization of opportunities for innovation management of the educational process; insufficient application by the teacher of;
- to form communicative competencies in primary school students, they are initially provided with basic knowledge; for example, a teacher can act cooperatively in students, work as a group, tolerance for various thoughts, be able to listen to his interlocutor and behave freely in the dialogue process, be able to clearly state his point of view in relation to the problem, analyze the point of view of.

The intellectual development of Primary School students has been slow to take place, as shown in research done in recent years. This is causing a decline in creative power among elementary school students.

To improve the educational process, first of all, attention should be paid to the development of the universal, social and cognitive spheres of students. This primarily requires the improvement of educational tools, ways, methods and techniques.

The challenges faced by education and the introduction of state educational standards and national programs based on a competency approach made it necessary to improve the educational process on the basis of an innovative approach.

In order to effectively solve the problem of the formation of competency in elementary students, it is required to improve the process of primary education on the basis of new educational blocks. In the later stages of education, in order for students to effectively master knowledge, skills and qualifications, it is required to form competencies related to basic life and science as early as the primary classes.

Realizing the intellectual capacities of Primary School students, their comprehensive development is extremely necessary to expand the possibilities of cognition.

Distinguished specialist V.D.Shadrikov had uncovered a systematic interpretation of competency in full form. In order for students to form competencies related to the base and science, it is required, first of all, to work with them on the basis of an active approach [2].

In the Encyclopedia of pedagogy, "an active approach is a form of an active attitude of people to the outside world, a way of transforming a person's self in a purposeful way, one of the important features of the human being. On the basis of activity, the essence of man is manifested, representing the personification of knowledge, skills and competencies by approaching the student from this point of view" [3; p.264].

Teaching an elementary student based on a competency approach is a new form of approach to the learning process. As a result of this approach, the possibility of the formation of knowledge, skills, qualifications, competencies and personal qualities in a systematic way in primary school students expands. As a result, students acquire the skills to successfully solve assignments and apply their knowledge to their practical activities. It can be seen that competency is not an indicator that contradicts the knowledge, skills, qualifications and personal qualities of students, but that all this constitutes a single student system.

G.A.Suckerman argues that the concept of competency is complemented by the concept of acting in ambiguous situations. Competency is such a quality of knowledge, skills and qualifications of students of graduating classes that it ensures, first of all, tolerance to flexibility, conflicts and uncertainties. Competency of the student can manifest itself as a

form of application of knowledge, skills and qualifications in practice in the process of solving assignments. It differs in the fact that knowledge is mastered by tests. Tests that determine the competency of the student do not serve to assess the size of knowledge, skills, qualifications, but serve as an instrument that ensures the manifestation of this knowledge, skills, qualifications through thought and Action [4].

The composition of educational competency of Primary School students consists in the readiness to independently solve tasks using methods of mastering them according to the development of basic cognitive processes in connection with the assimilation of the content of Education. They include: perception of educational materials, concentration of attention on one point, storage of basic concepts in memory, reflection on realities, phenomena, formation of an idea about them. In its composition, competencies mainly related to the base and educational science are embodied.

While base competency means competencies are expressed in Block view when solving assignments, competency in the subject of study is manifested in the independent movement of students in reading as well as in development. For initial base competency, multi-functionality is inherent, and the acquisition of these competencies provides an opportunity for students to solve various problems and tasks in everyday life situations. Base competencies are considered universal and convenient for use in various situations.

Initial base competencies are multifaceted, in which the results of the student's personal experience are expressed. These are reflected in interpersonal relationships, interaction, knowledge, skills, creativity.

In primary school students, the base life competency is formed in stages. There are opportunities for their formation at all stages of school education, which are expressed in educational results, quality indicators. These indicators are stated in a certain consistency in state educational standards, where the indicators are based on a competency approach.

In the formation of cognitive competencies in elementary students, we relied on the following theoretical concepts. They are: the concept of developmental education, the concept of immediacy as a component of a systematic-functional approach, the concept of a psychodidactic approach.

Approaches based on the formation of cognitive competencies in primary school students

During our research, we also tried to determine which pedagogical approaches, methods and methods are effective in the formation of competencies. It is known that G. A. Zukerman compared three pedagogical systems in his research. They are:

1. *Modernized system of traditional education.*
2. *Pedagogical system proposed by D.B.Elkonin and V.V.Davydov.*
3. *Waldorf pedagogy [4].*

Based on this approach, we have selected a number of tasks to conduct a small analysis. It is characteristic that these assignments are typical of the traditional pedagogical system. A lot of space has been allocated to assignments that serve to transfer ready-made knowledge. In this process, highly complex didactic units are taught to students using traditional reproductive methods. When choosing tasks, attention is paid to their level of social significance. From the point of view of the competence approach, solving these tasks created a number of difficulties for the students.

We sought an answer to the question of which teaching system is effective in the formation of competencies. For this purpose, two tasks were selected. Based on these tasks, it was intended to determine the level of mathematical literacy of students. When we gradually increased such tasks, we witnessed the rapid development of economic, mathematical knowledge and calculation skills of elementary school students. Because these assignments were formed based on the principles of person-oriented and developmental education. It can be seen that students' ability to apply and test their acquired knowledge in practice is not sufficiently developed in the traditional education process.

Tasks of a developmental and heuristic character ensure that students rapidly acquire basic life and science-related competencies. Our research shows that in order to successfully form cognitive competencies in elementary school students, it is necessary to systematically use developmental and heuristic exercises and problems..

REFERENCES:

1. Романова Е.А. Формирование социальных и личностных компетенций у современных дошкольников и младших школьников. // Журнал научно-педагогической информации. 2010. - №2. [Электронный ресурс] / <http://www.paedagogia.ru/2010/40-02/120-romanova>
2. Шадриков В.Д. Новая модель специалиста: инновационная подготовка и компетентностный подход // Высшее образование сегодня. - 2004. № 8.- с. 182-188.
3. Педагогика: энциклопедия. II-III жилд // тузувчилар: жамоа. – Тошкент: “Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси” Давлат илмий нашриёти, 2015. –376 б.
4. Цукерман Г.А. Пизанская башня отечественного образования. // Школ. психолог: прил. к газ. "Первое сент". 2008.1-15 февр. (3).

Working With Various Methods and Approaches

Dusbayeva Nazira Narimanovna

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute Senior teacher of the "Foreign Languages" department

Annotation: This article examines the diversity found in language teaching today, looking at traditional approaches to language teaching, communicative approaches, and innovative approaches.

Keywords: method, approach, chunks, communicative approaches, traditional approaches, innovative approaches.

Introduction.

"There is no single acceptable way to go about teaching language today." This quote from Diane Larsen-Freeman's writings on language teaching methodology sums up a major trend away from unity to diversity. There has been a growing realization that people learn in different ways, and that approaches which suit one person may not suit another. For example, some outgoing personalities love to experiment and can hardly wait for the chance to try speaking the new language. Others, more reserved, prefer to listen and understand before speaking. Some people find that studying the grammar is an important step for them in establishing a framework for their language learning¹. Others never study the rules, but find that putting themselves in situations where they have to communicate is enough to trigger their learning.

Against this backdrop, teachers of English have concluded that no single approach or method is appropriate for all learning styles. A good lesson will therefore be one in which you use a smorgasbord of activities taken from a variety of sources. By varying your technique, you will give students of all styles the chance to shine some of the time. With this thought in mind, you can begin to appraise the language learning approaches used in the country in which you serve. Each approach has something to offer. Your task is to identify and exploit those elements.

As you become more familiar with your job you will find that you learn to trust your instincts and your ability to judge when to switch techniques. At first you may need to read about methods and approaches, and you should look for opportunities to talk to experienced teachers about what they think of different methods². Then, gradually as you get to know your students, you will find that you can sense when a class is tired, or confused, or in need of quiet time, or particularly interested. And you will find that you know when to dip into your repertoire of approaches, games and exercises to find the appropriate activity which suits the mood of your students and which ensures they get the best out of every lesson.

The terms "method" and "approach" will be used interchangeably in this chapter. For example, the chapter refers to the Audiolingual Method and the Communicative Approach. A number of different ways of distinguishing between methods and approaches have been proposed by experts in the field but the distinctions usually blur. Both deal with theory of the nature of language and language learning; with syllabus, learning and teaching activities,

¹ Tomas Kraal. "The foreign language teaching methodology" Oxford University press. 1995.

² Kenneth A.Brufee, "Collaborative learning, some practical models" Oxford University press. 1999.

learner and teacher roles, and instructional materials; and with classroom techniques, practices, and behaviors.

APPROACH VERSUS METHOD	
Approach is the way in which something is approached	Method is the way I which something is done
Refers to the direction or angle	Refers to a process
Refers to the theoretical framework in general	Refers to step guidelines
Approach has to be decided before selecting the method	Method can be selected after deciding the approach

The approaches or methods are divided into:

- Traditional language teaching
- Grammar Translation Method
- Direct Method
- Audiolingual Method
- Communicative language teaching
- Communicative Approach
- Total Physical Response
- Natural Approach
- Competency-Based Approach
- Innovative language teaching
- Silent Way
- Community Language Learning
- Suggestopedia

Grammar- Translation and Audio- lingual Method. If students feel that they must know the rule for a certain features of grammar the teacher should try this adaptation of the Grammar Translation and Audio Lingual Method. They work through a set of audio lingual pattern drills which illustrate the feature³.

Direct and Audio Lingual Method. Conversation, dialogues or short narratives can be used to exercise the students' ability to guess meaning from context. They may be asked to listen to a tape recorder of a short passage and ask for guesses about the meaning of the words. Conversations and dialogues are also an excellent way to practice conversational formulas such as invitations, simple requests, compliments and others.

Communicative Approaches. One of the distinguishing features of communicative language teaching that is used in realistic ways. It means the students/ pupils use their English in real life tasks, for example taking a phone message from a friend or interpreting some news.

Total Physical Response. Meaning in the target language can often be conveyed through actions. Students can initially learn one part of the language rapidly by moving their bodies.

³ E.S. Polat, "New pedagogical and information technologies in the education system". Moscow, pp. 35-49, 2001.

The aim of the natural approach is to develop communicative skills, and it is primarily intended to be used with beginning learners. It is presented as a set of principles that can apply to a wide range of learners and teaching situations, and concrete objectives depend on the specific context in which it is used.

The Silent Way is an approach to teaching languages that is based on explicit ideas about how people learn, about the nature of language and about how foreign languages are best taught.

Suggestopedia. The originator of the Method is George Lozanov. He asserts that we set up psychological barriers to learning and we will be limited in our ability to learn we don't use the full mental powers that we have. According to Lozanov and others, we may be using only five to ten percent of our mental capacity. In order to make better use of our mental reserves, the limitations we think we have need to be "de suggested", Suggestopedia, the application of the study the suggestion to pedagogy, has been developed to help students of learners eliminate the feeling that they cannot be successful and, thus to help them overcome the barriers to learning.⁴

Task-based Teaching (TBT) [and Task-based Learning (TBL)] is the approach that TESOL Advantage advocates as best practice when it comes to English language teaching.

While TBT's basic principles are derived from CLT, there are some important differences. Critics of CLT have raised the following concerns:

1. Teachers can struggle with the non-specific requirements of CLT.
2. Teachers are often worried about giving up too much control during a CLT exercise.
3. Many learners have low intrinsic motivation to communicate in a foreign language and so struggle with CLT student-centric exercises.
4. Because CLT is a meaning-focused approach, learners may struggle with grammar issues.

REFERENCES:

1. Tomas Kraal. "The foreign language teaching methodology" Oxford University press. 1995.
2. Kenneth A. Brufee, "Collaborative learning, some practical models" Oxford University press. 1999.
3. E.S. Polat, "New pedagogical and information technologies in the education system". Moscow, pp. 35-49, 2001.
4. G. A. Berulava, M.N. Berulava, "Methodological basis for the development of higher education in the information society and the individual in the information educational space". // Pedagogy, № 4, pp. 11–18, 2010.
5. <https://tesoladvantage.com/methods-and-approaches-of-english-language-teaching/>

⁴ G.A. Berulava, M.N. Berulava, "Methodological basis for the development of higher education in the information society and the individual in the information educational space". // Pedagogy, № 4, pp. 11–18, 2010.

Gender Policy in Practice

Marjona Tinicheva Gulomjon qizi

Karshi Institute of Engineering and Economics, "Economics" faculty, "Logistics" department, 2nd year student

Annotation: The necessity and importance of women's education. The article also comments on the role of educated girls in life and their incomparable contribution to building the future.

Key words and phrases: women's education, gender politics, science, thinking, women entrepreneurs, opportunities for women's education.

We say that our girls don't know, they don't read, they don't understand because we don't teach them ourselves

Sh. M. Mirziyoyev

In our country, special attention is paid to ensuring the rights and interests of women, including creating conditions for their education. In particular, according to the relevant decree of the President, 4 percent state grant was allocated for women and girls to enter higher education institutions in our country in the 2020- 2021-academic year.

At the moment, 940 women in our republic were lucky enough to use this quota and become students. Great scientists in the history of our nation, among our great grandfathers, such there were also many virtuous women who brought people into the world, brought them up, and inspired them to great deeds. Even today, our women are selfless in raising children, in various fields, in their neighborhoods.

A number of laws, decrees and decisions have been adopted in recent years in order to ease their burden and ensure their rights and interests. In 2021, 2 trillion soums of loans and subsidies were allocated to more than 200,000 projects within the framework of women's entrepreneurship programs, and 320,000 women got permanent jobs. 190,000 women were trained in the profession. More than 4,000 women were allocated funds for the initial housing payment.

2 thousand girls were admitted to higher education on the basis of a separate grant. As a result, 60 percent of students who entered higher educational institutions last year were women. From the 2022-2023 academic year, all women and girls enrolled in the master's program are paid by the state. Graduate students with young children were allowed to study online. This shows how important women's education is in the politics of our country. Since 2020, the "Women's Registry" has been formed, and socio-economic, medical, legal and psychological support has been provided to about 900 thousand women included in it. Currently, more than 630,000 women are listed in the "Women's Registry", 200 000 of them are unemployed. Cases of crime, domestic violence and harassment among women, unfortunately, still exist. The head of our state said that the role and influence of neighborhood activists, public and intellectuals in solving these problems is not felt. - Both our prosperous life today and our bright future depend on women. If we want our people to

be satisfied with us, we must first of all create decent living conditions for our respectable mothers and sisters. If the mother agrees, the family agrees, if the family agrees, the society agrees, - said Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

This can be seen in the Holy Qur'an's chapter "Nisa" (that is, "Women"). In this Surah, Allah calls men to treat women fairly. In the holy hadith, women are also commanded to always do good. Imam Bukhari, Imam Moturidi, Beruni, Ibn Sina, Amir Timur, Alisher Navoi, Babur Mirza, our great ancestors and our enlightened ancestors also emphasized the role and importance of women in the peaceful, strong and prosperous family and the education of children. Who emphasized that the secret is incomparable? Unprecedented attention is being paid to the fundamental reform of the national education system based on the idea that "New Uzbekistan starts from the school threshold". A lot of work is being done to develop the fields of science, culture and art, literature, and sports, to increase the efficiency of spiritual and educational work, and to realize the talents and abilities of young people, especially our girls. Today, we all know and highly appreciate how selflessly our respected sisters are working in the process of change and renewal in our society, in the management system, in the fields of entrepreneurship, science, health care, culture and art, and in the neighborhoods. – says our President. I know many girls of my age and admire them. The policy of our country has created conditions for these girls to be an example to others. Gulrukhbonu Shokirova, Marjona Jurakulova, Rukhsora Shokirova, Mushtariy Masharipova, Kumush Fayzullayeva and others. Among my peers there are many celebrities and admirers like me. I would like to acknowledge the achievements of each of them. Gulrukhbonu Shokirova, 3rd stage student of the University of World Economy and Diplomacy - winner of the "Builder of the Future" medal.

Marjona Jurakulova Shakhrisabz pedagogy 2nd stage student of the institute “Kindness badge owner”.

Rukhsora Shokirova, 9 th grade student of school 159 - adviser to the captains of the head of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan.

Mushtariy Fayzullayeva Navoi - is studying weightlifting at the specialized Olympic reserve boarding school. Mukhlisa Amankulova - 3rd stage student of Karshi engineering-economics institute winner of the scholarship named after Islom Karimov, author of many projects and winner of competitions. Each one achieved many good results and became a place of study and the pride of his relatives, teachers and parents. The main reason is their education. Educate your daughters! They will educate the nation! I read somewhere that in Singapore, women with a diploma get a big dowry from the government when they get married, and if they have a child, they get more money than other uneducated women. So why is that? Because the great reformer Lee Kuan Yew realized that the country's success depends primarily on educated, intelligent women and mothers. History has shown that Lee Kuan Yew was one hundred percent right. A smart and knowledgeable woman evaluates the world and life with a realistic eye, more than uneducated women with a low outlook. Such women can build the future of their lives and families with modern trends and honesty. They will be able to give the right directions to their spouses and children. At least such women can pay great attention to their health and the health of their family. They are able to show their spouses bright paths to future prospects, criticize when necessary, and praise success when necessary. Knowledgeable and intelligent women are above the pain of the stomach, furniture, dishes, rags and other small things in the house. They aim very high and can make plans to take the family to great heights. Such women teach their husbands and children books and guide them to science. It is not for nothing that it is said that behind every great man is a great woman. A woman with a high intellect will definitely raise great children. Blood and body are passed from the father, mind and thinking are passed from the mother. Therefore, it is advisable to marry women who are knowledgeable and religious. Women

with sharp knowledge and intelligence can find their way in life in any situation. Because such women can find ways to protect their families economically and spiritually. Why do intellectuals choose highly talented and intelligent women for themselves, because they know that only weak people choose those who are weaker than themselves, and choose a partner who is suitable and unique for them, who is in tune with the times. Because only such strong women can inspire such strong men. What about us?

In our country, we are taught that "Women's happiness" lies in obedience, eating, sewing, and sacrificing one's life from a young age. No matter how much the trends change, no matter how much the world steps forward, our views are still in the situation of the 15th century. But the world admires not a woman's cooking skills, but her thoughtfulness and professionalism. Never be afraid to show your talent, knowledge, implements your new ideas, completely abandon old stereotypes. It is possible to learn when you want to do laundry and cooking, but it may be too late to fill the brain with knowledge, thinking and skills.

My final conclusions are that I think it is necessary to further strengthen the position of women in society. For this, it is necessary to remove obstacles to the education of women, to create conditions for them to do scientific work and become scientists, to reduce the restrictions on working in high positions, and to determine their place in the state administration. After all, as they say that a woman understands a woman's heart, women working in high positions are good at finding young talents who are being ignored and giving them support and advice to help them become useful people for the society.

The Importance of Innovative Technologies in Teaching a Foreign Language

Kho`janova Mastura Ibodullayevna

Tashkent University of Applied Sciences Faculty of Media and Communication Teacher of the "Linguistic support of intercultural communication" department

Annotation: This article covers several methods of effective teaching of English as well as several of the modern educational technologies used in language and its study.

Keywords: Language, English, independent language learning, educational technologies, project, interest, activity, interactive methods.

Introduction.

Today, the main focus is on the reader, his personality and his own inner world. Therefore, the main goal of a modern teacher is the choice of methods and forms of Organization of educational activities students, optimally corresponding to the established goal of personal development. In recent years, the issue of the use of new information technologies in schools has been increasingly raised. This is not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the educational process. The main purpose of teaching foreign languages is to form and develop the communicative culture of schoolchildren, to teach practical mastery of a foreign language.

Literature Analysis And Methods.

In the course of the study, popular methods of teaching and learning English, Internet resources were used. During the writing of the article, the principles of theoretical-deductive inference, analysis and synthesis, logic were used.

Discussion And Results.

The task of the teacher is to create conditions for practical mastery of the language for each student, to choose such teaching methods that allow each student to demonstrate their activity, creativity. The task of the teacher is to activate the student's cognitive activity in the process of teaching foreign languages. Modern pedagogical technologies, such as collaborative learning, project methodology, the use of new information technologies, Internet resources, help to implement an individual-oriented approach in the educational process, provide individualization and differentiation of teaching, taking into account the abilities of children, their level of learning. Forms of working with computer training programs in foreign language classes include: learning vocabulary; practicing pronunciation; teaching dialogical and monological speech; teaching writing; development of grammatical phenomena.

The possibilities of using Internet resources are huge. The Global Internet creates the conditions for students and teachers who are located anywhere in the world to receive any information they need: regional geographic materials, News in youth life, articles from newspapers and magazines, etc.

In the lessons, it is possible to solve a number of didactic problems with the help of the Internet in English: the formation of reading skills and qualifications using the materials of the global network; improving the writing skills of schoolchildren; replenishing the vocabulary of students; forming the motivation of students to learn English. In addition, the work aims to broaden the horizons of schoolchildren, explore the possibilities of Internet technologies to establish and support business relationships and relationships with peers in English-speaking countries. Students can participate in online tests, quizzes, contests, Olympiads, correspondence with peers in other countries, conversations, video conferences, etc. k. can participate in s.

Students can learn about the problem that is currently working on the project.

The meaningful basis of mass computerization is due to the fact that a modern computer is an effective means of optimizing mental working conditions, in general, any of its manifestations. The computer has one peculiarity; it is identified in its use as a tool for teaching others and as an assistant in the acquisition of knowledge, which is its inanimity. The machine can have "friendly" contact with the user and at some times "supports" him, but he never shows signs of anger and does not allow you to feel bored. In this sense, the use of computers is perhaps most useful in individualizing certain aspects of teaching. The main goal of learning a foreign language at school is the formation of communicative competence; all other goals (upbringing, teaching, development) are carried out in the process of implementing this main goal. The communicative approach involves teaching communication and the formation of the ability to inter-cultural interaction, which is the basis of Internet activity. Outside of communication, the Internet has no meaning - it is an international multinational, intercultural society, whose life is based on the electronic communication of millions of people around the world, talking at the same time - the largest conversation in terms of the number and volume of participants that happened. Participation in the lesson for him foreign language, we create a real communication model.

Currently, priority is given to issues of communication, interactivity, and authenticity of communication, language acquisition in a cultural context, autonomy and humanism of Education. These principles make it possible to develop intercultural competence as a component of communicative ability. The ultimate goal of teaching foreign languages is to teach a free direction in a foreign language environment and the ability to respond adequately in different situations, i.e. Comm. Today, new methods using Internet resources are opposed to teaching traditional foreign languages. To teach communication in a foreign language, you need to create real, real-life situations that stimulate the study of material and develop adequate behavior (that is, the so-called principle of communication authenticity). New technologies, in particular the Internet, are trying to correct this error. A communicative approach is a strategy that simulates communication, aimed at consciously understanding the material and creating psychological and linguistic readiness for methods of working with it, communication. It is not particularly difficult for the user to implement a communicative approach on the Internet. The communicative task must offer students to discuss a problem or question, students not only exchange information, but also evaluate them. The main criterion that allows you to distinguish this approach from other types of educational activities is that students independently choose linguistic units to form their thoughts. In a communicative approach, the use of the Internet is very well encouraged: its purpose is to interest students in learning a foreign language by collecting and expanding their knowledge and experience.

One of the main requirements for teaching foreign languages using Internet resources is the creation of interaction in the lesson, which is usually called interactivity in the methodology. Interactivity is the "integration, coordination and completion of communicative goal and resultant efforts using speech tools". By teaching a real language, the Internet helps to form speech skills and skills, and also provides sincere interest and therefore efficiency in teaching

vocabulary and grammar. Interactivity not only creates realistic situations from life, but also forces students to respond appropriately to them in a foreign language.

One of the technologies that provide student-oriented education is the project style as a way to promote creativity, cognitive activity and independence. The typology of the projects is diverse. Projects can be divided into monoproyects, collective, oral, concrete, written and Internet projects. In real practice, it is often necessary to deal with research projects, mixed projects with creative, practice-oriented and informative characters. Project work is a multifaceted approach to language acquisition, covering reading, listening, speaking, and grammar. The project method helps to develop active independent thinking of students and directs them to joint research work. In my opinion, project-based teaching can teach children to cooperate, while learning to cooperate fosters moral values such as the ability to reciprocate and empathize, shaping creativity and activating students. In general, in the process of Project training, there is an inseparability of training and upbringing.

The project method develops students' communication skills, culture of treatment, the ability to form thoughts compactly and easily, tolerates the opinion of communication partners, the ability to extract information from various sources, processes using modern computer technologies, creates a language environment that contributes to the emergence of a natural need. in a foreign language connection.

The project form of work is one of the most relevant technologies that allows students to apply the accumulated knowledge on the topic. Students expand their horizons, boundaries of knowledge of the language, accumulate experiences of its practical use, learn to listen and hear speech in a foreign language, understand each other in the defense of projects. Children work with reference books, dictionaries, a computer and thus create the possibility of direct contact with genuine language, which does not provide language learning in the classroom only with the help of a textbook.

Working on a project is a creative process. The student is looking for a solution to the problem independently or under the guidance of a teacher, for which it is required not only to know the language, but also to have a large amount of subject knowledge, to acquire creative, communicative and intellectual skills.

In the process of foreign languages, the project method can be used within the framework of application materials on almost any topic. Working on projects develops imagination, fantasy, creative thinking, independence and other personal qualities.

To modern technologies are also applicable to collaborative technology. The main idea is to create conditions for active joint activities of students in various educational conditions. Children are united into groups of 3-4 people, they are given one task, while the role of each is discussed. Each student is responsible not only for the result of his work, but also for the result of the entire group. Therefore, weak students try to figure out what they do not understand from what is not strong, and strong students strive to thoroughly understand the assignment to the weak. And the whole class will benefit from this, because the spaces are closed together.

Conclusions and Suggestions.

The introduction of information technology into training greatly diversifies the process of perception and processing of information. Thanks to the computer, the Internet and Multimedia, a unique opportunity was created for students to master a large amount of information with subsequent analysis and sorting. The motivational foundations of educational activities are also significantly expanding. In the context of using multimedia, students receive information from newspapers, TV, conduct interviews themselves and conduct teleconferences.

The main criterion for assessing the level of knowledge of a foreign language in language portfolio technology is a test. The priority of this technology is to direct the educational process from teacher to student. The reader, in turn, is consciously responsible for the results of his cognitive activity. The above technology leads to the gradual formation of students' skills to independently master information. In general, the language portfolio is multifunctional and contributes to the development of multilingualism.

REFERENCES:

1. Erden, M. and S. Altun, 2006. Learning Styles. İstanbul: Morpa Culture Publications. ISBN: 9752844863.
2. Johnson, K. E. The Sociocultural Turn and Its Challenges for Second Language Teacher Education. // TESOL Quarterly., – London. 2006.
3. Kaplan, E.J. and D.A. Kies, 1995. Teaching styles and learning styles. J. Instruct. Psychol.
4. Butler, K.A., 1988. Learning and teaching styles In theory and practice. Columbia CT: The Learner's Dimension. ISBN-10: 0945852002
5. Harmer J. The Practice of English Language Teaching. – London., 2001.

Artistic Ideological Education of Future Music Teachers through the Epic of Khorazm

Yakubov Zafarbek

Urganch State University Teacher of the Department of Music Education

Abstract: This article provides information about the theoretical features of Khorezm's epics. Also, comments were made about the possibilities of artistic and ideological education of future music teachers through the Khorezm epic.

Keywords: Khorezm epics, teacher, education, methodology, education system, pedagogy.

Uzbek epic is a very ancient and prestigious symbol of spiritual heritage. Folk creativity, art has a special place in the spiritual development of a person. The development of all arts is based on folk art. From the beginning of mankind to the present day, folk oral examples have been used in the arts such as literature and singing. The most beautiful of these examples is the art of giving. Art not only enriches a person's outlook and thinking, but also introduces him to the world of virtues, goodness, and beauty. Human life cannot be imagined without music. After all, art is one of the most important aspects of human spiritual activity, a great and powerful force that encourages creativity.

Today, in order to widely promote the art of bakhshi and story-telling in our country and abroad, to provide material and moral support to talented young bakhshi, masters of bakhshi, story-tellers, scientists of the field, according to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated April 26, 2018, No. 304 "Road map" for the years 2018-2022 was approved by the decision no. It is planned to control the complete and high-quality implementation of measures provided for in the "Roadmap", to coordinate the activities of responsible ministries and agencies, local state authorities on a systematic basis.

Preservation and development of unique examples of the art of Uzbek poetry and epic poetry, its wide promotion, strengthening the feelings of respect and attention to this art form in the hearts of the young generation, friendship between different peoples. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to hold the "International Art of Giving" festival on November 1, 2018 in order to strengthen friendship and fraternal ties, creative cooperation, cultural and spiritual relations at the international level. was accepted, and it was determined the need to organize creative meetings of scientists and practitioners of this field between the festival events. In connection with this, an international scientific conference on the topic "The role of the art of giving in world civilization" was organized. The main purpose of holding this scientific conference is to further develop the art of giving and writing epics, scientific study of epics of Uzbek and other nations, scientific cooperation in this regard, cooperation in the field of culture and art, as well as in the field of enlightenment on an international scale consists of expansion.

Epics embody very rich and ancient traditions of the artistic thinking of our people. Bakhshi is a folk storyteller, an artist who sings and recites songs and epics by heart, passing them down from generation to generation. Bakhshi should know the life and culture of the people, the history of the country he lives in, and how to play a certain music, and he should have

thoroughly mastered the art of hafiz. He should be able to effectively use various forms of the lively folk language, puns and puns, folk proverbs and expressions. One of the main requirements of telling a story is to be able to find a tone that captivates the audience, to tell the story in an attractive and interesting way. This, in turn, requires natural talent, strong perception, regular training with diligence and endurance. Bakhshis love to sing epics of various content that glorify loyalty to the motherland, love, friendship, brotherhood, being brave and brave, and heroism.

The epic of Khorezm has its own characteristics in terms of the composition of the repertoire. In almost all regions of Uzbekistan, individual performance dominates in the creation of epic works, but in Khorezm, collective performance is the leader. Khorezm epic is distinguished by its ancient roots, unique style and dialect, bright and attractive songs. In ancient Khorezm, story tellers were treated as lovers, bakhshis, and women as halfas. The word bakhshi should be close to the Persian word "*bakshidan*". When translated into Uzbek, the word from "*Bakhshi*" means "*to give*", "*to forgive*". In fact, Bakhshis have been artistically performing epics dedicated to one event, as if they had experienced it themselves.

The difference of Khorezm epics from other styles is its musicality, well-developed song texts, smooth climaxes of Khorezm epics, as in most Turkic peoples, instrumental preludes, curtain and vocal changes. One of the rarest aspects is that it is a unique style and dialect, a rich complex and at the same time common literary and musical reality.

The tunes and songs in the epics "*Gorogli*", "*Avazkhan*", "*Baziryon*" on the Khorezm road are not inferior to statuses or songs in terms of their potential. Khorezm epic consists of 2 main schools "*Shirvani*" and "*Iranian*". The common feature of both styles is that most of the Bakhshis are literally literate, and after reciting a part of the story, they do not weave poetry when it is their turn to sing, but instead compose the epic with a stable musical text. memorized and used instead. Sometimes they carry his manuscript with them and can use it during the performance.

Bakhshis in the Shirvani style often keep it a secret from anyone, even if they know the name of the epic. And those in the Iranian style sometimes add the name of the name during the story, where the text of the poem appears. Shirvani-style bakhshis sing epics accompanied by dutor, bulomon or gijjak, circles, while Iranian-style bakhshis perform epics mainly with dutor. It also differs from Shirvani in its dramatic mood, simple musical weight, restrained performance, and various jumping movements.

One of the main features of the Iranian style epic tradition is that bakhshi tells epics mainly with dutor. He is often accompanied by a bully or a bully. In some cases, the Bakhsh sings epics in front of the people alone, without musicians. Khorezm epic school has its own traditions and differs from other local epic schools. Khorezm's epics are distinguished by their performance in "*open voice*", serjilo instrumental prelude, curtain and pitch changes.

Bakhshis such as Ahmad Bakhshi, Gurbannazar Abdullayev (Bola Bakhshi), Rozimbek Murodov, Kadir Bakhshi Jumaniozov, Otakhan Bakhshi Matyokubov, Jumaboy Khudaiberganov, Qalandar Bakhshi Normetov, Norbek Bakhshi Abdullayev contributed a lot to the development of Khorezm epic. Kurbannazar Abdullaev (Bola Bakhshi) is one of the people who created a unique school of bakhshi in Khorezm. Kurbannazar Abdullaev knew by heart "*Avazkhan*", "*Ashiq Gharib va Shahsanam*", "*Gorogli*", "*Bozirgon*", "*Khirmon dali*", "*Ashiq Mahmud*", in total about 40 epics. In 1938, Kurbanazar Abdullayev (Bola Bakhshi) was awarded the title of "People's Epic of Uzbekistan". He was the first in Uzbekistan to receive such a title.

In short, as time goes by, technology penetrates deeply into people's lives, but people still rely on national spirituality. Our folklore art is past, present and future. The wise, great and eternal heritage of our people will glorify the Uzbek name everywhere and always. Because

at the core of original folklore works is an idea that serves for human perfection. It reflects the eternal history of the people.

To preserve and develop unique examples of this unique art, to promote it widely, to strengthen the feelings of respect and attention to this art form in the hearts of the young generation, and to further strengthen international cultural relations between the peoples of the world. Serves for It is necessary to thoroughly study the history of bakhshi and the art of epic writing, the work of bakhshi and epic writers, to conduct fundamental research in this regard, to restore the forgotten epics, and to pass them on to the next generation.

One of the main tasks in the development of schools of epics is to record performances of bakhshis on audio and video tapes, turn their work into a book, write down epics of Khorezm, and create films from these epics as much as possible. After all, epics, which combine several types of art such as literature, poetry, music and spectacle, are not only a means of education, but also a unique masterpiece of our cultural heritage.

REFERENCES:

1. T.Ismailov; "Characteristics Of Khorezm Doston Art" "Экономика и социум" №3(82) 2021;
2. Matyokubov B. "Zarhat pages of Khorezm epic performance" - Khorezm. Urganch publishing house. - 1999.
3. Matyokubov B. "Epics of the Epic" - Tashkent. "Building Print" publishing house. -2009.
4. Sarimsakov B. "Uzbek folk oral poetic creation" - Tashkent. Teacher's Publishing House. - 1990.

Modern Composer Creativity and Variety Art, Interaction Issues

Nazarov Khushnud Irkinovich

Head of the Department "Composition and Arrangement", associate professor National Institute of Pop Art named after B.Zokirov at the Uzbekistan State Conservatory

Annotation: This article discusses the characteristics of Estrada art in the work of modern composers and the creation of Estrada music in the work of Uzbek composers.

Keywords: Art, musical genre, pop, "Ra'no", "Gazli ko'xliklari", "Maxbubga", "Ketma Nigor", "Qaydasan", "Yor kel".

By modern compositional creativity, we can understand the creation of works in various genres, formed as a result of the musical development of the peoples of the whole world. For example, works in the following musical genres: opera, ballet, oratorio, cantata, symphonies, all stage musical works, choral works, instrumental works - quartets, sonatas and melodies, vocal works - romances, songs. and the creators who can create works can be called modern composers. We all know well that modern compositional art has a great place and importance in our spirituality and cultural development.

It is known that each era or time has its own spiritual world based on its level of development. The demand specific to the needs of the society is formed in proportion to the time of the worldviews suitable to the taste. The new way of thinking, attitudes and worldviews formed due to our independence are the basis of our unique idea of national independence. This is a sign of the spiritual perfection of the future great country. Today's main demands are to be independent in every field, to restore our national values and to operate within the framework of world standards. We can see this in the rapid development of modern composers' work and in the widespread spread of pop music forms among our people. In our music, universal musical forms, imbued with the spirit of the times, are developing more and more. It should be noted that the original state of our modern music is being enriched with new secular genres, typical of our day. Folk music can be said to be the manifestation of our national traditions and rituals in the tones. These examples are closely related to the daily life, training and national values of our people. In order to preserve them and pass them on to the next generation, special folklore ensembles have been established and are currently operating.

Pop music. The word Estrada means "hill" (supa) in Latin. In the 50s of the 20th century, the word pop entered music and began to be used as a small form of performing arts. Pop music is a leading part of pop art. Estrada is popular music of a light household character, the history of its formation begins with the theater and performance forms of Western nations. It developed from the interaction of the coffeehouse and music hall cultures popularized in the West. Asta - slow jazz, European and Eastern harmony and rhythm, rock, pop, etc. music and trends took over pop music. In Uzbekistan, pop music began to form in the 50s of the 20th century¹. It was founded by the famous pop star Botir Zakirov. In 1957, the young pop group

¹ Амануллаева Д. Обзор стилистических направлений вокально-джазового искусства Узбекистана (1991 –

from Uzbekistan successfully participated for the first time in the 6th International Festival of Youth held in Moscow and won the proud 4th place. It was a great achievement. After that, pop music quickly became popular and developed. Pop groups such as "Yalla", "Pakhtaoy", "Navo", "Sado" were formed.

Estrada music occupies a special place in the work of modern composers. A number of Uzbek composers have created and continue to work in this direction. For example, Rustam Abdullayev, Khabibullo Rahimov, Nadim Narkhodjayev, Dilorom Amannulayeva, Avaz Mansurov, Khurshida Hasanova, Aydin Abdullayeva and many other young composers are working effectively. Working in the pop song genre requires a lot from the composer: to have a sensitive sense of time, to be a kind of "barometer", to take into account the artistic taste of the listeners, to choose appropriate topics. Describing pop songs of Uzbek composers, it should be noted that they correspond to the general development of our time. "*The stylistic direction in pop art*," says D. Amanullayeva, is a unique "*fashion*" determined by the era and the listener. The song is a reflection of time, a "*mirror*" of our life.

For the development of pop songs, the composer D. Amanullayev has published a number of academic manuals: "Pop Songs" (Tashkent. 2007), pop-jazz vocalists (Tashkent. 2014), pop songs songs (Tashkent. 2015), which are included in the educational process and are fundamental educational material for pop students. In this genre, only composers who are in tune with the times can achieve their good results. The uniqueness of the pop genre, which has brought many composers of Uzbekistan wide popularity among the mass audience, has opened a new, interesting and active creative path for many composers.

In the 1970s and 1980s, almost all composers of that time, Mutal Burkhanov, Manas Leviyev, Sharif Ramazanov, Gafur Kadirov, I. Akbarov, I. Hamrayev, worked in the genre of pop music, and this is connected with the search for unique national means of expression. was liq. Composer Ikram Akbarov wrote and performed for the first time specially for the famous pop singer, People's Artist of Uzbekistan Botir Zakirov "*Ra'no*", "*Gazli ko'xliklari*", "*Maxbubga*", "*Ketma Nigor*", "*Qaydasan*", "*Yor kel*", "*Qo'shchinor*", "*Qor yog'ar*", "*Baxor vasli*", "*Azizim*", "*Lolazor chorlaydi*" pop songs like Uzbek Estrada gained fame with its charm in the composer's work. This rise in pop art gave the world bright examples, which later became classics of Uzbek pop art. Also, as we know, children's songs occupy a special place in pop music; they require the composer to know children's psychology, children's vocal data and voice abilities, the ability to sensitively feel the children's world, its variety and diversity. One of the signs of updating the musical system of the composer's children's song is the departure from the previous experiences of the composers (D. Saydaminova, A. Mansurov, D. Amanullayev) and the technique of pop music expected by the activities of the first children's VIA (Pakhtaoy, Guncha) created in the 1980s. Allows for wide use.

The pop song created by the Uzbek composer focuses on people, their feelings and thoughts. In this genre, various themes and plots aimed at reflecting modern human life and its time are covered. Composers find their own rhythm intonations, means of musical expression, placement of musical materials for their songs, but the most important thing in songs is the melody that composers create from the best musical language - chanting, characteristic of Uzbek song lyrics, and thus continuing the tradition. Today, Uzbek pop music corresponds to the basics of musical art trends and meets all the requirements and indicators of this genre.

REFERENCES:

1. Amanullaeva D. Overview of the stylistic trends of the vocal-jazz art of Uzbekistan (1991 - 2009) // Processes of reforming the system of musical education. T., 2009.
2. History of Uzbek Soviet Music, Volume III. T., 1991.
3. Messner E. Fundamentals of composition. M., 2001.
4. Nazaikinsky E.V. The logic of musical composition. M., "Music", 1982.

Work on a Small Polyphonic Cycle in the Class of Special Piano

(on the example of Prelude and Fugue No. 8 "In Memory of Navoi" by G.Mushel)

Madina Fayziyeva

Associate Professor, Honored Artist of the Republic of Uzbekistan Head of the Department of Special Piano, Uzbekistan State Conservatory

Abstract: The article is devoted to the issues of the pianist's work on one of the brightest and most original samples of the polyphonic small cycle. Prelude and Fugue No. 8 in c-moll "In Memory of Navoi" from the Piano Polyphonic Cycle 24 Preludes and Fugues by the brilliant Uzbek composer and pianist George Muschel.

The study and subsequent performance of this creation contributes to the development of the pianist's creative thinking, professional improvement, artistic and intellectual growth of the individuality. It is open to the performer the world of Uzbek piano polyphony, which characterized by bright and original national imagery.

Keywords: prelude, fugue, polyphonic ear, imagination, personality, fantasy, artistic image, funeral procession, elegy, melody, national coloring, nuance, performer, intellect.

The piano polyphonic cycle 24 preludes and fugues (1975) by George Muschel (1909 - 1989), a remarkable composer and pianist, is a highly artistic example of the musical twentieth century. "The theme of twenty-two (out of 24) macrocycles is based on the intonations of Uzbek folk music".¹ Prelude and Fugue No. 8 c-moll "In Memory of Navoi" is one of the most inspired works by Muschel, where he expressed his love and respect for the great thinker of the East, whose genius he repeatedly turned to in his work. In 1941 - 1942, Muschel wrote the Second Symphony, dedicating it to the memory of Navoi, which is a four-movement cycle. "Strophes from different works of the poet, proposed as an epigraph to each part of the symphony, allow the author to convey a generalized program".² In a certain sense, the Prelude and Fugue "In Memory of Navoi" is a logical continuation of an important theme in Muschel's work, connected with the personality of the great poet.

Describing this microcycle, T. Gafurbekov emphasized: "This is perhaps one of the most profound, artistically convincing works of the cycle (apparently, it is no coincidence that it is also popular in the version for organ)".³ There is no doubt that in the repertoire of every Uzbek pianist, the cycle Prelude and Fugue No. 8 should take its rightful place.

It is advisable to start working on Prelude and Fugue No. 8 in c-moll with a general

¹ Вахидов А.А. Стилистические особенности прелюдий и фуг Г. Мушеля. – Ташкент: Ўқитувчи, 1982, с. 3.

² Каримова З. Г. Навои в музыке. – Т.: Издательство литературы и искусства памяти Г. Гуляма, 1988, с. 132.

³ Гафурбеков Т. Б. О национально-народных истоках узбекской камерно-инструментальной музыки // Музыкальная культура Узбекской ССР. – М.: Музыка, 1981, с. 231.

acquaintance with the work, its imaginative world, features of the musical language, and compositional structure. Cycle No. 8 is built on the principle of contrast between Prelude and Fugue. The sphere of images of the Prelude is sublime, lyrical, the Fugue is tense, dramatic.

The Andante prelude is a three-part form with a developing middle. The initial melody develops against the background of rhythmically moving chords, in the structure of which seconds and quarts occupy a significant place:

According to the insightful and deep observation of T. Gafurbekov: “In the Prelude - elegy, the features of a majestic procession, a funeral procession, as if seeing off the immortal son of the Uzbek people, the poet-humanist, clearly appear”.⁴ This observation of a musicologist is important for understanding the figurative world of the Prelude and choosing performing means.

The national coloring of the sound is given by the use of the fifth reduced degree of the mode in singing turns preceding the cadenzas. The middle section of the Prelude does not contain fundamentally significant changes in texture. At the same time, the intonationally developing initial melody here acquires a general register decrease. If the melody in the first section sounded mainly in the second octave, and the closely spaced harmony mostly in the first, then in the middle section the melody sounds mainly in the first octave, and the harmony in the small one. It is very important for a pianist to pay attention to these features of the texture, and to show all the timbre nuances in the performance.

In the last four bars of the middle section, the contemplative-song melody acquires the features of declamation. “In fact, the section ends with two “exclamations” that have a pathetic connotation”.⁵ This moment is the climax of the Prelude. At the same time, it can be seen as a forerunner of the tense dramatic figurative world of the Fugue. In the reprise, the opening melody varies. The composer sets out the final motives of the melody an octave lower, and then returns them to the previous pitch level, which logically and harmoniously affirms the main thesis of musical thought.

Comprehending the sound embodiment of the Prelude, the pianist needs to focus on the deep philosophical content of the music, which reveals a stylistic commonality with some of the preludes from D. Shostakovich's Twenty-four Preludes and Fugues, in particular, with the Prelude in C major, which opens this monumental cycle. The austere, majestic character of the Prelude in c-moll evokes associations with the old sarabandes from the clavier suites. In this sense, the Prelude provides the pianist with the richest source for the manifestation of his performing talent and thinking. “The ability to penetrate into the world of perfect sounds is not in an arbitrary reading of the text, not in the ostentatious emphasis on this or that contrapunctuating voice, not in doubling and additions. The true merits of interpretation depend on a heightened sense of counterpoint, on the ability to link the art of Bach's polyphony with the quality of the modern piano”.⁶ This wise reasoning by S. Feinberg regarding the interpretation of Bach's polyphony can rightly be attributed to the performance of G. Muschel's polyphonic works, especially the Prelude and Fugue in c-moll, which are

⁴ Гафурбеков Т. Б. О национально-народных истоках узбекской камерно-инструментальной музыки // Музыкальная культура Узбекской ССР, с.231.

⁵ Вахидов А. А. Стилистические особенности прелюдий и фуг Г. Мушеля, с. 24.

⁶ Фейнберг С. Е. Мастерство пианиста. – М.: Музыка, 1978, с. 55.

distinguished by the composer's bold approaches to the embodiment of the polyphonic idea.

The Moderato fugue is innovative both in general and in details. In terms of innovative methods of polyphonic writing and musical dramaturgy, it goes beyond the framework of classical fugues, which T. Gafurbekov notes: "Reliance on quarter-quint foundations, predominant ostinato texture, moreover, with a consistent mutual development of song-cantilena constructions with instrumental (dutar-tanbour) acting out, undoubtedly come from the nature of the Uzbek monody".⁷

According to the correct observation of A. Vakhidov, "the three-voice fugue is combined with the recitative, which occupies a significant place in the form".⁸ Unusual is the very beginning of the Fugue, which opens with a recitative that contrasts with the Prelude, translating the music into the realm of dramatic collisions. The low register of the instrument, octave unison conduction, *ff* nuance, sharp dissonant harmonies require special attention of the pianist:

The recitative, in which the influence of D. Shostakovich is noticeable, has its source not only in vocal, but also in instrumental recitation. "This is evidenced by his melodic and textural warehouse, a clear orientation towards organ sound (by the way, the author at the end of the fugue gives a remark about the existence of an organ edition)".⁹ It should be noted that Muschel uses here a three-line piano score notation of the musical text, for a more vivid display of the voices of a polyphonic polyphonic fabric.

After three pathos sounding of the recitative, the actual Fugue begins. The theme is exhibited in the nuance of *pp* in the middle voice after the completion of the recitative. This is one of the few extremely concise polyphonic themes. It occupies only two cycles. Her intonations are closely related to the melody of recitative. In the theme, attention is drawn to the presence of lowered second and fourth steps of the mode, which gives the melody a special expressiveness, deepens its lyric-philosophical character. The deep national soil of the Fugue is manifested in its commonality with maqom origins, in particular, with the Navo melody from Sarahbori, cited by O. Matyakubov in his book "Maqomot":¹⁰

Common features of the Fugue theme with maqom origins are found in Namuda Navo-rang from Sarahbori Navo, cited by O. Matyakubov in his book "Uzbek classical music":¹¹

⁷ Гафурбеков Т. Б. О национально-народных истоках узбекской камерно-инструментальной музыки // Музыкальная культура Узбекской ССР, с. 232.

⁸ Вахидов А. А. Стилистические особенности прелюдий и фуг Г. Мушеля, с. 25.

⁹ Там же, с. 25.

¹⁰ Матякубов О. Р. Мақомот. – Т., 2004;

¹¹ Матякубов О. Р. Узбекская классическая музыка. Книга 2. Теоретические основы. – Т., 2015, с. 39.

Throughout the Fugue, the interval composition of the theme varies, which enriches its emotional figurative world.

The fugue is characterized by the extreme concentration of musical material. There are almost no interludes in it. This is partly dictated by the properties of the topic itself - its brevity and at the same time the capacity, fullness of the content. On the other hand, the functions of the interludes are taken over by the recitative - being intonationally connected with the theme, it simultaneously creates the necessary contrast to it. The recitative is carried out in the Fugue three times, taking into account the exposition. It permeates the Fugue and acquires important dramatic significance as the climactic phases of development. On the one hand, recitative is a generalization of development, on the other hand, it is an impulse to continue development.

The aphorism of the musical statement in the Fugue is due to the composer's contact with Navoi's poetry, which is characterized by the mastery of oriental miniatures, such genres as ghazals, rubaiyat. Navoi's poetic miniatures comprise several thousand ghazals, which he liked to combine into cycles of beits. Therefore, the ratio of recitative and theme can be likened to bayts in the poetic miniatures of Navoi.

The reprise of the Fugue, like its previous section, is also innovative. The culmination of the theme in the bass after a long organ point on the dominant, against which three performances of the theme are given, although it establishes the main key of the fugue, but at the same time continues to develop. In the intensity of the development of thematism in this case, the combination of functions is manifested, the processuality of the form is activated. "The combination of functions, according to V. Bobrovsky, is the basis of all forms of movement (variability) of the musical form".¹² Thus, the accumulation of movement energy takes place, which is stabilized in the *Meno mosso* section, where a cadenza is given in three measures based on the material of the final construction of the Prelude. A miniature four-bar coda in the *pp* nuance reminisces the main motif common to the theme of the Fugue and recitative, which here sounds like an echo against the background of a sustained tonic bass.

Thus, Prelude and Fugue No. 8 "In Memory of Navoi", c-moll, provides the pianist with an interesting example of a small polyphonic cycle, the study of which contributes to the development of creative thinking, professional improvement, artistic and intellectual thesaurus of personality. It opens the world of Uzbek piano polyphony, which is characterized by bright and original national imagery, to the performing musician. The development of an individual performance concept for this work contributes to the development of the young pianist's professional competence and implies mastery of a wide range of historically established and innovative aspects of modern musical performance.

REFERENCES:

1. Вахидов А.А. Стилистические особенности прелюдий и фуг Г. Мушеля. – Ташкент: Ўқитувчи, 1982;
2. Каримова З. Г. Навои в музыке. – Т.: Издательство литературы и искусства памяти Г. Гуляма, 1988;

¹² Бобровский В. П. Функциональные основы музыкальной формы. – М.: Музыка, 1978, с. 43.

3. Гафурбеков Т. Б. О национально-народных истоках узбекской камерно-инструментальной музыки // Музыкальная культура Узбекской ССР. – М., 1981;
4. Фейнберг С. Е. Мастерство пианиста. – М.: Музыка, 1978;
5. Бобровский В. П. Функциональные основы музыкальной формы. – М.: Музыка, 1978.

Expression of Education in the Family in the Karakalpak Language

Berdimuratova G. A

Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan Department of Karakalpakstan, Karakalpak humanities science and research Doctoral student of the institute

Abstract: The article talks about family relations and kinship attitudes, educational issues discussed in his language. In the vocabulary of the Karakalpak language, it has the first place in the sense of the relationship between father, father, life partner, birth-relative, and child-child relations.

Keywords: linguoculturalism, family, cognitive, culture, concept.

Language painting in world cognition is a historical representation of views and world structure in language. Each natural language has its own picture of the world. For that reason, categorial-semantic studies related to the concept of family are being carried out in world language education, and a number of scientific works have been developed in such orientations as the study of the concept of "family" within the framework of concepts in the education of every national language, and the study and characteristics of its semantic properties. [1. 34p].

In the works of art, the study of the concept of family, how to interpret the signs and characteristics of events and phenomena, the expression of attitude, and, at the same time, the relationship between national culture, national color, and the form of marriage, in the expressed attitude, are considered. These studies, of course, rely on the precious moments and experiences of scientists of the past. Their participation in this orientation will not only help them learn the scientific achievements of these subjects, but also contribute to the development of these subjects.

In analyzing the concept, J. Lakoff, M. Johnson, Langacker, Jackendorf R. and S. Stepanov, A. P. Babushkin, Yu. D. Apresyan, S. Kh. Lyapin, v. I. Karasik, D. O. Dobrovolsky, N. N. Boldyrev, I. A. Sternin, E. S. Kubryakova, Yu. N. We can mention the scientific works of scientists such as Karaulov Sh. Saparov, D. Ashurov.

In this article, we will talk a little about the place of the family in the culture of the Karakalpak people.

More recently, the origin of the word "oyl", explaining the meaning of the Arabic "child, needy", is noted in "Farhangi tili Tajiki". A person's heart and mind are the purest, the purest feelings, the basic understanding and views of life are molded in the house.

In our people, what kind of a person is, his behavior, upbringing, character and attitude towards the family are appreciated. This is important for him to find his place in society. There are such rules and regulations that are not written in the world, they have been passed down from generation to generation by our ancestors for many centuries. It is considered a sacred place where every nation, nation, while keeping the time, ensures the development of national abilities and gives birth to mentally and physically perfect children. In this regard, in our research, we will focus on the concepts related to family vocabulary.

In order to know the meaning of a word, we use the explanatory dictionary, and by understanding the meaning of this word, we get acquainted with the corresponding concept. One of the most valuable opinions is D.S. According to Likhachev, he showed that: "...the right concept does not come from the meaning of the word; it is the result of the meaning of the word in the dictionary and the experience of the individual and the people." [2, p. 17]

The Family Institute is considered to be the most important public institution that provides consultation to a clear linguistic and cultural center from the cultural, psychological and social point of view with the individual characteristics of each person. A person evaluates representatives and relationships in the sociocultural space compared to the stereotypes in his center, his culture. A person receives these stereotypes and cultural assets from the family. In addition to the fact that valuable cultural traditions, relations, discipline, customs and traditions, which have been molded since childhood, are the most important defining orientation for a person, these stereotypes can change during his life.

According to V. A. Maslova, for the culture of any people, the most important and relevant world events are considered as the topics of proverbs, prose and poetic works in the language. [3, s. 37-38].

It is possible to include the phenomenon of the family, which has unique personality and national differences (social, ethical, politeness), among the universal concepts. The national difference of the modern concept can be learned only by comparing it with other cultural content. Here it is shown in the works of a number of scientists (Y.V. Zheleznova, A.A. Mamedgasanova, N.N. Zanegina, M.A. Terpak, A.S. Trushchinskaya, E.S. Sirotkina) on comparative relational learning. . In addition, the attention of scientists has been directed to the concepts that appeared based on the representations of other related words that are close to the concept of family.

Parallel research works of Kazakh scientists are devoted to learning the semantics of the terms marriage and family, kinship relations in the family, and their activities. Kazakh scientist Kh. Argynbayev's novel "Kazakh household" was written as a result of 20 years of ethnographic and archival research.

Like the peoples of Central Asia, the Karakalpak people are considered to be a rich people with their own family traditions, national values, and customs. This, in turn, creates a contrasphere. According to Sh.S. Saparov, the main task of cognitive philology is to learn the mental processes that take place in the human mind in a business-related way related to the language, the objects of its analysis are education and practical application [4: 11p].

In Karakalpaks, the rules of behavior at home and in public places are being strictly observed to this day. Karakalpaks, like the people of the East, eat food sitting on the ground (floor), place food on the table with their hands, and eat liquid food in separate special dishes. Taking water from the hand in front of the aukat, after washing, did not shake hands, eating aukat started from an older age or from a meal, the customs and rules were kept, this was a sign of freedom and respect. In ancient times, kefir and yogurt were drunk as a liquid, and the tradition of making tea began to appear in the Central Asian peoples, including Karakalpaks, at the beginning of the 19th century. The birth of a baby in Shanurak causes great excitement among the Karakalpak people. Special attention is paid to naming a baby. For naming, older elders or religious scholars are recommended. 40 days after the birth of the baby, there is a ceremony to bathe the baby, and a large party is held, and the tradition of putting the baby in the cradle is held. He puts a mirror to let it be. All kinds of charms are put on the baby's crib or clothes to protect it from the evil eye and dangers.

Karakalpak weddings are held in several stages, like the Turkic folk. Kuyeud's parents hand over their gifts to the girl. In this case, older people give permission for marriage. Then they agree on the girl's money.

Family is the most important educational occasion for Karakalpak people and occupies an important place in human life. The first lessons of education are learned in the family, valuable family traditions and personal qualities are molded in this family and passed from one child to another. Education in the world has a great place in the development of an individual and has a great influence on his life. The study of shanugarak, studying it from the sociological, psychological and pedagogical point of view, is becoming the focus of scientists.

In Karakalpak households, in most cases, not only father, mother, and children make it, but also great-grandfather, old woman's sister, another married brother or sister, their children, and their children make a big household together. Doing this together, gathering at the same table and having a meal can strengthen kinship relations and have a great educational character. They sit together at the father's table and solves the problems in the family, gives advice, supports and strengthens each other in spiritual and material ways. This type of communication and manner of behavior in the environment does not instill calmness, harmony, patience, unity, demandingness, care and maturity in children and molds human qualities. Even if one of the households is separated from the family, they remain in the care of their elderly parents, take care of them in their household work, and help with the upbringing of their children. Such houses are very strong and tasteful. The effectiveness of education in the village depends on the number of children and their willingness.

In Karakalpak people, the relationship with the girls in the family is almost non-existent, and they have favorable preferences compared to other peoples. A girl child in the dust is considered to be a symbol of happiness, success, purity, wealth of the household, purity. The respect for girls is special, and they are seated in various places of honor.

The way of life of the Karakalpak people has a positive effect on education. In particular, a few houses make a village, many houses make a big village, and a few villages make a clan, and a few clans shape a society. Communities build the world together. My family is a province, and provinces together create a country. Therefore, it proves that the people's work together in peace and harmony, in harmony, is directly related to strong relationships in the family.

Good words are one of the most effective methods of education. Our people have valuable proverbs: "A good word is food for the soul" and "A good wish is half a dream". Kindness, kindness, and respect can be molded in children with good words. Therefore, in order to protect the child from this or that undesirable activity, it is necessary to make it clear that such activities will lead to undesirable results and guide him in a good way. For example, when you say not to cross in front of a hidden person, you need to explain two moral meanings. First, crossing is a sign of indecency and disrespect, and secondly, it means that if you return the favor, that is, if you do something that touches the heart and mind of an older person, he will be angry with you.

The warning "Don't cover your face" means that the dead person's face will be covered, so it should be explained that this is a bad ritual. It is said that if the face is covered, it will be difficult to breathe and it will harm the health.

"You can't shoot white swans." A white swan is considered to be a symbol of love and happiness. White swans never breed in pairs, they teach us to protect our mother nature and not to harm it.

Putting a child in his place and giving him a gift to give him the way and status of an older one can have a great educational meaning. The proverb "If a person comes from the door, then from the hole" has a deep meaning. In the tradition of the Karakalpak people, there is a great educational meaning that happiness and fortune come with the guest who comes to the house. This is considered as a way of teaching hospitality, harmony, agreement.

Sitting on the table. The manners and rules of self-control, eating from an early age, not talking, spitting, sitting together, saying goodbye after a meal, thanking those who prepared food, bring up great responsibility and discipline in children.

Social relationships such as being friendly with neighbors, having a brotherly relationship, choosing friends wisely, being hospitable, polite, have an important place for the child's future. As the saying goes, "Seven neighborhood parents for one child" has a great impact on the education of the neighborhood and the center of the community. There is a saying in our people: "Buy not a good house, but a good neighbor." That's why neighbors, friends, colleagues have a positive influence on the child's education.

The word "Family" has many associations with "close people", "a group of relatives", "happy parents, and grandparents", "and a community of married couples who love each other", "a group of kind people", and it is appropriate to mention that they are "people who never sell, support and empower each other".

Coming out of these ideas, the concept of "brighter" in our language was depicted in various "colors" (words). In particular, family is "lovely", "huge", "happy", "kind", "good", "loving", "many children", "rich", "wonderful", "Culturized", "provided", "urban", "good", "educated", "incomparable", "caring", "quiet", "everyone is waiting for you" are mentioned by me.

Literatures:

1. Stepanov Yu.S. Constants: Dictionary of Russian Culture. Research experience. - M.: School "Languages of Russian culture", 1997.
2. Likhachev D.S. Conceptosphere of the Russian language // Liberation from dogmas: the history of Russian literature: the state and ways of studying / Russian Academy of Sciences, Institute of World Literature. A.M. Gorky; resp. ed. D.P. Nikolaev. M., 1997. T. 1. S. 33–42.
3. Maslova V.A. Linguoculturology.–M.: "Academy", 2001. - P.208
4. Safarov Sh. Kognitiv tilshunoslik. "Sangzor" nashriyoti, 2006y

Issues of Increasing Population Level and Welfare

Sh. S. Sharifov

PhD., Associate Professor of the Department of Economics Branches Samarkand State University named after Sharof Rashidov

D. E. Rashidova

Assistant of the Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Abstract: This article discusses the ongoing positive work in our country to improve the standard of living and welfare of the population and the scientific and theoretical views of our economists in the interpretation of the authors, as well as conclusions and recommendations.

Keywords: standard of living, well-being, quality of life, lifestyle, agriculture, service, poverty, low income.

In our country, there was a need to create a concept of improving the well-being of the population in accordance with the new socio-economic conditions. In its formation, some rules of the "Quality of Life" concept, which has been widely used in global practice in recent years, can be used. Because this concept forms the conditions that define a person's physical, mental and social well-being. Here it is not only about objective factors that evaluate the quality of life (food, housing, employment, level of education), but concepts such as "well-being", "happiness", "satisfaction", "pleasure" are subjective feelings of a person. is also being discussed. For example, the level of health, family relationships, work, financial situation, creativity, etc. are important components of satisfaction.

V. Bobkov, A. Pochinok and other economists defined the concept of "well-being" as follows: well-being is the provision of the population with material, social, cultural and spiritual resources necessary for life, that is, elements, services and conditions that satisfy human needs.

The standard of living of the population is considered the most important criterion for evaluating the effectiveness of the country's socio-economic policy, and its implementation is the main goal of society's development. First of all, the standard of living is characterized by the combination and interdependence of two components: the provision of material and non-material resources of the population and their level of consumption.

I. Hasanov, A. Eminov think about the level of increasing the income of rural families in the conditions of the market economy.

- determination of consumer requirements, assessment of their development opportunities and determination of the form, method and order of satisfaction;
- increase the income structure of the population and determine the prospects for change;
- predicting the growth of consumption and improving its composition;
- changing the structure of consumer demand;
- determining the ways and terms of solving the housing problem;

➤ development of services, education, culture, healthcare, as well as transport and communication.

A. Kadirov "In order to ensure social equality, a number of social events are being implemented in our republic. In particular, minimum wages and other payments were usually increased in advance, linked to changes in prices, which ensured that the population remained solvent and did not allow the standard of living to fall sharply. In this way, by increasing the minimum wage, an increase in the average wage and monetary income of the population was achieved," he says. A. Akobirova reminds that one of the main indicators of raising the standard of living of the population in the conditions of the market economy is an adequate salary.

R.Karlibaeva, I.Danabaev express the opinion that the priority directions of development of rural infrastructure should not only aim to raise the standard of living in villages, but also to develop all sectors and industries in the same direction.

In this regard, N. Mahmudov writes, "By taking a broader approach to the issue of socio-economic modeling of rural development and welfare, ensuring rural development and welfare is carried out on the basis of activities that are directly related to each other and have their own characteristics." According to him, the well-being of the life of the villagers depends on the effective organization and management of the production process there. The production process, in turn, is inextricably linked with the activities of the supply and service sectors with specific quantitative units.

Thus, the concept of "Quality of life" includes human interactions with the environment. They represent the extent to which needs are met and the extent to which existing capabilities are in line with expected capabilities. In addition, the implementation of the rules of the concept serves as the main foundation for the further improvement of the living conditions and well-being of the villagers. For this, it will be necessary to study the conditions of the villages, to evaluate their interaction with the environment, to use the available opportunities, to meet their needs and to adapt to the expected opportunities.

Quality of life means, in a broad sense, the satisfaction of the population with their life in terms of various needs and interests. This concept includes characteristics and indicators of the standard of living, work and recreation, housing conditions, social security and guarantees, maintenance of legal order, natural and climatic conditions, indicators of environmental protection, availability of free time and opportunities for its rational use, and finally, peace. , embraces calm, domestic comfort and stability.

Quality of life is a category that includes objective and sociological components that go beyond the economy, i.e. satisfaction of needs and interests, satisfaction of people with life.

The transition period as a long-term process conditionally includes intermediate processes such as deepening of economic reforms and liberalization of the economy, democratization of society, and modernization of the country.

It is necessary to pay attention to three changes that have become the most important characteristic of the period of transition to the market economy. These are the "loss of the state" of the task of individual disposal of resources, the budget crisis and transformational decline, the formation of a multi-level economy at the expense of large and small economic entities in the form of new ownership.

Of course, the democratization of social life in the conditions of the market economy gradually opens a wide path for entrepreneurs. The return of property to the producers, the full transition to the market economy will lead to an increase in the standard of living of the population.

The system of international statistical indicators is also used in the detailed study of the living conditions, well-being and living standards of the population. International statistics of living standards have been developed since the second half of the 20th century. In 1960, the UN working group created a system of indicators of the standard of living in the report on the principles of determining and evaluating the standard of living of the population. The last version of the system of indicators reflecting the standard of living of the population was developed by UN International Statistics in 1978. It includes indicators belonging to 12 groups:

1. Birth, death and other demographic description of people.
2. Sanitary and hygienic conditions.
3. Food consumption.
4. Housing conditions.
5. Information and culture.
6. Labor and employment conditions.
7. Income and expenses.
8. Cost of living and consumer prices.
9. Vehicles.
10. Organization of recreation.
11. Social security.
12. Human freedom.

These indicators protect the interests of the general population, improve housing conditions, labor and employment levels, sanitation and hygiene conditions, social support, organize recreation, and increase the well-being of the population.

Scientists define the concept of standard of living in different ways.

By following an active social policy in Uzbekistan, the population is provided with free services, social assistance is provided to its needy groups. If we consider the trends of living well-being in the regions of our country, especially in rural areas, which are not related to the level of income, education, healthcare, provision of communal services, provision of clean drinking water and heat are among the service sectors. Inequalities in access to these services persist.

Although incomes have started to increase during the transition to market relations, the quality of services provided to the population in rural areas is still insufficient. After all, several factors influence the improvement of the living conditions of rural residents. It is observed that these factors are interconnected, that there is a certain relationship between them, that the development of one affects the change of the other. For example, the higher the production, the higher the welfare. However, the growth rate of welfare is not the same as the growth rate of the economy. Because it depends on how much of the income is spent on consumption.

It depends on the amount of savings. The distribution of income is also important. Distribution is influenced by the social commitment of its participants. If the social functions of the state are strengthened, its consumption in the gross income will be greater. As companies take on greater liabilities, their share of profits also increases. Finally, if the majority of social needs are met at the expense of the population's income, its contribution to income increases. In the market system, the main part of gross income goes to households.

Such distribution of income refers to its remaining part after accumulation.

Since the level of economic and social well-being characterizes the quality of life, the World Bank considers their indicators in the human well-being index. Since it is a measure of quality of life, its generalized indicator does not always correspond to the level of economic well-being. If economic well-being is directly related to the level of production, social well-being is also related to the accumulated national wealth, for example, intellectual potential, the size of non-productive funds. All aspects of welfare are summed up in the national welfare fund. It is a sum of consumer funds and non-productive investments aimed at improving people's livelihood.

In our opinion, in order to improve the standard of living and conditions of the population, it is necessary to take a serious approach to the issue of modeling in order to determine the level of consumption of the population in many ways, to assess the possibilities of their development, and to develop the perspectives of determining the forms and methods of meeting their needs.

In assessing the living conditions and well-being of the population, its consumption costs are also of incomparable importance. The analysis of the state of these expenditures showed that a number of problems closely related to their prospective evaluation should be solved. The following sources of information were used to provide a preliminary prospective assessment:

- a) the dynamics of money expenses and incomes of rural residents of the region;
- b) the budget of rural residents of the region;
- c) regional consumption budget.

During the analysis of interdependence, a system of preliminary assessment of material benefits and services received by the villagers is derived.

Based on the above, it is necessary to solve a number of problems in order to widely use econometric modeling, taking into account the climate, customs and conditions of the market economy of each region in order to improve the living conditions, lifestyle and standard of living of the population in the modernization of the country:

- elimination of differences in the field of service between the village and the city;
- modeling of the priority development of market infrastructure entities serving in the regions;
- improvement of the competitive environment between market infrastructure entities providing services in the regions;
- priority development of excellent technological processes that produce competitive products by introducing modern advanced technologies in the regions;
- modeling of the fuller involvement of production funds and labor forces in economic circulation, that is, management of the correct use of limited resources of society.

It is clear to all of us that in the course of today's economic reforms in our country, great attention is paid to the urbanization of villages, that is, to the improvement of the living conditions and well-being of the villagers. Remarkable work is being done, especially in terms of development of service sectors and deepening of economic reforms in this area. Therefore, due to the large production volume and technologically large enterprises processing agricultural products were transformed into joint-stock companies.

Quantitative indicators of material security of the population (per capita national product and income, consumption of food products, basic non-manufactured goods, services, housing, etc.) occupied a high place in the past. Life expectancy, mortality, including infant mortality,

unemployment, income inequality, educational attainment, environmental conditions, and other such indicators are now prioritized. A number of service industries serve to develop them, especially in rural areas, by introducing modern advanced technologies, forming a competitive service environment, improving living conditions and increasing the well-being of the population.

Literature

1. Sotsialnaya politika, uroven i kachestvo jizni. Dictionary. - M.: VTsUJ, 2001.
2. K.Kh. Abdurahmanov, K.Kh. Abdurahmanov. Population lifestyle and income. Study guide. Tashkent, TDIU, 2010, p. 15.
3. Hasanov, A. Eminov. To what extent is increasing the family income organized? "Economic Bulletin of Uzbekistan" magazine, 2001, issues 7-8, pages 41-42.
4. A. Kadirov, R. Bozorov. The place and role of the national currency in improving the well-being of the population. "Economy and Education" magazine, 2008, issue 2, page 113.
5. R. Karlibaeva, I. Danabaev. Priority areas of rural infrastructure development. "Agriculture of Uzbekistan" magazine, 2009, issue 8, page 30.
6. N. Mahmudov. Socio-economic model of rural development and welfare improvement. "Economy and Education" magazine, 2010, issue 1, page 21.

A Comprehensive Review of the Fishes of the Aral Sea: Past, Present, and Future Perspectives

Jamila Jiyenbaeva

Gulistan Dawekeeva, biology teacher at Nukus Olympic and Paralympic Sports Training Center 3rd year student of the Faculty of Biology, KSU

Abstract: The Aral Sea, once the world's fourth-largest inland body of water, has experienced significant ecological changes over the past few decades. The decline in water levels due to water diversion for agricultural purposes has resulted in dramatic alterations to the sea's ecosystem, profoundly impacting its fish fauna. This scientific article provides a comprehensive review of the fishes of the Aral Sea, focusing on their historical presence, current status, and potential future scenarios. The aim is to shed light on the consequences of ecological degradation and highlight the importance of conservation efforts for the revival of this unique aquatic ecosystem.

Key words: diversity, types of fish, sea, Aral, Amu Darya, Syr Darya, ecology

Introduction: The Aral Sea, situated in Central Asia, was once renowned for its rich biodiversity and abundant fish populations. However, excessive water withdrawals from the two major rivers that feed the sea, the Amu Darya and Syr Darya, have caused a drastic reduction in water levels. As a result, the sea has fragmented into smaller remnants, leaving a significant impact on the fish species inhabiting its waters. This article aims to present a comprehensive overview of the fishes of the Aral Sea, discussing their historical distribution, current status, and potential future scenarios.

Materials and discussion: Historical Distribution: Historical records suggest that the Aral Sea was home to a diverse range of fish species. It was once a thriving ecosystem supporting economically important species such as the Aral barbel (*Barbus brachycephalus*), Sevan trout (*Salmo ischchan*), and the unique endemic Aral lamprey (*Eudontomyzon mariae*). These fishes played crucial roles in the food web and contributed to the local fishing industry.

Ecological Impact and Current Status: The ecological changes caused by the shrinking of the Aral Sea have had a profound impact on its fish fauna. The decline in water levels, increased salinity, and degradation of water quality have led to the extinction or severe decline of numerous fish species. [1.82] Endemic species have been particularly vulnerable, and many commercially important fish populations have collapsed. Currently, only a limited number of resilient species, including the Aral roach (*Rutilus rutilus aralensis*) and the Amu Darya shovelnose sturgeon (*Pseudoscaphirhynchus kaufmanni*), are still found in the remnants of the sea.

Conservation Efforts:

Efforts to restore the Aral Sea and its fish fauna have gained momentum in recent years. Various projects focus on water management, re-establishing connectivity between the remaining sea basins, and introducing fish species adapted to the current environmental conditions. Successful reintroduction programs have shown promise in reviving populations of native fish species, giving hope for the future of the Aral Sea's aquatic biodiversity.

Future Perspectives:

The future of the fishes in the Aral Sea depends on effective water management, sustainable fishing practices, and continuous ecological restoration efforts. Ongoing research aims to understand the adaptive capacities of fish species and their responses to changing environmental conditions. Collaborative initiatives involving local communities, governments, and international organizations are crucial for the successful recovery of the Aral Sea's fish fauna. [2.78]

The Aral Sea has witnessed the extinction of several fish species due to the severe ecological changes it has undergone. Species like the Aral trout (*Salmo trutta aralensis*) and Aral barbel (*Barbus brachycephalus*) have disappeared completely. The critically endangered Aral sturgeon (*Acipenser nudiiventris*) and the endemic Aral lamprey (*Eudontomyzon mariae*) are on the brink of extinction. Although the fish diversity in the Aral Sea has significantly declined, a few resilient species continue to persist. These include the Aral roach (*Rutilus rutilus aralensis*), Amu Darya shovelnose sturgeon (*Pseudoscaphirhynchus kaufmanni*), and various carp species (Cyprinidae family). These remaining fish populations have adapted to the changed environmental conditions of the smaller sea remnants. One of the major challenges for fish in the Aral Sea is the increased salinity resulting from the shrinking water body. As the water volume decreased, salinity levels rose dramatically, exceeding the tolerance thresholds of many fish species. The rise in salinity has disrupted the osmoregulation processes and reproductive capacities of fish, further contributing to population declines.

Efforts to restore the Aral Sea's fish fauna involve both conservation and reintroduction programs. Conservation initiatives aim to protect the remaining fish species and their habitats, mitigate pollution, and reduce illegal fishing activities. Reintroduction programs focus on restocking native fish species in the sea, using captive breeding and hatcheries. These programs often prioritize the reestablishment of commercially valuable species, such as the Aral roach and shovelnose sturgeon. Ecological Consequences: The decline of fish populations in the Aral Sea has had cascading ecological consequences. With the reduction in predatory fish species, populations of herbivorous and planktivorous species have surged, leading to imbalances in the food web. [3.109] Additionally, the loss of fish biomass has affected the nutrient cycling and energy flow within the ecosystem, influencing other organisms, including birds and mammals, dependent on fish as a food source. International Collaboration: Given the transboundary nature of the Aral Sea, international collaboration is crucial for the conservation and restoration efforts. Organizations such as the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and the International Fund for Saving the Aral Sea (IFAS) have been actively involved in coordinating projects and providing financial and technical support to the affected countries, fostering regional cooperation for the sustainable management of the Aral Sea.

Future Challenges:

The restoration of the Aral Sea's fish fauna faces numerous challenges. These include ongoing water diversion for agricultural purposes, limited financial resources for conservation projects, and the need for long-term monitoring and adaptive management strategies. Climate change further exacerbates these challenges, as rising temperatures and altered precipitation patterns may affect the hydrology and ecological dynamics of the sea. [4.14]

The Aral Sea is located in Central Asia, bordered by Kazakhstan to the north and Uzbekistan to the south. Historically, it was one of the largest inland bodies of water in the world, spanning an area of approximately 68,000 square kilometers (26,300 square miles). It was fed by two major rivers, the Amu Darya and Syr Darya, which flowed from the Pamir and Tian Shan mountain ranges. The Aral Sea has undergone significant environmental changes over the past few decades. In the 1960s, extensive irrigation projects were initiated to divert water

from the Amu Darya and Syr Darya rivers for agricultural purposes, primarily cotton cultivation. As a result, the inflow of water into the sea was drastically reduced, leading to a continuous decline in water levels. The shrinkage of the Aral Sea has been one of the most dramatic environmental transformations of modern times. Its water volume has decreased by more than 80%, causing the sea to fragment into smaller remnants. The once-vast expanse of water has been replaced by deserts and salty plains, known as the Aralkum Desert, due to the exposure of the seabed. [5.72]

Ecological Consequences:

The shrinking and fragmentation of the Aral Sea have had severe ecological consequences. The decline in water levels has resulted in increased salinity and reduced water quality, making the environment hostile for many aquatic species. The disappearance of the sea has disrupted local weather patterns, leading to hotter summers and colder winters in the surrounding regions.

Human Impact:

The environmental changes in the Aral Sea region have had significant impacts on human populations. Fishing communities that relied on the sea for their livelihoods have suffered due to the collapse of fish populations and the loss of employment opportunities. The deterioration of water quality has also posed health risks, as the blowing dust from the exposed seabed carries toxic chemicals and salts, contributing to respiratory and other health issues.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the fishes of the Aral Sea have experienced a significant decline in species diversity and abundance due to ecological degradation. However, conservation and restoration efforts offer hope for the recovery of this unique aquatic ecosystem. By addressing the challenges and implementing sustainable management practices, it is possible to conserve the remaining fish species, reintroduce extirpated species, and revive the ecological integrity of the Aral Sea. The fishes of the Aral Sea have faced significant challenges due to ecological degradation caused by water diversion. The loss of numerous fish species and the collapse of once-thriving populations have disrupted the ecological balance of this unique aquatic ecosystem. However, ongoing conservation efforts and restoration projects provide hope for the recovery of the Aral Sea's fish fauna. By implementing sustainable practices and prioritizing the conservation of native fish species, it is possible to revive this fragile ecosystem and ensure the long-term viability of its aquatic biodiversity.

References:

1. Micklin, P. P. (2007). The Aral Sea Disaster. *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences*, 35, 47-72.
2. Glantz, M. H., & Kostianoy, A. G. (Eds.). (2012). *The Aral Sea Encyclopedia*. Springer Science & Business Media.
3. Jumabaev, K., & Ataniyazova, O. (2018). Environmental Impacts of the Aral Sea Crisis. In *Environmental Management of River Basin Ecosystems* (pp. 271-284). Springer.
4. Karimov, B., & Vlek, P. L. G. (Eds.). (2010). *The Aral Sea Basin: Water for Sustainable Development in Central Asia*. Springer Science & Business Media.
5. Micklin, P. (2008). The future Aral Sea: hope and despair. *Environment*, 50(4), 6-21.
6. Micklin, P. P. (2016). The Aral Sea Crisis. In *Landsc*

Research on automation of gas meters and introduction of technological mobile application system in the Republic of Uzbekistan

Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi

Student of Nukus Mining Institute

Abstract: As we are currently living in the era of advanced technology, we need to use the opportunities of technology properly. Currently in the Republic of Uzbekistan technological automation, studying the technical parameters of machines and having real-time information are gaining importance. Connecting gas meters to the system in the Republic of Uzbekistan is considered a complicated process. The reason is that every house uses natural gas (methane). This means that each gas meter is checked by one person from door to door, which is time-consuming and prone to human error. Android to automate this system automatically calculates and analyzes gas meters through a mobile camera. An application was presented when calculating the gas meter and meter numbers are attached to the application and automatically calculated using optical character recognition technology to obtain consumption units. This proposed software prototype was tested for 30 gas meters and it showed 97% accuracy results. It is a technology based application enhanced for reading numbers and reading barcodes. The purpose of this article will be to establish a program for calculating gas meters through a technological application and prevent errors.

Keywords: Technical automation, parameters of gas meters, viewing in the computer system, attaching the meter to the android application, software for detecting optical symbols, barcode reader application mode

Introduction: Currently, highly mechanized and productive sectors of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan are developing. In production areas automated system materials are widely used. A gas meter is a special flow meter used to measure gas. We use it to measure the volume of fuel gases such as natural gas (methane) and liquefied petroleum gas. Gas meters are used by these enterprises in all residential, commercial and industrial buildings that consume fuel gas supplied by gas service is established. It is necessary to install these gas meters in accordance with their technical parameters and to pass GOST standards in case of errors. Meter staff should be proficient in a specific set of skills and opportunities should be created to do the job properly. Meter readers must also find their way into the meter, it will be necessary to ensure that the meters work correctly regardless of the obstacles. This is important. The amount of time to manually record each meter, which can lead to human error and may lead to conflict between consumers and service providers due to incorrect records, and there is currently no proper data management system to facilitate accurate calculation and proper documentation. Reading the meter requires processes that cause various problems. Gas volume computing glitches, software update delays, and bug detection issues are the primary means and it is one of the most difficult problems for industries to find answers to. Related to the current procedure to the gas consumption calculation process and the gas meter reading system is not fully automatic. The meter involves manual procedures from the moment the reader starts reading the meter and the last counter reading will remain unchanged until you refresh the device. Meter readings are entered manually and the device is

handed over by the data entry clerk in the office. Therefore, such situations warrant an automated system to help generate gas bills correctly, while also allowing easy verification of gas bill records. The system also aims to eliminate problems and errors. This often happens with the calculation and production of gas bills that provide an efficient moment and helps update gas bill records. This calculation system was researched by O'telbayev Azizbek in house 105, house 79, Amir Temur street, Nukus, Republic of Karakalpakstan, and with gas consumers in this multi-storey building. A closer look revealed that there is currently no such fully automated gas meter the absence of a reading system with significant functionality. Some of the documents discussed here are just confusing and causing problems. presents the idea of a combination of mobile and web applications based on a technological system. Counter the reader must have an Android application with optical character recognition technology. The consumer takes an image of the meter and the mobile computing app extracts data from the image. This data is then sent to the server-side web application. Then the server restarts and data will automatically generate the account and email the account to the consumer. This article suggests, it will be enough for the consumer to provide the android application with a map of the counters and provide the data. This is the picture then automatically processed by the computing system and sent to the server and the server creates after the system and sends the bill to the consumer. It offers the use of an android application with an automatic calculation system and the counter is formed based on the existing system for the student. Receives image extract data using consumers and sends the data to the server. The server creates the account and sends it to him the consumer thereby makes payments. Here the server can receive and broadcast consumer complaints. In the system any relevant information will be saved automatically.

Parameters and description of technological gas meters

The system consists of a meter reader who reads the meter through a mobile application and a consumer who checks the consumption units at home through a mobile application. This will help you track your gas usage over the course of a month. Designed for mobile application supporting both meter and user is our main goal. The application works using automatic system management monitoring mode technology. The admin panel is a website with full access to a large database, which is responsible for manipulating data, creating calculations and saving reports, as well as many other tasks. . As shown in Picture 1, a picture of the tasks and the counter. Includes a meter that reads the gas meter through a mobile application and displayed by a user who checks household consumption units through a mobile application. Counter based on studies to monitor gas usage within a month. Designed for mobile application helps the calculator reader and user to calculate quickly and easily. The application works using system technology. Computing system is a website with full access to a large database, which data manipulation, calculation creation and automatic storage of reports, and much more including functions.

Picture 1. Gas meter parameters and indicators of the calculation system currently used in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Conclusions

Technology is increasingly developing and entering industries with new modern technology. There have been technological advancements since the beginning of the era of technology development led to a huge increase in industrial productivity. The solution for this research is, we have shown how to solve problems with the manual gas meter calculation system. This reduces human errors in recording readings and automates the system from the server side. Also, the counter is easy to use by the student and the customer and avoids excessive time consumption. In this way, counter workers travel less loads and they can collect readings from more numbers more easily and more accurately. In addition, customers have the opportunity to view their gas bills mobile app and can pay bill online. Admins are also easy there are options to perform their tasks through the web application.

Picture 2. Problems in the computing system and the appearance of a program that is not attached to the technical system.

Results

The application based on technological computing system uses new technology, which has low production cost, low performance and costs, more information security and less labor required. The proposed software prototype was tested on 30 gas meters (in apartment buildings) and it gave 97% accuracy results in reading both numbers. The technology system application is attached to the barcode reader software to view and pay this bill. Another advantage of the technological computing application is that it connects the meter to the network and creates the possibility of their automatic control. For example, you can see how much gas you use in your home per day or at a certain time. O'telbayev Azizbek, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute under the Navoi State University of Mining and Technology, is conducting research on the automation of the computing system through computer networks in an automated program based on the technological system. If these studies are successful, we may implement an automatic alert mode program for meter technology control.

References

1. qizi, Y.H.B. 2023. Research on Automated System Testing in Web Site Applications. *International Journal on Integrated Education*. 6, 5 (May 2023), 98-104.
2. Baxtiyor qizi, Y. H. . (2023). Methods of Temperature Management and Control at the Interface of Technological System Applications. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 18, 33–39. Retrieved from <https://emjms.academicjournal.io/index.php/emjms/article/view/958>
3. Yo'ldoshova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi. (2023). AUTOMATION OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES AND THE IMPORTANCE OF THE TECHNOLOGICAL SYSTEM IN THE FUTURE OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES. *Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal*, 4(05), 16–23. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/4BHNU>
4. Allambergenova Mexribanu Mirzabek qizi. (2023). WAYS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF THE PRODUCTION LINE IN ENTERPRISES THROUGH INDUSTRIAL ROBOTS. *INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY*, 3(5), 83–89. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7911704>
5. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). Development of automated power supply management system software. *Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 17, 114–120. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejet/article/view/4061>

6. Qizi, Y. H. B. (2023). Use of Wireless Technologies in the Automation of Technological Processes. *International Journal on Orange Technologies*, 5(4), 7-16. Retrieved from <https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJOT/article/view/4256>
7. Qizi, Y. H. B. . (2023). Setting the Time Mode in the Process of Automating Robots. *Pioneer : Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress*, 2(4), 37–46. Retrieved from <https://innosci.org/jarsp/article/view/1133>
8. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). RESEARCH ON CREATING A WIRELESS MACHINE CONTROL SYSTEM THROUGH ROBOTIZATION AND AUTOMATION OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES. *Neo Scientific Peer Reviewed Journal*, 9, 52–63. Retrieved from <https://neojournals.com/index.php/nspj/article/view/168>
9. Yeshmuratova Amangul Artikbayevna, Amanbaev Nursultan Salamat o'g'li, O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li. (2023). ENSURING COMPUTER DATA AND MANAGEMENT SYSTEM SECURITY. *INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 3(4), 282–287. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7809865>
10. Yeshmuratova Amangul Artikbayevna. (2023). TECHNOLOGICAL METHODS OF ENSURING INFORMATION SECURITY IN TECHNICAL SYSTEMS. *EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH*, 3(4), 188–192. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7809700>
11. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi, Uzaqbergenov Aytbay Jumabay o'g'li, & Erejepova Altingul Nuratdinovna. (2023). ABOUT THE AUTOMATION AND ROBOTIZATION OF THE TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESS OF SOFTWARE. *European Scholar Journal*, 4(2), 106-110. Retrieved from <https://scholarzest.com/index.php/esj/article/view/3252>
12. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). AUTOMATION AND MONITORING OF PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES USING IOT. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7693583>
13. Mirzabek qizi, A. M., & Orinbay qizi, K. S. (2023). Application of Modern Microprocessors in Technological Measuring Devices and Principles of their Use. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 32, 320–326. Retrieved from <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1158>
14. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). TECHNOLOGICAL AUTOMATION PROGRAM OF THE MOBILE PLANNING SYSTEM FOR ROBOTS. *American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 14, 189–200. Retrieved from <https://ajird.journalspark.org/index.php/ajird/article/view/586>
15. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). Automation Technique Design Classification of Technological Objects. *International Journal of Scientific Trends*, 2(2), 128–136. Retrieved from <https://scientifictrends.org/index.php/ijst/article/view/66>
16. Yo'ldoshova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi. (2023). Use of energy-saving operational technological systems in automation processes. *The Peerian Journal*, 16, 60–70. Retrieved from <https://www.peerianjournal.com/index.php/tpj/article/view/515>
17. Janabay Qizi, K. A. . (2023). Application of Automation Tasks and Management of Technological Processes. *Pioneer : Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress*, 2(3), 13–19. Retrieved from <https://innosci.org/jarsp/article/view/940>
18. Yo'ldoshova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi. (2023). AUTOMATION OF WORK WITH E-MAIL AND ROBOTICS SYSTEM CONTROL SYSTEM. *INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 3(3), 394–404. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7776607>
19. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AUTOMATION WELDING PROCESS SYSTEM TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH.

- INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, 3(3), 611–621. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7794534>
20. Yo'ldoshova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi. (2023). MANAGEMENT OF THE SYSTEM SCHEME OF AUTOMATION OF ROBOTIZATION PROCESSES. INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY, 3(3), 183–193. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7776593>
 21. Yo'ldoshova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi. (2023). PRODUCTION PLANNING IN TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES AND ROBOTIC PROCESS AUTOMATION PROGRAMS. European Scholar Journal, 4(3), 137-143. Retrieved from <https://www.scholarzest.com/index.php/esj/article/view/3332>
 22. qizi, Y. H. B. . (2023). Stages of Modern Technological Development of Automation of Robotization Processes. Miasto Przyszłości, 33, 284–293. Retrieved from <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1233>
 23. Janabay qizi, K. A., Jumabay o'g'li, U. A., & Nuratdinovna, E. A. (2023). Application and Technological Description of Microprocessors in Technological Measuring Devices. Miasto Przyszłości, 33, 89–96. Retrieved from <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1192>
 24. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). IN THE MANAGEMENT OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES A PROCESS MODEL THAT SUPPORTS DESIGN AUTOMATION. INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY, 3(3), 213–223. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7794553>
 25. Dauletov Kalniyaz Abatbayevich, & Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). Research on methods of automatic control of constant pressure compressors. Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology, 20, 17–22. Retrieved from <https://zienjournals.com/index.php/tjet/article/view/3917>
 26. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). STAGES OF SELECTION OF CONTROL TECHNOLOGY IN THE AUTOMATION OF THE CONTROL SYSTEM OF ROBOTS. JournalNX - A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal, 9(5), 100–106. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/9G5AF>
 27. Uteniyazov A. K. et al. The effect of ultrasonic treatments on current transport processes in Al-Al₂O₃-p-CdTe-Mo structure //Advances in Materials Science and Engineering. – 2021. – T. 2021. – C. 1-6.
 28. Dauletov K. A. et al. A heat-resistant Schottky diode based on Ge/GaAs heterosystem //Poverkhnost. – 1999. – №. 3. – C. 60-62.
 29. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). Development of automated power supply management system software. Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology, 17, 114–120. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejet/article/view/4061>
 30. Yo'ldoshova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi. (2023). Technological computing processes in system automation in the management of technological processes. Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology, 18, 16–21. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejet/article/view/4125>

Digital technologies in the educational system

Asamatdinova Mexribanu Muratbay qizi,

Assistant teacher of Faculty of computer engineering

Ayapbergenova Saltanat Shinpolatovna,

Assistant teacher of Faculty of Telecommunication Technology and Vocational Education

Abstract: Digital technologies have revolutionized various aspects of human life, and the educational system is no exception. In recent years, the integration of digital technologies into education has emerged as a significant catalyst for transforming traditional teaching and learning methods. This article explores the impact of digital technologies in the educational system, highlighting the benefits, challenges, and future prospects. By examining the implementation of digital technologies, such as online learning platforms, educational apps, and virtual reality, we uncover their potential to enhance student engagement, foster personalized learning experiences, and promote global connectivity. Additionally, we discuss the importance of addressing concerns related to access, equity, and data privacy to ensure that the benefits of digital technologies are harnessed by all learners. Overall, digital technologies have the potential to shape a more dynamic and inclusive educational landscape, preparing students to thrive in the 21st century.

Key words: digital technologies, educational system, online learning, personalized learning, student engagement, global connectivity, challenges, future prospects

Introduction: Currently, highly mechanized and productive sectors of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan are developing. In production areas automated system materials are widely used. A gas meter is a special flow meter used to measure gas. We use it to measure the volume of fuel gases such as natural gas (methane) and liquefied petroleum gas. Gas meters are used by these enterprises in all residential, commercial and industrial buildings that consume fuel gas supplied by gas service is established. It is necessary to install these gas meters in accordance with their technical parameters and to pass GOST standards in case of errors. Meter staff should be proficient in a specific set of skills and opportunities should be created to do the job properly. Meter readers must also find their way into the meter, it will be necessary to ensure that the meters work correctly regardless of the obstacles. This is important. The amount of time to manually record each meter, which can lead to human error and may lead to conflict between consumers and service providers due to incorrect records, and there is currently no proper data management system to facilitate accurate calculation and proper documentation. Reading the meter requires processes that cause various problems. Gas volume computing glitches, software update delays, and bug detection issues are the primary means and it is one of the most difficult problems for industries to find answers to. Related to the current procedure to the gas consumption calculation process and the gas meter reading system is not fully automatic. The meter involves manual procedures from the moment the reader starts reading the meter and the last counter reading will remain unchanged until you refresh the device. Meter readings are entered manually and the device is handed over by the data entry clerk in the office. Therefore, such situations warrant an automated system to help generate gas bills correctly, while also allowing easy verification of gas bill records. The system also aims to eliminate problems and errors. This often happens

with the calculation and production of gas bills that provide an efficient moment and helps update gas bill records. This calculation system was researched by O'telbayev Azizbek in house 105, house 79, Amir Temur street, Nukus, Republic of Karakalpakstan, and with gas consumers in this multi-storey building. A closer look revealed that there is currently no such fully automated gas meter the absence of a reading system with significant functionality. Some of the documents discussed here are just confusing and causing problems. presents the idea of a combination of mobile and web applications based on a technological system. Counter the reader must have an Android application with optical character recognition technology. The consumer takes an image of the meter and the mobile computing app extracts data from the image. This data is then sent to the server-side web application. Then the server restarts and data will automatically generate the account and email the account to the consumer. This article suggests, it will be enough for the consumer to provide the android application with a map of the counters and provide the data. This is the picture then automatically processed by the computing system and sent to the server and the server creates after the system and sends the bill to the consumer. It offers the use of an android application with an automatic calculation system and the counter is formed based on the existing system for the student. Receives image extract data using consumers and sends the data to the server. The server creates the account and sends it to him the consumer thereby makes payments. Here the server can receive and broadcast consumer complaints. In the system any relevant information will be saved automatically.

Parameters and description of technological gas meters

The system consists of a meter reader who reads the meter through a mobile application and a consumer who checks the consumption units at home through a mobile application. This will help you track your gas usage over the course of a month. Designed for mobile application supporting both meter and user is our main goal. The application works using automatic system management monitoring mode technology. The admin panel is a website with full access to a large database, which is responsible for manipulating data, creating calculations and saving reports, as well as many other tasks. . As shown in Picture 1, a picture of the tasks and the counter. Includes a meter that reads the gas meter through a mobile application and displayed by a user who checks household consumption units through a mobile application. Counter based on studies to monitor gas usage within a month. Designed for mobile application helps the calculator reader and user to calculate quickly and easily. The application works using system technology. Computing system is a website with full access to a large database, which data manipulation, calculation creation and automatic storage of reports, and much more including functions.

Picture 1. Gas meter parameters and indicators of the calculation system currently used in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Conclusions

Technology is increasingly developing and entering industries with new modern technology. There have been technological advancements since the beginning of the era of technology development led to a huge increase in industrial productivity. The solution for this research is, we have shown how to solve problems with the manual gas meter calculation system. This reduces human errors in recording readings and automates the system from the server side. Also, the counter is easy to use by the student and the customer and avoids excessive time consumption. In this way, counter workers travel less loads and they can collect readings from more numbers more easily and more accurately. In addition, customers have the opportunity to view their gas bills mobile app and can pay bill online. Admins are also easy there are options to perform their tasks through the web application.

Picture 2. Problems in the computing system and the appearance of a program that is not attached to the technical system.

Results

The application based on technological computing system uses new technology, which has low production cost, low performance and costs, more information security and less labor required. The proposed software prototype was tested on 30 gas meters (in apartment buildings) and it gave 97% accuracy results in reading both numbers. The technology system application is attached to the barcode reader software to view and pay this bill. Another advantage of the technological computing application is that it connects the meter to the network and creates the possibility of their automatic control. For example, you can see how much gas you use in your home per day or at a certain time. O'telbayev Azizbek, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute under the Navoi State University of Mining and Technology, is conducting research on the automation of the computing system through computer networks in an automated program based on the technological system. If these studies are successful, we may implement an automatic alert mode program for meter technology control.

References

1. qizi, Y.H.B. 2023. Research on Automated System Testing in Web Site Applications. *International Journal on Integrated Education*. 6, 5 (May 2023), 98-104.
2. Baxtiyor qizi, Y. H. . (2023). Methods of Temperature Management and Control at the Interface of Technological System Applications. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 18, 33–39. Retrieved from <https://emjms.academicjournal.io/index.php/emjms/article/view/958>
3. Yo'ldoshova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi. (2023). AUTOMATION OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES AND THE IMPORTANCE OF THE TECHNOLOGICAL SYSTEM IN THE FUTURE OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES. *Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal*, 4(05), 16–23. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/4BHNU>
4. Allambergenova Mexribanu Mirzabek qizi. (2023). WAYS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF THE PRODUCTION LINE IN ENTERPRISES THROUGH INDUSTRIAL ROBOTS. *INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY*, 3(5), 83–89. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7911704>
5. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). Development of automated power supply management system software. *Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 17, 114–120. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejet/article/view/4061>
6. Qizi, Y. H. B. (2023). Use of Wireless Technologies in the Automation of Technological Processes. *International Journal on Orange Technologies*, 5(4), 7-16. Retrieved from <https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJOT/article/view/4256>
7. Qizi, Y. H. B. . (2023). Setting the Time Mode in the Process of Automating Robots. *Pioneer : Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress*, 2(4), 37–46. Retrieved from <https://innosci.org/jarsp/article/view/1133>
8. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). RESEARCH ON CREATING A WIRELESS MACHINE CONTROL SYSTEM THROUGH ROBOTIZATION AND AUTOMATION OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES. *Neo Scientific Peer Reviewed Journal*, 9, 52–63. Retrieved from <https://neojournals.com/index.php/nspj/article/view/168>
9. Yeshmuratova Amangul Artikbayevna, Amanbaev Nursultan Salamat o'g'li, O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li. (2023). ENSURING COMPUTER DATA AND MANAGEMENT SYSTEM SECURITY. *INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 3(4), 282–287. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7809865>
10. Yeshmuratova Amangul Artikbayevna. (2023). TECHNOLOGICAL METHODS OF ENSURING INFORMATION SECURITY IN TECHNICAL SYSTEMS. *EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH*, 3(4), 188–192.

- <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7809700>
11. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi, Uzaqbergenov Aytbay Jumabay o'g'li, & Erejepova Altingul Nuratdinovna. (2023). ABOUT THE AUTOMATION AND ROBOTIZATION OF THE TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESS OF SOFTWARE. *European Scholar Journal*, 4(2), 106-110. Retrieved from <https://scholarzest.com/index.php/esj/article/view/3252>
 12. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). AUTOMATION AND MONITORING OF PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES USING IOT. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7693583>
 13. Mirzabek qizi, A. M., & Orinbay qizi, K. S. (2023). Application of Modern Microprocessors in Technological Measuring Devices and Principles of their Use. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 32, 320–326. Retrieved from <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1158>
 14. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). TECHNOLOGICAL AUTOMATION PROGRAM OF THE MOBILE PLANNING SYSTEM FOR ROBOTS. *American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 14, 189–200. Retrieved from <https://ajird.journalspark.org/index.php/ajird/article/view/586>
 15. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). Automation Technique Design Classification of Technological Objects. *International Journal of Scientific Trends*, 2(2), 128–136. Retrieved from <https://scientifictrends.org/index.php/ijst/article/view/66>
 16. Yo'ldoshova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi. (2023). Use of energy-saving operational technological systems in automation processes. *The Peerian Journal*, 16, 60–70. Retrieved from <https://www.peerianjournal.com/index.php/tpj/article/view/515>
 17. Janabay Qizi, K. A. . (2023). Application of Automation Tasks and Management of Technological Processes. *Pioneer : Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress*, 2(3), 13–19. Retrieved from <https://innosci.org/jarisp/article/view/940>
 18. Yo'ldoshova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi. (2023). AUTOMATION OF WORK WITH E-MAIL AND ROBOTICS SYSTEM CONTROL SYSTEM. *INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 3(3), 394–404. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7776607>
 19. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AUTOMATION WELDING PROCESS SYSTEM TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH. *INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 3(3), 611–621. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7794534>
 20. Yo'ldoshova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi. (2023). MANAGEMENT OF THE SYSTEM SCHEME OF AUTOMATION OF ROBOTIZATION PROCESSES. *INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY*, 3(3), 183–193. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7776593>
 21. Yo'ldoshova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi. (2023). PRODUCTION PLANNING IN TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES AND ROBOTIC PROCESS AUTOMATION PROGRAMS. *European Scholar Journal*, 4(3), 137-143. Retrieved from <https://www.scholarzest.com/index.php/esj/article/view/3332>
 22. qizi, Y. H. B. . (2023). Stages of Modern Technological Development of Automation of Robotization Processes. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 33, 284–293. Retrieved from <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1233>
 23. Janabay qizi, K. A., Jumabay o'g'li, U. A., & Nuratdinovna, E. A. (2023). Application and Technological Description of Microprocessors in Technological Measuring Devices. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 33, 89–96. Retrieved from <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1192>
 24. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). IN THE MANAGEMENT OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES A PROCESS MODEL THAT SUPPORTS DESIGN AUTOMATION. *INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY*, 3(3), 213–223. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7794553>

25. Dauletov Kalniyaz Abatbayevich, & Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). Research on methods of automatic control of constant pressure compressors. *Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 20, 17–22. Retrieved from <https://zienjournals.com/index.php/tjet/article/view/3917>
26. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). STAGES OF SELECTION OF CONTROL TECHNOLOGY IN THE AUTOMATION OF THE CONTROL SYSTEM OF ROBOTS. *JournalNX - A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal*, 9(5), 100–106. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/9G5AF>
27. Uteniyazov A. K. et al. The effect of ultrasonic treatments on current transport processes in Al-Al₂O₃-p-CdTe-Mo structure // *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering*. – 2021. – T. 2021. – C. 1-6.
28. Dauletov K. A. et al. A heat-resistant Schottky diode based on Ge/GaAs heterosystem // *Poverkhnost*. – 1999. – №. 3. – C. 60-62.
29. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2023). Development of automated power supply management system software. *Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 17, 114–120. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejet/article/view/4061>
30. Yo'ldoshova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi. (2023). Technological computing processes in system automation in the management of technological processes. *Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 18, 16–21. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejet/article/view/4125>

Selecting a proper method for teaching grammar as a skill for adult students by conducting a detailed research.

Sayfullayeva Fayozaxon Tohirovna

Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology

Email: fayoza_sayfullaeva@icloud.com

Abstract: One of the clear perspective needed issues of learning and teaching is the role which the grammar has in the foreign languages. As Rinvoluceri (1984) cited, explicit teaching should not be facilitated in L2 classrooms that input hypothesis affirms the acquisition of L2 language competence through exposure. As long as learners experience by comprehensible and meaningful way, they can acquire by exposure instead of explicit grammar. However, paradoxically, he recommends giving grammar by story-telling and reading as homework only for adult learners in high schools. Moreover, he also suggests that it should be conducted in mini-lessons covering only simple rules just to satisfy the curiosity as filling gaps without expecting the acquisition of grammar rules in the classrooms.

Key words: grammar error, explicit grammar, story-telling, acquisition of grammar, rules, present continuous, interlanguage development.

Introduction: This research includes the learner's profile, the chosen grammar point and its description for remedial teaching and a proper lesson plan. The identification of the grammar errors in productive skills of the learner is given in the accordance with the interview and the writing sample that is the core reason for the topic of the remedial teaching.

To finish this small-scale project successfully including the grammar errors and the helpful lesson creation the appropriate participant A was selected to be involved in doing the interview voluntarily that she found comfortable to state her name with a particular letter to feel confidential. To form a more real imagination, providing general linguistic factors including educational success and potentials regarding learning languages, styles, methods, age and institutions are considered as first crucial initials. The first course student of the World Languages University was chosen whose nationality is Uzbek. She is an enthusiastic 17 years old girl who wants to learn language skillfully as a native speaker. As she stated in the interview that she started learning English as L2 after her critical period when she was 15 years old which shifted more obstacles for her to learn the target language faster. This was the reason to try various learning styles and methods to develop the proficiency that led to find out her own favorable approach to continue learning. As her dominating learning style is kinesthetic, the same unchanged process feels somehow dull. Because she mostly try different situations by changing them more often that this process needs to include real practice, acting and touching. Usually she appreciates communications as a tool for learning regarding speaking with friends, chatting with natives through texting and sending voice messages. Moreover, she prefers to learn by imitating and copying from natives' speech gradually to improve native-like production, listening them to raise the comprehension and writing reviews and descriptions for books and movies. She tries to live up-to-date, that's why she always watches and listens the latest movies and songs in English languages. One trait of her feels quite similar with mine that she is quite risk-taker and obsessed with

American sitcoms, that's why she can communicate with a lot of native phrases and vocabularies. As she has an introvert personality, she developed the fluency well by interacting a lot.

However, she has sensible errors to use the grammar correctly that the accuracy limps in productive skills. For example, she said "it is raining since morning" in the interview. Currently her level is pre-intermediate that she has B1 certification which was taken for the entrance of the university. I got her writing "My recent holiday" that revealed some considerable grammar errors with present perfect continuous. Furthermore, she has misunderstandings of the usage "since" and "for". These were the reason for me to choose "Present perfect continuous" with time expressions as a topic for my remedial teaching and the lesson plan.

Description of the grammar point

Being progressive forms of the tenses, present perfect continuous is considered one of the problematic grammar points for foreign language learners who mostly confuse the meaning with present perfect or present continuous. It was the challenge that the chosen participant encountered in more often in her both written and spoken discourse. This part of the project intends to find and analyze the source of the problem by realizing the nature of the present perfect progressive and searching for the proper and fruitful pedagogical approaches.

One of the burning challenges of teaching\learning of ESL\EFL students is to decide whether present perfect continuous forms or present perfect forms. This difficulty is because that one of the functions of the present perfect is to mention about the action that has started in the past and continues till the present which is almost the same with present perfect, according to Thornbury (1999). Although present perfect continuous form was not researched as the hot discussions in the linguistic field, there are a few particular definitions about it in the accordance of the aspect by several language specialists. Trask (1993) describes that the present perfect continuous tense is also called as present perfect progressive that defines actions or situation started in the past and still ongoing in the present. According to Crustal (2008), the construction is formed in this tense with two elements as subject + have\has + the present participle (root+ing) + objective that it serves to predicate by showing person and grammatical number. As Hartman and Stroke (1972) pointed out present perfect progressive is utilized to refer the unspecified time somewhere between "before now" and "now". Moreover, perhaps the speaker is thinking about the circumstance which started but possibly did not finish within that period of time. According to Trask (1993), the owner of the speech is interested in the process as well as the result that the process can be still continuing or can have just finished.

The main root of the problem of the target learner may be the willingness to study grammar that is set of rules defining the meaning by giving confusing structures in her mind. In turn, this may complicate the instructor's task and demands to give students motivation before introducing this part of the grammar. According to Nunan (1998) highlights that LL will never be able to interact by engaging in the target language explaining their ideas and emotions concisely unless they give emphasis on grammar of the language. As long as the students find the rules of grammar arduous, the instructor ought to create such materials which can grab learners' attention and make the lesson more enthusiastic. There are a number of ways to conduct grammar far more fabulous through integrating effective tools such as media, technology, video or audio into the lesson.

The other cause of learners' mistakes in the usage of present continuous tense can be the lack of ability to realize the rules and the meaning which is one of the learning challenges of grammar that was cited by Ellis (2006). Though the students understand the particular rule and they even may not have difficulty to place correctly, they are not able to use it in interaction accurately. According to Ellis (2006), this obstacle may come into existence as a result of selected pedagogical approaches that focus on rote learning rather than freely applied production of the target language. In modern English classrooms, the communication

skills are more appreciated to design the practical activities which is beneficial to motivate learners to produce target language freely and the structure of the grammar than making them to implement lower order activities. According to Shameem & Tickoo, new language grammar patterns can be engaged in effectively when learners are covered with communicational activities that gives the instructor advantage to observe potential learning problems.

Conclusion: As the properly chosen approaches and methods tend to be the key to intended success of the lesson, the crucial step of grammar teaching is to make clear the main spot of the lesson, form or meaning, maybe both of them. According to Doughty (2001), the emphasis of meaning is efficacious especially for interlanguage development. However, as DeKeyser (1998) claimed teaching target language forms explicitly by focusing on form approach tend to be more proper in EFL classroom as it is a gradual process. Teaching grammar as a skill originally was proposed by Batstone (1994) that it created possibilities to combine form and meaning equally. Therefore, the provided activities in lesson plan cover both form and meaning of Present Perfect continuous tense. Coming from the skill approach, the grammar can be integrated in the context combining with other skills. Moreover, to sequence the lesson PPP approach will be utilized to fit the grammar for overall context of the ESL\EFL lesson.

References:

1. Batstone, R. (1994). Grammar. Language Teaching: A Scheme for Teaching Education. UK: Oxford University Press.
2. Crystal, D. (2008). A Dictionary of Linguistics and Phonetics. (6th ed.). Oxford: Blackwell Publisher Ltd.
3. DeKeyser, R. (1998). Beyond focus on form: Cognitive Perspectives on Learning and Practicing Second Language Grammar. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
4. Doughty, C. (2001). Cognitive Underpinnings of Focus on Form. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
5. Ellis, R. (1993). Second Language Acquisition and Structural Syllabus. TESOL Quarterly, 27, 91-113.
6. Ellis, R. (2006). Current Issues in the Teaching of Grammar: An SLA Perspective. TESOL Quarterly, 40 (1), 83-107.
7. Hartman, R., Stroke, F. (1972). Dictionary of Language of Language and Linguistics. England: Applied Science Publishers LTD.
8. Nunan, D. (1998). Teaching grammar in context. ELT Journal, 52, 101-109.
9. Rinvoluceri, M. (1984). Grammar Games: Cognitive, Effective and Drama Activities for EFL Students. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
10. Shameem, N., Tickoo, M. (1999). New Ways in Using Communicative Games in Language Teaching. Alexandria, VA: TESOL.
11. Thornbury, S. (1999). How to teach grammar. Pearson Education Limited.
12. Trask, R. (1993). A Dictionary of Grammatical Terms in Linguistics. London: Routledge.

Features of designing knitwear

Matjanova Parwaz Baxitovna,
the Faculty of Industrial Technology

Abstract: Knitwear design plays a significant role in the fashion industry, encompassing both aesthetics and functionality. This scientific article explores the essential features of designing knitwear, focusing on the intricate interplay of various factors, including yarn selection, stitch patterns, garment construction, and innovation in design techniques. By understanding these features, designers can create knitwear that not only showcases unique aesthetics but also meets the practical requirements of comfort, durability, and versatility.

Key words: Knitwear design, Yarn selection, Stitch patterns, Garment construction, Innovation in design techniques, Functionality, Comfort

Introduction: Knitwear has evolved from traditional hand-knitted garments to a versatile and highly desirable fashion category. Designers have the opportunity to explore diverse yarns, textures, and stitch patterns to create unique pieces that cater to evolving fashion trends. This article delves into the key features of designing knitwear, examining the crucial aspects that designers must consider during the design process.

Yarn Selection: Yarn selection is a vital aspect of knitwear design, as it determines the characteristics of the final garment. Designers must consider factors such as fiber content, yarn weight, texture, and color. Each type of fiber possesses distinct properties, influencing the drape, stretch, warmth, and care requirements of the finished knitwear. Furthermore, the choice of color and texture significantly impacts the visual appeal and tactile experience of the garment. [1.89]

Stitch Patterns and Texture

Stitch patterns contribute to the aesthetics and functionality of knitwear. Designers employ various stitch patterns, such as cables, ribbing, lace, and colorwork, to create texture, depth, and visual interest. Each stitch pattern affects the fabric's stretch, drape, and thickness, influencing the fit and comfort of the garment. By understanding the characteristics of different stitch patterns, designers can achieve the desired visual and functional effects.

Garment Construction: Garment construction in knitwear design involves shaping, seaming, and finishing techniques. Shaping techniques, such as increases and decreases, enable designers to create fitted or oversized silhouettes. Seamless construction methods, such as circular knitting or knitting in the round, minimize seams for enhanced comfort and aesthetics. Additionally, designers employ various finishing techniques, such as blocking, edging, and embellishments, to refine the appearance and durability of the knitwear.

Innovation in Design Techniques: Advancements in technology and design techniques have revolutionized the field of knitwear design. Computer-aided design (CAD) software enables designers to visualize and manipulate intricate stitch patterns and garment shapes. Additionally, innovative knitting techniques, such as 3D knitting, allow for the creation of seamless, customized garments with minimal waste. Exploring these innovative techniques empowers designers to push the boundaries of knitwear design and offer unique, sustainable solutions. [4.106]

Functionality and Comfort

While aesthetics are essential, functionality and comfort are equally crucial in knitwear design. Designers must consider factors such as breathability, insulation, and moisture management to ensure the comfort of the wearer. Furthermore, incorporating stretch and flexibility into the design allows for ease of movement and adaptability. Balancing aesthetics with functionality ensures that knitwear is not only visually appealing but also practical for everyday wear. [3.65]

Designing knitwear requires a comprehensive understanding of the essential features that contribute to its aesthetic appeal and functionality. By carefully selecting yarns, employing appropriate stitch patterns, utilizing effective garment construction techniques, and embracing innovation, designers can create knitwear that captivates the fashion industry. The interplay between aesthetics and functionality is crucial, allowing for the creation of versatile, comfortable, and visually appealing knitwear garments that meet the demands of contemporary consumers. Silhouette and Fit: The silhouette and fit of knitwear play a significant role in the overall design. [4.87] Designers must consider the desired shape of the garment, whether it is loose and oversized, or fitted and tailored. This decision affects the choice of stitch patterns, construction techniques, and shaping methods. The silhouette and fit should align with the intended aesthetic and purpose of the knitwear, ensuring that it enhances the wearer's body shape and offers a flattering appearance. Pattern Development: Pattern development is a crucial aspect of knitwear design. Designers create patterns that guide the construction of the garment, including instructions for stitch patterns, shaping, and finishing details. Accurate and clear patterns are essential for both commercial production and individual knitting enthusiasts. Designers must pay attention to pattern drafting, charting, and instructions, ensuring that they are comprehensive and accessible to knitters of different skill levels. Sustainability Considerations: In recent years, sustainability has become a key consideration in the fashion industry, and knitwear design is no exception. Designers are increasingly focusing on eco-friendly practices by selecting sustainable fibers, such as organic cotton, bamboo, or recycled yarns. Additionally, they explore techniques like zero-waste knitting, upcycling, and incorporating modular design concepts to minimize material waste and reduce environmental impact.

References:

1. Crawford, A. (2011). *Basics Fashion Design 02: Textiles and Fashion*. AVA Publishing.
2. Braddock, S., & O'Mahony, M. (2014). *Techno Textiles 2: Revolutionary Fabrics for Fashion and Design*. Thames & Hudson.
3. Cheong, H., & Fan, J. (2019). *Knitting Technology: A Comprehensive Handbook and Practical Guide* (3rd ed.). Woodhead Publishing.
4. Hemmings, J. (Ed.). (2015). *The Textile Reader*. Berg.
5. Miles, M., & Smethurst, A. (2010). *The Thames & Hudson Dictionary of Fashion and Fashion Designers* (2nd ed.). Thames & Hudson.

PEDAGOGICAL VIEWS OF THE JADID ENLIGHTENMENT ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF GENDER CULTURE

Ochilova Gulnoza Asrorovna

Shakhrisabz State Pedagogical institute Teacher of the Department of Pedagogy

Annotation: this article reflects on the reforms and changes carried out by the state on the development of gender culture today. Also meditated are the pedagogical views of Western and eastern allomas and Jadid enlightenment on the shaping of gender culture.

Keywords: gender equality, family resilience, politics, economics, law, ideology and Culture, Education, Science, Oriental gender equality.

Introduction: One of the important problems today, there are many scientific views on the development of gender culture. This is due to the fact that it is important for the development of society to correctly formulate gender relations. Therefore, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his speech at the 46th session of the United Nations Human Rights Council, said: "We will continue strongly to work on issues of gender policy aimed at radically increasing the role of women in the socio-political life of our country and in the field of business", –he argued.

It is known that in accordance with Resolution No. 70 of the United Nations General Assembly adopted at the summit on Sustainable Development in September 2015, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a resolution "on measures to implement national goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development in the period up to 2030" in order to organize systematic work on At the same time, Uzbekistan has developed nine tasks related to "ensuring Gender equality and expanding the rights and opportunities of all women" as part of the implementation of the fifth goal of Sustainable Development. In accordance with the tasks of the fifth goal (Gender equality), it is necessary to eliminate any form of discrimination against all women by 2030, to ensure full and effective participation of women at all levels of decision-making in political, economic and social life, as well as equal opportunities for leadership.

In addition, this goal involves the introduction of the principles of gender equality in the process of adopting state programs at different levels of the state. In recent years, work has been carried out in several directions to ensure gender equality, to increase the role of women in social and political life:

improvement of women's rights legislation;

improving the institutional framework for the protection of Women / 2018;

increase awareness of gender equality and women's rights of the population;

education of officials responsible for ensuring compliance with them in the practice of application of law on the basis of the relevant legal norms.

Article 46 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that "women and men are equal", designated as. Hence, both the International and legal constitutional legal basis of gender equality is guaranteed. Gender equality also refers to social equality.

Gender is a social state in which the relationship between women and men is manifested in all spheres of life and activity of society, including politics, economics, law, ideology and Culture, Education, Science. The word “Gender is derived from the English” gender, Latin genus, meaning origin. If the biological sex divides humans into women and men, gender focuses on separating the place of women and men in society.

The fact that the state provides them with the same conditions and opportunities for women and men to find and define their place in society serves as the basis for ensuring gender equality. In Uzbekistan, in recent years, important measures have been taken to strengthen the legislative and institutional framework for ensuring gender equality. Issues of Gender equality are also reflected in our national legislation, that is, on September 2, 2019, the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on equal rights and guarantees of opportunities for women and Men” No. 562 was adopted. The document was adopted by the Ohio House of Representatives on August 23, 2019. In terms of the point of introduction of Gender equality, positive shifts in education should be highlighted. That is, since 2017, the activities of correspondence departments in various specialties have been restored in most higher education institutions. This form of Education allows young women to pursue higher education while maintaining children and fulfilling other family obligations.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said in the House of Commons Senate in June 2019, "The stereotype that arises in the minds of our men makes me think a lot. Usually we respect a woman, first of all, as a mother, as the guardian of the family stronghold. This is undoubtedly true. But today, not every woman should be an ordinary observer, but also an active and enterprising participant in the democratic changes taking place in the country", – argued that. These transformation processes can also be seen in the development trend, scientific, social, political and philosophical thought of Western and Eastern Tamaddun. Now let's briefly dwell on the views of members of the western and Eastern allomas and the jadidist movement. Socrates was condemned to death on charges of poisoning the minds of young people with his ideas about freedom and freedom of the individual, the right of Man and citizens. Plato, the father of philosophy, also favored these views in his work “the Ideal state”, demonstrating his commitment to the ideas of his great comrades. Plato concludes that the difference between male and female nature is relative and applies only to the reproductive sphere. A woman can choose professions at her discretion: music, philosophy or other professions, including military affairs. In Plato's work, “can a woman be considered capable of this difficult and responsible task? Will the female part of humanity be able to participate in all issues along with men?”, – he throws questions in the middle. Plato reveals the social roots of the problem by describing this reality of the role of women in society who were doomed to “cook soup” and “engage” as a result of the strong and long-term influence of tradition, customs in their day. Roman statesman and jurist Emilius Papinian writes about the position of women in society: “according to the general provisions of our legislation, the position of women is worse than that of men”. Although free, the woman did not have any civil rights. For example, he could not serve in the Army, vote at meetings, be elected to public office, be a judge or prosecutor, have no right to conduct a trial as a third-party lawyer. In the East, however, the woman has always been glorified as a friend of the man, yori, Akila, kind, compassionate of family peace. In Oriental thought, the position of women in society in Turkic peoples was very high. The Arab historian Ibn Battuta reports, “by the order of the Sultan and his wife”, as the Turkish khagans signed. Islam ranks men who have a good attitude towards their women among the best of human beings. In this regard, the hadith says: “the best among you is that you have a good attitude towards your people. By denying the tradition of ignorance, Islam has protected and elevated the woman to higher levels. The Prophet Muhammad (s.a.v.): "O mankind! Follow the wives' fees. Treat them with compassion, affection. Fear Allah in their truth. Wives are the trust of Allah to you. You gave them a word in the name of Allah, and they were honest with you with their command divine. You have the rights of wives, as you have the rights over wives. They said, “the truth of your

wives is that they do not trample the honor of their family on anyone you do not like.”

In his pedagogical views, Abdullah Avlani cites that family tinchi is directly in the hands of intelligent, intelligent, intelligent, educated women. In his work, Adib quotes the parents' concerns to the girls who are starting a family, noting that peace and happiness in the family are more the responsibility of women: “oh my daughter! You are leaving the house you learned to marry and fall into an unfamiliar house. You do not know the qualities of your future groom. You will be the Earth, and it will be the sky. If you are as humble as the Earth before him, he will be as noble as the sky. As the sky bruises the earth with its healing rain, so it pleases you with its kindness. May your husband hear from you only soft and sweet words, do not sit in front of you in a naughty or old dress or with your faces disheveled and your hair unregulated.

Abdurauf Fitrat's views on issues of family relations are also noteworthy. A number of her works suggest that women should be good-natured, educated, ecclesiastical, shy, sharm-fanciful, brave, deeply in love with her husband, unshakable, obedient to her husband, courteous, straight, modest and intelligent, well aware of her duty and duty, and frugal.

At the same time, a manifestation of the Turkic language, thinker Alisher Navoi, in the chapter “on marriage and wives” of the work “Mahbub ul-qulub”, expressed thoughts about marriage and its benefits, Family etiquette and the qualities of women in the family: “the state and happiness of a Good Wife – Family. The tidiness of the house is from him, the calm and tranquility of the owner of the house is from him. When Husny, the soul is poor, when it is polite, the soul is weak. If there is a discharge, there will be an ordination in the fast, the equipment will be clean and the order will stand” .

During the renewed Uzbek period, the distinctive Oriental tools, forms and styles of gender equality are widely used. As a result of the provision of gender equality between women and men, it can be recognized in particular that household chores, upbringing of children and all other tasks are assigned not only to the woman, but also to the father. It is also worth noting that it can be said that the fact that parents pay attention to issues of Eastern gender equality with Western gender equality even from a point of view of mentality serves to further clarify the issue.

References:

1. Article 46 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent: "Uzbekistan", 1992.
2. Shavkat Mirziyoyev speech at the twentieth Plenary Session of the Senate of the Supreme Assembly on June 21, 2019.
3. Platon. Dialogi [Dialogues]. Translation from ancient Greek. Khar'kov, Folio Publ., 1999. – 383 p.
4. Гуревич Д., Рапсат-Шарле М. -Т. Повседневная жизнь женщин в Древнем Риме. – Москва, 2006. – С. 239–240.
5. Alisher Navoi. "Mahbub ul-qulub" (mahbub proverbs and stories to Hearts). The current Uzbek language is tabdil. - Tashkent:" Psalm-standard", 2018.

A Treasury of British Folklore

Tosheva Dilbar Muzaffar kizi

Student of the chair Linguistics In the faculty of Roman-german philology

Karshi state university

Annotation: English mythology is the collection of myths that have emerged throughout the history of England, sometimes being elaborated upon by successive generations, and at other times being rejected and replaced by other explanatory narratives.

Key words: myth, legend, symbolically converge, figure, reality, traditions, folklore

Introduction: English mythology is the collection of myths that have emerged throughout the history of England, sometimes being elaborated upon by successive generations, and at other times being rejected and replaced by other explanatory narratives. These narratives consist of folk traditions developed in England after the Norman Conquest, integrated with traditions from Anglo-Saxon mythology, Christian mythology, and Celtic mythology.

Elements of the Matter of Britain, Welsh mythology and Cornish mythology which relate directly to England are included, such as the foundation myth of Brutus of Troy and the Arthurian legends, but these are combined with narratives from the Matter of England and traditions from English folklore .

English folklore consists of the myths and legends of England, including the English region's mythical creatures, traditional recipes, urban legends, proverbs, superstitions, and folktales. Its cultural history is rooted in Celtic, Christian, and Germanic folklore. When we hear tales of myths and folklore, we often think of Norse and Greek mythology. But British folklore, legends, and myth are nothing short of enchanting.

In the list of British books, you'll discover folktales, meet mystical creatures, learn British songs, and more. Take a journey through wooded forests, mystical places, and beautiful countryside. We've got something for all kinds of readers on this incredible list of British books about legends and myths. Whether you're looking for an easy or academic read, British poetry, or magical legends and myths, you'll find it here . Storyland is a unique compilation of the mythologies of Britain, written by the academic Amy Jeffs. Her fantastic retellings add a new light to the myths and legends native to the countries of Britain: England, Wales, and Scotland. This mythology doesn't skimp on British or Scottish folklore. At 384 pages, you can thoroughly enjoy the unique and magical British heritage that this book has to offer. This unique compendium doesn't stop there; it hosts the author's fantastic lino art that aligns itself with each piece of text. This book is truly one to savour and return to.

A Treasury of British Folklore: Maypoles, Mandrakes and Mistletoe is perfect for the reader who wants to their toes into the swampy, murky lowland waters of English legend and myth. This 204-page treasure trove of tales is just enough to give the reader a complete overview of British folklore.

Treasury really is the word. Here, Dee DeeChainey pays homage to the customs that have bled through the ages and stories rooted in Britain's past. Discover the tales of British folkloric creatures, as well as English legends and myths in this romp through the ages. While Kevin Crossley-Holland wrote this book with a middle-grade audience of readers in mind, it

remains perfect for readers of all ages. You and your family can discover the folktales of Britain and Ireland together in this enchanting collection. The book contains 48 beautifully written stories that transport you “between worlds,” where impossible magic and ordinary human lives collide. With mystical sections such as “Magic and Wonder,” “Fairies and Little People,” and “Ghosts,” there is a story to delight every reader of every age here.

Grimoire is the culmination of Robert Robertsons most significant work. It’s a volume of narrative poetry full to bursting with Scottish folklore, and it is ideal for anyone looking to explore this subject through sensational, moving language. It’s full of new perspectives, as he lends Scottish folktales a new light with his long-form poetry. Robertson includes the language of the land in his work. Weaving English and, at times, local Scottish dialects together make this a beautifully woven collection of dazzling tales. This is something truly unique and special. Who doesn’t love a good mermaid tale? Well, be careful what you wish for. Dee Dee Chainey and Willow Winsham wrote this book for every adult and child looking for water-related myths and legends. Take a journey through seas, rivers, and lakes all around the world.

As you read this fascinating book, you’ll discover selkies in Scotland or the legend of Maui in the Pacific Ocean. This treasury will introduce you to well-known stories and even the more obscure myths and legends. You’ll come across English sailor superstitions and shape-shifting pink dolphins. The woods are a dangerous place to get lost in. But when you lose yourself within the pages of *Weird Woods: Tales from the Haunted Forest of Britain*, you will feel as though you’ve come home. This book will keep you up at night with twelve chilling tales from twelve different authors. The tales here will help you navigate the vast forests and wooded lands of England where you’ll come across supernatural creatures of British folklore. Get ready to take a dangerous but exciting tour through and beyond the trees! Thoughtfully written by ecologist and author Lisa Schneidau, it’s here that you can discover where British folklore, mythical creatures, and Britain’s natural flora connect. Following the arc of the seasons, the *Botanical Folk Tales of Britain and Ireland* is here to take you on a journey through the greenery and foliage of Britain. With thirty-nine tales included, there is something for everyone’s curiosity. And, when you’re finished reading, you’ll have a new appreciation for the power of plants and the near magical benefits they provide us.

Visit the ancient land of Scotland with *The Anthology of Scottish Folk Tales*. This magical collection draws together the most memorable Scottish folklore passed down through the ages. With its handy map, it shows you where each tale takes place, drawing the reader even further into its charm and beauty. At 176 pages, it’s an excellent introduction to classic stories of Scottish folklore, such as “The Seal Killer” and “Buff Barefoot.” This Arthurian epic was rediscovered two hundred years ago after being published for the first time in 1839. It was originally written long ago by an unknown author and is one of the most well-known Arthurian legends to date. Following the tale of Sir Gawain, nephew to King Arthur himself, you can discover the myths and legends surrounding this larger-than-life character. This tale of honour and duty is interestingly eerie and will certainly keep you on the edge of your seat from start to finish .

Take an excursion across the largest country of the British Isles with the help of *The Anthology of English Folk Tales*. Travel over hills and across rivers to visit the unique haunts of the locals found in these English folk stories . This small anthology was inspired by The History Press’ popular Folk Tales series. It’s a collection of excellent English folk tales written by a selection of different authors. These British folkloric tales cover the full scope of any delightful folk tale compendium, including romance, fairy tales, and things that go bump in the night. Cozy up with your favorite blanket and a hot drink to spend an evening off with the fairies as you enjoy celebrating Scotland’s unique customs, beliefs, and dialects. The most recent edition of *The New Penguin Book of English Folk Songs* has brought together a complete collection of England’s folk songs.

Folk songs were not originally written down by the masses but sung throughout the day to

accompany everyday life. The authors have included sheet music to help readers fully immerse themselves in folk songs of past days.

This collection includes England's folk songs between the 1870s to 1980s and the original voice of the working class. It's perfect for both academic and leisure reading. Submit yourself to the captivating tale woven by Thomas Malory. If you've ever wished to immerse yourself in the legend of King Arthur thoroughly, look no further.

This tightly woven tale follows the life and death of King Arthur and his legendary rise to King in the mythical age of Arthurian times. British legends and myths abound in this tome and are perfect for academic and leisure reading. Malory doesn't leave out any enchanting myths during Arthurian times. With no stone left unturned (pun intended), the tale includes the Noble Knights of the Round Table, Morgan le Fay, and Guenevere, and all the legends surrounding these infamous characters of English myth and legend.

Literature

1. "Birth of England: The Wessex Kings – Alfred the Great". BBC Online. 2004. Retrieved 7 March 2018.
2. "King Arthur, 'Once and Future King'". BBC Online. 2017. Retrieved 7 March 2018.
3. "Athelston: Introduction". University of Rochester. 1997. Retrieved 7 March 2018.
4. "British Library Beowulf manuscript is star of BBC documentary". Culture24. 2009. Retrieved 11 March 2018.
5. "The Travels of Sir Bevis of Hampton". Bevis of Hampton. 2015. Retrieved 7 March 2018.
6. "Brutus of Troy". anthonyadolph.co.uk. 2015. Retrieved 11 March 2018.
7. "Brutus of Troy". berkshirehistory.com. 2006. Retrieved 11 March 2018.
8. "The Tale of Gamelyn: Introduction". University of Rochester. 1997. Retrieved 11 March 2018.
9. "Sir Guy of Warwick". BBC Online. 2018. Retrieved 11 March 2018.
10. "Havelok the Dane: Introduction". University of Rochester. 1997. Retrieved 11 March 2018.
11. "Hengist and Horsa". English Monarchs. 2018. Retrieved 11 March 2018.
12. "King Horn: Introduction". University of Rochester. 1997. Retrieved 11 March 2018.
13. Jalilovna, K. S. (2022). Common Similarities and Differences of Uzbek and English Fairy Tales. *European Journal of Innovation in Nonformal Education*, 2(1), 366-369.
14. Khalilova, S. (2022). PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS OF GLOBALIZATION. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 28, 6-11.
15. Jalilovna, K. S. (2022). COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH FAIRY TALES. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 80-83.
16. Jalilovna, K. S. (2022, February). A CASE STUDY ON VOCABULARY LEARNING THROUGH READING FAIRY TALES. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 5-6).

Enhancing Problem Solving Skills in Trainee Teachers through Constructionist-Based Teaching Approach

Ugochi Peace Ibeh Jaja

*Department of Curriculum and Instructional Technology, Faculty of Education,
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.
Email: ugochi.jaja@gmail.com*

Prof. Eunice C. Victor-Ishikaku

*Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education,
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.
Email: eunicevictor886@yahoo.com*

Abstract: This study investigates the Physics lecturers and the application of constructionist-based teaching approach in selected tertiary institutions in South-South/ South-East, Nigeria. The population consisted of 76 physics education lecturers in the selected tertiary institutions. The study posed 1 research question and 1 hypothesis. Survey research design was adopted for the study. Census sampling technique was adopted to select seventy-six (76) sample size. Self-structured questionnaire titled: Constructionist-Based Approach and Physics Education Lecturers Questionnaire (CAPELQ) was used for the data collection. The research supervisor and two lecturers in department of Curriculum Studies and Instructional Technology validated the instrument, while Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used for the test of reliability, which yielded reliability of 0.85. Out of the 76 distributed questionnaires, 65 respondents completed and returned the questionnaire, yielding 85.53% response rate, which includes 47 males (72%) and 18 females (28%). Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions while Factorial Design ANOVA was used in testing the hypotheses at 0.05% level of significance. The findings showed that project-based and collaborative learning make the trainee teachers to learn better. Also, Physics education lecturers do not differ significantly in terms of qualification ($F=0.42$, $p=0.959$) and experience ($F=0.214$, $p=0.808$), but they differ significantly in terms of gender ($F=10.700$, $p=0.002$) over the utilisation of the constructionist-based teaching approach in teaching Physics. It is therefore recommended that the constructionist-based teaching approach should be adopted in preparing Physics teachers.

Keywords: Problem Solving Skills, Problem Based Learning, Constructionist Teaching Approach, Teaching, Learning.

Introduction

Problem-solving skills involve analysing the possible causes of a problem and developing an action plan that solves that problem. Problem-solving skills are constantly used both in personal and professional lives. Problem-solving skills comprise defining a problem; finding the cause of the problem; recognising, arranging, and choosing alternatives for a solution; and applying a solution. Problem-solving skill is a process (a continuing activity) in which we discover what we do not know via what we know. It involves overcoming obstacles by generating hypotheses, testing those hypotheses and arriving at satisfactory solutions.

Problem-solving skill involves three basic functions: (i) seeking information (ii) generating new knowledge and (iii) making decisions. Problem-solving skill is defined as a person's ability to engage in cognitive processes when understanding and solving problems for which the method of solving is not readily available (Shute, et al. 2016). Problem-solving skill is one of the important skills that should be provided to prospective teacher students because, in addition to developing thinking skills, it also trains students' ability to manage learning to develop thinking skills. Problem-solving is an important skill for students so it should be an important element of learning design at every point.

Constructionism is a constructivist learning theory which states that building knowledge occurs best through building things that are tangible and sharable (Ackerman et al., 2009: 56). "Constructionism (in the context of learning) is the idea that people learn effectively through making things. Constructionism relates to experiential learning and builds on some of the ideas of Jean Piaget." Constructionism emphasises the importance of the knowledge, beliefs and skills that an individual brings to the experience of learning (Garbett, 2011). Constructionism can be perceived as an educational theory, learning theory, an educational movement, or a philosophy of learning. Its common characteristics include active involvement of learners who are intrinsically driven, knowledge production by learners, social learning environment and social contact. The role of the teacher is redefined from that of a giver of knowledge to that of an organizer of necessary learning experiences or a coach who provides guidance that gradually decreases as learners become more proficient. Learning is reflective and builds on learners' existing knowledge. The goal of instruction in a constructionist's sense is not the acquisition of the basic knowledge but conceptual development and deep understanding.

The Tenets of Constructionist-Based Teaching Approach

Constructionist-based teaching approach advocates learner-centred, discovery learning where learners use what they already know, to acquire more knowledge. The following teaching models will be discussed in this work: (i) Problem-based learning, (ii) Project-based learning (iii) guided discovery learning, (iv) collaborative learning and (v) experiential learning.

(i) Problem-Based Learning (PBL)

Problem-based learning is a constructionist method which allows learners to learn about a subject by exposing them to multiple problems and asking them to construct their understanding of the subject through these problems. This kind of learning can be very effective in mathematics and science classes because learners try to solve the problems in numerous ways, stimulating their minds.

(ii) Project-Based Learning

Project-based learning is a learner-centred pedagogy that involves a dynamic classroom approach in which it is believed that learners acquire a deeper knowledge through active exploration of real-world challenges and problems (Yasserli et. al., 2018). Project-based instruction differs from traditional inquiry by its emphasis on learners' collaborative or individual artifact construction to represent what is being learned.

(iii) Guided Discovery-Based Learning

Discovery-based learning is typically characterized by having; (i) minimal teacher guidance, (ii) fewer teacher explanations, (iii) solving problems with multiple solutions, (iv) use of hand-on materials, (v) minimal repetition and (vi) memorization. The outcome of guided discovery-based learning is the development of inquiring minds and the potential for life-long learning. Discovery learning promotes learners' exploration and collaboration with teachers and peers to solve problems. Learners are also able to direct their own inquiry and be actively involved in the learning process which helps with learners' motivation.

(iv) Collaborative Learning

An important aspect of collaborative learning is the move from assimilation to construction, which is creating new understanding hinged on learners' discussions. Collaborative learning requires cognitive and environmental determinants. Social presence is required to enhance social interactions, which is a major tool for collaborative learning (Laal & Ghodsi, 2012). Therefore, collaborative learning shows a significant effect on learners' social interaction skills. The constructionists believe that collaborative learning encourages learners to team up best with one another while enhancing socialisation among themselves.

(v) Experiential Learning

Experiential learning is an engaged learning process whereby learners "learn by doing" and by reflecting on the experience. Experiential learning activities can include, but are not limited to, hands-on laboratory experiments, internships, practicums, field exercises, study abroad, undergraduate research and studio performances. Experiential learning contains all the following elements: (i) reflection, critical analysis and synthesis, (ii) opportunities for learners to take initiatives, make decisions, and be accountable for the results, (iii) opportunities for learners to engage intellectually, creatively, emotionally, socially, or physically and (iv) a designed learning experience that includes the possibility to learn from natural consequences, mistakes, and successes.

Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by Jerome Bruner's Discovery Theory of Learning, which was propounded by Jerome Bruner in 1966. Bruner posited that the learner must think and explain his way of reasoning to the teacher instead of memorising what was taught by the teacher. A major theme in the theoretical framework of Bruner is that learning is an active process in which learners construct new ideas or concepts based upon their current/past knowledge. The learner selects and transforms information, constructs hypotheses, and makes decisions, relying on a cognitive structure to do so. Cognitive structure (i.e., schema, mental materials) provides meaning and organization to experiences and allows the individual to "go beyond the information given". Bruner (1966) states that a theory of instruction should address four major aspects: (i) predisposition towards learning, (ii) the ways in which a body of knowledge can be structured so that it can be most readily grasped by the learner, (iii) the most effective sequences in which to present material, and (iv) the nature and pacing of rewards and punishments.

Good methods for structuring knowledge should result in simplifying, generating new propositions, and increasing the manipulation of information. In his more recent work, Bruner (1986; 1990; 1996) has expanded his theoretical framework to encompass the social and cultural aspects of learning as well as the practice of law which is one of the major objectives of science teaching/learning. The application of Bruner's theory of learning to science teaching/learning is that the science teacher should intentionally create or present to learners either in form of apparent contradiction or inconsistency among sources of information which are given in the process of instruction. Encouraging discovery learning in science class by science teachers will result into aiding problem solving. Learners should be taught concepts in such a way that they have applicability beyond the situation in which they were taught.

Statement of the Problem

It has been observed that many Sciences, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) learners are unable to understand and assimilate STEM concepts or employ the said knowledge in new situations. STEM subjects are generally regarded as very difficult subjects in Nigeria. The genuineness of this outcry is depicted by the deteriorating poor performance

of learners in examinations. According to Taangahar and Ameh (2019), there is a low students' academic performance in physics which is because of their belief that physics is a difficult subject. Although several attempts have been made at improving quality teaching, these efforts have not been proportionately reflected in learners' overall performance. The serious problem in Nigeria is that very little is being done to alter this situation (Adul, 2011). The Nigerian Educational System has experienced deep crises for many years. One of the factors that could be responsible for the downward trend in learners' performance is their negative attitude towards the subjects. Secondly, teacher's failure to employ appropriate methods of teaching scares the learners away from the subject. Thus, the efficacy of constructionist-based instructional strategy is attempted to fill the vacuum between the situation and existing research.

The search for an effective method of teaching Physics as one of the STEM subjects has necessitated the need to employ more interactive and knowledge construction approach for improved teaching and learning. The teaching approach that advocates knowledge construction approach is the constructionist-based approach. The contradictory evidence in achievement and interest has resulted to the need to verifying if constructionist-based teaching approach is used in Physics teachers training in the selected tertiary institutions in South-South and South-East, Nigeria.

With the poor performance in Physics, one is tempted to raise the following questions: is the problem with the teachers or the learners, what are the teaching methods employed by the teachers, do they consider individual differences in teaching the subjects, are the problems with the learners amongst others? This study therefore looked at the aspect of the teaching methods to see if appropriate teaching methods are being used in the preparation of Physics teachers, hence the quest for this investigation.

Aim and Objective of the Study

The study explores the efficacy of the constructionist-based approach in advancing Physics teachers' training in the selected tertiary institutions. Specifically, the study is designed to determine if Physics education lecturers adopt the tenets of constructionist-based approach in pedagogical training.

Research Question

The research question formulated to guide the study was: Do Physics education lecturers adopt the constructionist-based learning approach in pedagogical training?

Hypothesis

The null hypothesis that guided the study was:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in Physics education lecturers adopting the tenets of constructionist-based teaching approach in pedagogical training based on gender, years of experience and qualification.

Methodology

The study was carried out in some selected tertiary institutions in the South-South/ South-East of Nigeria. The research adopted a survey research design. The population for this study consisted of all the Physics education lecturers in the seven (7) selected tertiary institutions in South-South/South-East, Nigeria. The number of Physics education lecturers from the seven tertiary institutions offering Physics Education as a course of study was seventy-six (76).

Table 1: Distribution of Population Table

S/N	NAMES OF SCHOOLS	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL
1	University 1	-	3	3
2	University 2	11	1	12
3	University 3	2	1	3
4	College of Education 1	14	1	15
5	College of Education 2	12	3	15
6	College of Education 3	3	6	9
7	College of Education 4	14	5	19
	TOTAL	56	20	76

Source: Field Survey, 2021/2022.

The research adopted census sampling technique. All the Physics Education lecturers were selected and used in the study, giving a total of seventy-six (76) from the seven (7) selected tertiary institutions in South-South/South-East. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire titled 'Constructionism Approach and Physics Education Lecturers' Questionnaire (CAPELQ). The questionnaire was divided into section A and section B. Section A sought bio data of the lecturers such as name of school, gender, qualifications and others, while section B of the questionnaire contained ten (10) items on a four Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) where the respondents were expected to tick based on the degree of agreement or disagreement to each of the items' statements. The responses were scored as follows: SA = 4, A = 3, D = 2 and SD = 1 to achieve a criterion mean score of 2.50, i.e., $10/4 = 2.50$.

For the validity of the instrument, three lecturers in department of Curriculum Studies and Instructional Technology looked at it and made necessary corrections before it was given to the respondents. To determine the reliability of the instrument the split-half method was used. The Constructionism Approach and Physics Education Lecturers' Questionnaire (CAPELQ) was administered to the 10 education lecturers and their responses were collected and split into two halves and were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) formula which yielded the value of 0.85. This indicated high coefficient and so was used for the study.

The researcher administered the Constructionism Approach and Physics Education Lecturers' Questionnaire (CAPELQ) to the selected lecturers. Out of the 76 distributed questionnaires, 65 respondents completed and returned the questionnaire, yielding 85.53% response rate. This included 47 males (72.31%) and 18 females (27.69%). The statistical tools used for this study were mean and standard deviation, to answer the research questions while Factorial Design Analysis of Variance was used in testing the hypotheses at 0.05% level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: Do Physics education lecturers adopt the tenets of constructionist-based approach in pedagogical training?

Table 1: Summary of descriptive statistics on the adoption of the tenets of constructionist –based approach in pedagogical training by Physics education lecturers.

S/N	Utilisation of Constructionist-Based Learning Approach in Pedagogical Training by Physics Education Lecturers	SA	A	D	SD	N	\bar{x}	σ
1	The adoption of project-based learning approach in pedagogical training makes the Physics teacher trainees to be actively involved.	50	10	5	0	65	3.69	0.61
2	The adoption of problem-based learning approach in pedagogical training makes the learning environment to be democratic for Physics teacher trainees.	25	33	7	0	65	3.28	0.64
3	The adoption of guided discovery-based learning approach in pedagogical training makes learning activities to be interactive.	32	25	8	0	65	3.37	0.69
4	The Physics education lecturers facilitate a process of learning in which learners are encouraged to be responsible and autonomous.	28	35	2	0	65	3.40	0.55
5	Experiential learning when adopted as a learning approach in pedagogical training of Physics teachers makes learning activities to be learner centred.	42	23	0	0	65	3.65	0.48
6	Social interaction of Physics education lecturers encourages learners to reflect, evaluate their work, and identify intermediary skills needed in learning Physics.	21	34	9	1	65	3.15	0.71
7	The exposure of learners to collaborative learning promotes diverse viewpoints in learning Physics.	36	20	8	1	65	3.40	0.76
8	Discovery learning helps Physics teacher trainees to develop advanced skills such as critical thinking, analysis, evaluation, and creativity.	30	34	1	0	65	3.45	0.53
9	The project work assigned to Physics teacher trainees encourage them to identify the skills they need to develop in order to improve in Physics courses.	40	21	4	0	65	3.55	0.61
10	The use of problem-solving teaching approach in pedagogical training can help learners develop research skills that will enable them to teach and learn Physics.	35	21	9	0	65	3.40	0.72
Grand mean							3.43	0.63

The mean ratings of the responses of Physics Education lecturers in Table 1 ranged from 3.14 to 3.69 which are all greater than mean value of 2.50 on the 4-point Likert rating scale. This showed that the ten identified items in the table are agreed on by the Physics education Lecturers. The standard deviation, which ranged from 0.48 to 0.76 showed that the responses

of the respondents are not only close to the mean but close to one another. Specifically, the result showed that the respondents strongly indicated that the adoption of project-based learning approach in pedagogical training makes the Physics education trainees to be actively involved ($\bar{x}=3.69$, $\sigma=0.61$). This was followed by experiential learning when adopted as a learning approach in pedagogical training of physics education trainees makes learning activities to be learner-centred ($\bar{x}=3.65$, $\sigma=0.42$) and the project work assigned to physics education trainees encourage learners to reflect on their progress and identify the skills they need to develop to improve ($\bar{x}=3.55$, $\sigma=0.61$). The least was social interaction of Physics education lecturers encourages learners to reflect, evaluate their work, and identify intermediary skills needed in learning physics ($\bar{x}=3.15$, $\sigma=0.71$).

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in Physics education lecturers adopting the tenets of constructionist-based teaching approach in pedagogical training based on gender, years of experience and qualification.

Table 2. Summary of factorial ANOVA on the difference in the Physics education lecturers' utilisation of the constructionist-based teaching approach based on gender, years of experience and qualification.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig. (p)
Corrected Model	0.612a	14	0.044	1.357	0.210
Intercept	253.245	1	253.245	7863.721	0.000
Gender	0.345	1	0.345	10.700	0.002
Qualification	0.003	2	0.001	0.042	0.959
Teaching experience	0.014	2	0.007	0.214	0.808
Error	1.610	50	0.032		
Total	767.970	65			
Corrected Total	2.222	64			

a. R Squared = .275 (Adjusted R Squared = .072)

The result from table 2 on the difference in the Physics education lecturers' utilisation of the constructionist-based teaching approach based on gender, qualification and experience showed that the physics education lecturers do not differ significantly in terms of qualification ($F=0.42$, $p=0.959$) and experience ($F=0.214$, $p=0.808$), but they differ significantly in terms of gender ($F=10.700$, $p=0.002$), over the utilisation of the constructionist-based learning approach in teaching Physics. The null hypothesis was rejected in terms of gender but was retained in terms of qualification and years of experience.

Summary of Findings

The result from table 1 shows the summary of descriptive statistics on the Physics education lecturers' adoption of tenets of constructionist-based instructional approach. Specifically, the result shows that the respondents strongly indicated that the adoption of project-based learning approach in pedagogical training makes the Physics education lecturers to be actively involved ($\bar{x}=3.69$, $\sigma=0.61$). This was followed by experiential learning when adopted as a learning approach in pedagogical training of physics education trainees makes learning activities to be learner-centred ($\bar{x}=3.65$, $\sigma=0.42$) and the project work assigned to physics education trainees encourage learners to reflect on their progress and identify the skills they need to develop in order to improve ($\bar{x}=3.55$, $\sigma=0.61$). The least was social interaction of Physics education lecturers encourages learners to reflect, evaluate their work, and identify intermediary skills needed in learning physics ($\bar{x}=3.15$, $\sigma=0.71$). The result further shows that the grand mean rating of the Physics education lecturers over the

utilization of the tenets of constructionist-based learning approach was 3.43, with a standard deviation (σ) of 0.63.

The result from table 2 on the difference in the Physics education lecturers' utilisation of the constructionist-based learning approach based on gender, qualification and experience showed that the physics education lecturers do not differ significantly in terms of qualification ($F=0.42$, $p=0.959$) and experience ($F=0.214$, $p=0.808$), but they differ significantly in terms of gender ($F=10.700$, $p=0.002$), over the utilisation of the constructionist-based learning approach in teaching Physics. The null hypothesis was rejected in terms of gender but was retained in terms of qualification and years of experience.

Discussion of Finding

The discussion of findings for this study is based on the research question and hypothesis that guided the study. Result from research question 1 (Table 1) shows the summary of descriptive statistics on the Physics education lecturers' adoption of tenets of constructionist-based instructional approach. Specifically, the result shows that the respondents strongly indicated that the adoption of project-based learning approach in pedagogical training makes the Physics education lecturers to be actively involved ($\bar{x}=3.69$, $\sigma=0.61$). This was followed by experiential learning when adopted as a learning approach in pedagogical training of physics education trainees makes learning activities to be learner-centred ($\bar{x}=3.65$, $\sigma=0.42$) and the project work assigned to physics education trainees encourage learners to reflect on their progress and identify the skills they need to develop in order to improve ($\bar{x}=3.55$, $\sigma=0.61$). The least was social interaction of Physics education lecturers encourages learners to reflect, evaluate their work, and identify intermediary skills needed in learning physics ($\bar{x}=3.15$, $\sigma=0.71$). The result of HO1 (Table 2) on the difference in the Physics education lecturers' utilisation of the constructionist-based learning approach based on gender, qualification and experience showed that the physics education lecturers do not differ significantly in terms of qualification ($F=0.42$, $p=0.959$) and experience ($F=0.214$, $p=0.808$), but they differ significantly in terms of gender ($F=10.700$, $p=0.002$), over the utilisation of the constructionist-based learning approach in teaching Physics. The null hypothesis was rejected in terms of gender but was retained in terms of qualification and years of experience.

This result is in agreement with Adekoya and Olatoye (2011) and Ezeudu (2013) which indicated that project-based learning method improves learners' achievement in sciences more than the traditional teaching methods like lecture and demonstration. Zakaria, et al (2010) and Baran et al. (2018) also agree that innovative learning methods such as problem-based, project-based, gaming, collaborative and guided discovery learning methods improve learners' ability. This study has established that the adoption of the tenets of constructionist-based learning approach such as project-based, problem-based and collaborative learning methods enhance the performance of Physics teacher trainees in Rivers State and Nigeria.

Conclusion

The star deduction of the study is that project-based and collaborative learning make the physics education trainees to learn better when using constructionist-based approach to teach Physics education in the tertiary institutions. The interest of Physics education lecturers in adopting the tenets of constructionism was high. Conclusively, Physics education lecturers do not make any difference in terms of qualification and years of experience but make huge difference in gender, in the application of constructionist-based approach. Gender does not make any difference, but qualification and years of experience make much difference over the interest to utilising constructionist-based teaching approach. This study showed that the application of the constructionist-based learning approach by the Physics education lecturers, irrespective of their gender, years of experience and qualifications increases the trainees'

knowledge in producing more independent and social Physics teachers who can impart knowledge to their learners and make significant impact in teaching and learning of Physics.

Recommendations

With respect to the findings of this study, the following recommendations are hereby made:

1. Physics education lecturers should adopt the constructionist-based approach in training their trainees.
2. The Physics education lecturers should learn to work in collaboration with their peers to effect social interaction in the use of constructionist-based learning approach.

References

1. Ackermann E., Gauntlett, D. and Weckstrom, C. (2009). Defining Systematic Creativity, LEGO Learning Institute, Summary, PDF download.
2. Adekoya, Y. M. & Olatoye, R. A. (2011). Effect of demonstration, peer-tutoring, and lecture teaching strategies on senior secondary school students' achievement in an aspect of agricultural science. *The Pacific Journal of Science and Technology*. 12 (1), 320-332.
3. Adul, B.A (2011). Effects of Meta learning instructional strategies on learners' achievement in advancement: a challenge to women in the 21st century. *Journal of Women in Colleges of Education (Jowice)*. 4, 159-163.
4. Alcock, M.; Fisher, M. & Zmuda, A. (2017). *Quest for learning: How to maximize learner engagement. Strategies to engage learners in the Classroom Using Guided Inquiry Design*. Solution Tree Press.
5. Alfieri, L., Brooks, P. J., Aldrich, N. J. & Tenenbaum, H. (2011). Does discovery-based instruction enhance learning? *Journal of Educational Psychology*. 103(1) 1-18.
6. Baran, M., Maskan, A., & Yasar, S. (2018). Learning physics through project-based learning game techniques. *International Journal of Instruction*. 11(2), 221–234. <https://doi.org/10.12973/iji.2018.11215a>.
7. Bruner, J. (1966). *Toward a theory of instruction*. Harvard University Press.
8. Bruner, J. (1986). *Actual minds, possible worlds*. Harvard University Press.
9. Bruner, J. (1990). *Acts of meaning*. Harvard University Press.
10. Bruner, J. (1996). *The culture of education*. Harvard University Press.
11. Chu, S. K. W., Reynolds, R. B., Tavares, N. J., Notari, M., & Lee, C. W. Y. (2017). *21st century skills development through inquiry-based learning*. Springer.
12. Ezeudu, F. O. (2013). Influence of concept maps on achievement retention of senior secondary school students in organic chemistry. *Journal of Education and Practice*. 4 (19) 013.
13. Garbett, R.A. (2011). *Issues in social studies and problems of nation-building in Nigeria*. Goad Educational Publishers.
14. Heick, T. (2018). 3 Types of project-based learning symbolize its evolution. Available at <http://www.teachthought.com/learning/5-types-of-project-based-learning-symbolize-its-evolution/>.
15. Hmelo-Silver, C. E. (2013). Creating a learning space in problem-based learning. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Problem-based Learning*. 7(1), 23-39.
16. Kolb, D. A. (1984). *Experiential learning: Experience as the source of learning and development*. Prentice-Hall.

17. Laal, M., Ghodsi, M. S. (2012). Benefits of collaborative learning. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 31, 486-490, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.12.091>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877042811030205>).
18. Markham, T. (2011). Project-Based Learning. *Teacher Librarian*, 39(2), 38-42.
19. Maros, M., Korenkova, M., Fila, M., Levicky, M. & Schoberova, M. (2021): Project-based learning and its effectiveness: evidence from Slovakia. *Interactive Learning Environments*, DOI: 10.1080/10494820.2021.1954036.
20. Shieh, C-J. & Yu, L. (2016). A study on information technology integrated guided discovery instruction towards students' learning achievement and learning retention. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*. 12(4)833-842.
21. Shute, V. J., Wang, L., Greiff, S., Zhao, W. & Moore, G. (2016). Measuring problem solving skills via stealth assessment in an engaging video game. *Computers in Human Behaviour*. 2016, 106-117.
22. Taangahar, B. A. & Ameh, I. (2019) Effect of discipline and attitude on academic performance of secondary school physics students in Ogbadibo Local Government Area of Benue state. *Benue State University Journal of Education (BSUJE)*. 19 (2) 178-185.
23. Tu, Ch., & McIsaac, M. (2002). The relationship of social presence and interaction in online classes. *The American Journal of Distance Education*. 2(16), 131-150.
24. Yasseri, D., Finley, P. M., Mayfield, B. E., Davis, D. W.; Thompson, P. & Vogler, J. S. (2018). The hard work of soft skills: augmenting the project-based learning experience with interdisciplinary teamwork. *Journal of Instructional Science*. 46 (3) 457-488.
25. Zakaria, E., Chin, C.L. & Daud, Y. (2010). The effect of cooperative learning on student mathematics achievements and attitude towards mathematics. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 6 (2) 272-275.

Theoretical Principles of Aesthetic Education of Students Based on the Music of Makom Instruments

Boltayev Umidbek Rustamovich

Teacher of Urganch State University, Independent researcher

Abstract: In this article, there is a scientific discussion about the importance and theoretical-practical foundations of Maqom art in the education of our future students.

Keywords: Educational system, music culture, Status art, aesthetics, Development strategy, tradition.

Introduction.

Since ancient times, the Uzbek people have occupied a special place with their rich national and cultural values, traditions, and their great contribution to world culture. The fact that the whole world recognizes the rich musical heritage created by the Uzbek people in the development of world culture and art is a worthy assessment of our nation's long past history and present day.

Fundamental reforms in the continuous education system of our republic began in 2017. From the same year, work towards the final result at all levels of the education system, ensure the competitiveness of specialist personnel being trained in higher education, increase the potential of pedagogic personnel at all stages of the education system, improve the material and technical base of educational institutions. strengthening, provision of educational laboratories, science offices, provision of education with improved educational literature was put on the agenda as a priority task.

In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan *"On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026"* specifies the need to pay great attention to the development of education¹. The intensification of integrative and innovative processes has set itself the task of educating a well-rounded person who is qualified and professionally formed in music education. This, in turn, requires providing music education with new teaching methods, high-quality repertoire, educational literature, teachers to find, polish and learn performance traditions.

The head of our state said, *"As we aim to turn Uzbekistan into a developed country, we can achieve this only through rapid reforms, science and innovation. For this, first of all, we need to educate new generation personnel who will be proactive reformers, who will think strategically, and who will be educated and qualified"*².

Therefore, the aesthetic education of students with the help of Maqom musical tunes, raising education to a new level of quality, remains directly dependent on the effectiveness of its teaching.

¹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated 28.01.2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026". El. address: <https://lex.uz/docs/5841063>

² Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis.

December 29, 2020. Email address: www.lex.uz

His research on the study of musical heritage is noteworthy. In particular, I. Rajabov's "On the Question of Statuses", "Statues", O. Matyokubov's "Maqamot" and S. Saidi's "Semantics of Shashmaqom and Status Circle Methods", theoretical and practical foundations of statuses, which are one of our national values, Eastern music theorists works, musical views, pre-Islamic traditions, musical words, tazkiras of distinguished teachers are referred to, and their life and creativity, as well as the basic principles of performance styles and schools of performance are shown.

In this field, which has a history of almost 2000 years, Borbad Marwazi, Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Safiuddin Urmavi, Haji Abdul Qadir Maroghi, Najmuddin Kavkabi, Darvesh Ali Changi, and in the words of Maulana Ro Dakiy, Umar Khayyam, Ustad Bedil, Firdavsi, Manuchehri, Khusrav Dehlavi, Nadirabegim, Urmavi and others created great figures. They left a very rich legacy in the field of music theory and composition, as well as in the literary interpretation of words, in the midst of our past history of life and death. However, during the Arab invasion, written sources related to music were burned and lost. Therefore, the musical works they created have not reached us.

But the written sources of the history of the next thousand years have reached us. Medieval musicologists learned more about music theory and composition in Abu Nasr Farabi's "Big Book of Music", "A Word About Music", Abu Ali Ibn Sina's "Treatise on the Science of Music", "Kitobu ash- "healing" based on the definition of music science and composition. The science of music was further developed in the works of scientists who lived and created in the 13th-14th centuries - Saifiuddin Urmavi, Haji Abdulkadir Maroghi, Abdurahman Jami, Najmiddin Kavkabi and others.

V. A. Uspensky (1879-1949) is one of the first scholars to refer to Uzbek notation as a source of status. He came to Bukhara in 1923 to record Shashmaqom by the order of the Republic of Bukhara People's Councils, and heard Shashmaqom directly from Ota Jalal (1845-1928) and Ota Ghiyos (1859-1927), who were living Shashmaqom at that time. 'starts to take notes directly. The Saqili Ashkullo part of Dugoh status is never remembered by teachers. Then everyone is surprised when Ota Ghiyos looks at the Tanbur line in his hand and plays the Shaqili Ashkullo. The Russian scientist was extremely happy to see the source in which the statuses were completely recorded, and he sent a letter about this rare book to his close friend and colleague, professor of the Moscow Conservatory Viktor Mikhailovich Belyaev (1886-1968) and about the wonderful find. the good news spreads among experts and arouses interest.

Abdurauf Fitrat's work "Uzbek classical music and its history" is valuable for its classification of Bukhara shashmaqom, Khorezm Khalfachiligi and Dutor, circle methods, and the initial news related to the status of Tanbur line³. These pamphlets contain information on ancient traditions, history of Khorezm states, performance methods, method structures, and famous performers of the period up to the 30s of the 20th century.

In the book "Obzor muzykalnoy kultury Uzbekov i drugikh narodov Vostoka" published in Samarkand in 1931 by N. Mironov, there is a musical score "Sarakhbor Zihi nazzora" from the Khorezm Dostonchilik and Khalfachilik art, Tanbur and Dutor maqams.⁴

Ye.E., who served a lot in Uzbek musical folklore. In her article "Janr Uzbekskaya muzyka", Romanovskaya mentions the existence of dutor maqams in other local traditions and mentions the names of 4 maqams.

In the collections of Shashmaqom recorded by Yunus Rajabi, the sound sequence and structural parts of all the main tunes (maqoms) are shown in detail. Yu.Rajabi's research, a

³ Abdurauf Fitrat "Uzbek classical music and its history". - Tashkent, 1993. - 70 p.

⁴ Mironov N. Review of musical cultures of Uzbeks and other peoples of the East. - Samarkand, 1931. - p. 29

thorough connoisseur of Uzbek classical music, an excellent hafiz and musician, is a world in itself. Alloma Yu.Rajabiy recorded Shashmaqom as a collection and published it in the form of a book. He also sealed audio recordings and video films of Shashmaqom's performances. These works carried out by the teacher are one of the main sources for learning the basics of Shashmaqom.

Today, the process of revival of our national values requires a comprehensive study of our cultural heritage, including our artistic traditions formed over the centuries. In this regard, the art of composition in traditional music, which is an invaluable spiritual property of our people, is one of the important and valuable sources, and it is important that they are studied on a large scale.

The scientific problem that has arisen is to study the importance of aesthetic education of students by means of Maqom musical tunes as a separate dissertation research, and to collect all available methodological materials in connection with the practical activities that should be carried out in this regard, systematizing them in practical performance. is to show effective ways of application on a scientific basis. These cases once again confirm the relevance of the topic of the dissertation research.

Research tasks:

- Getting to know the research carried out in the implementation of status inheritance;
- Elucidate the semantics of maqam instrument performance under comparisons and hypotheses;
- to determine the level of study of the problem based on interdisciplinary analysis of theoretical and methodical literature, scientific research on the topic;
- Conducting experimental work on the topic of research and developing methodical recommendations based on its final results.

Literature review (analysis).

In the process of choosing the subject of this research, scientific researches and published scientific-methodical sources related to Maqom and music pedagogy and methodology were studied during the last quarter of a century. Methodological aspects of organizing music lessons in general secondary schools, explaining educational materials on topics are emphasized. In the course of his research, People's Artist of Uzbekistan F. Mamadaliev's "Issues of performance of national music" (Mamadaliev F. Issues of performance of national music. - T., 2001.), "History of performance of Uzbek folk instruments" by professor A. Odilov. (Odilov A. The history of performance in Uzbek folk instruments. - T.: Teacher, 1995. - 128 p.) we tried to learn analytically. Also, I. Rajabov's "On the issue of status", "Status", O. Matyokubov's "Status" and S. Saidi's "Semantics of Shashmaqom and status circle methods" are scientific manuals that cover the theoretical and practical foundations of status, which are one of our national values. was studied

As a result of the studied and analyzed sources, we came to the conclusion that the organization of music lessons, imparting knowledge to students, educational and educational (aesthetic, moral, patriotic, artistic taste, etc.) .

Summary.

In conclusion, we can say that many lovers of our national classical music know that the musical wealth of our nation is very multifaceted, rich and colorful. Our catchy and wonderful tunes bring joy and happiness to a person. It has the power to express a person's noble qualities and feelings. Magnificent masterpieces of maqam art are of special importance in the study of our musical wealth. They are an inexhaustible source for the

creation of new musical works. As with all areas of social life, the art of music cannot progress without enjoying the priceless heritage of the ancestors. Therefore, staying true to traditions and relying on them at every moment is the guarantee of the future fruit, children's prospects and the upbringing of a well-rounded generation. "Maqoms, musical monuments of various places are among the sources of value, which include, in particular, ancient "primary line" (downstream) melodies and certain "traces" of old "goh" style instruments. is finding its expression." - says O. Ibrohimov in his book "Maqom va Makon". The fact that the status means that it is one of the most complex, healing and miraculous compositions among the world classical performers, it is a factor that shows the pride of our Motherland and the brilliant wisdom of our ancestors, pleases us.

In the future, studying and teaching the characteristics of status paths and performance classifications in the education of the young generation will have a positive effect on the destiny and development of the country.

REFERENCES:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated 28.01.2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026". El. address: <https://lex.uz/docs/5841063>
2. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. December 29, 2020. Email address: www.lex.uz
3. Abdurauf Fitrat "Uzbek classical music and its history". - Tashkent, 1993. - 70 p.
4. Boltayev R. "On the relationship between Khorazm Tanbur and dutor statuses" Lessons of Shashmaqom (the second collection of lectures and articles) - Tashkent 2005.
5. Boltayev R. "Parda and Method Basis of Khorezm Statuses" // Lessons of Shashmaqom UNESCO collection Tashkent: 2007. - B.47.
6. Matyokubov O. Shashmaqom science// Lessons of Shashmaqom (the third collection of lectures and articles) -Tashkent: 2007. -B. 15-27.
7. Matyokubov O. Authority. -Tashkent: Music, 2004. - 400 p.
8. Matyokubov O. Khorezmskiye makomi. Abstract diss.na soisk.uch. degree cand. art - Tashkent-Leningrad: 1977. - 23 p.
9. Mironov N. Review of musical cultures of Uzbeks and other peoples of the East. - Samarkand, 1931. - p. 29

The Level of Salinity and the Dynamics of Change in the Irrigated Soils of Dostlik Massif, Furqat District, Fergana Region

Jabbarov Odil Abdimalikovich

“Soil composition and repository, quality analysis center” State Unitary Enterprise

Sodikova Maftunakhan Olimjon qizi

National University of Uzbekistan Master’s degree

Makhkamova Dilafroz Yuldashevna

National University of Uzbekistan (PhD) in biology assistant professor, Faculty of Biology

Abstract: This article discusses the impact of various factors such as an increase in the area where the groundwater level is close to the surface of the earth, global climate change, and improper irrigation on soil reclamation, which can lead to hydromorphism processes and salt accumulation in the soil. The article also provides information about the increasing activity of these issues. Additionally, the article presents an analysis of the irrigated soils of the Dostlik massif, including their current state, salinity level, and dynamics of change over the years.

Keywords: Soil ground water, improper irrigation, salinity, dry residue.

Salinity is the most significant issue affecting irrigated soils in our republic. While other problems such as chemical pollution, erosion, drought, nutrient depletion, and human impact can also lead to soil degradation, their impact is usually less severe than that caused by salinity. Factors such as improper irrigation, non-compliance with agricultural practices, periodic rise of seepage waters, and failure to maintain the collector-drainage system at a high level of operation can contribute to the increasing problem of salinity [1,2,4,7].

Water-soluble salts accumulate in irrigated soils, and the intensity of secondary salinization processes depends on several factors, including the depth and level of mineralization of groundwater, the concentration of soil solution, and the quality of irrigation water. The state of groundwater is the leading factor in this process. The closer the groundwater is to the surface and the higher the level of mineralization and evaporation, the faster the salt accumulation and secondary salinization processes occur in the soil [3,6].

The condition of groundwater varies significantly throughout the year, particularly during the vegetation period, depending on the topography of the area, lithological-geomorphological structure, hydrogeological conditions, irrigation regime and standards, the level of drainage, and the type of irrigated crops [5,8].

Groundwater plays a crucial role in the formation of irrigated soils, particularly in the valley's conditions, where achieving an optimal groundwater regime and balance is critical. Groundwater has a comprehensive impact on the formation of saline soils, acting as the primary source of salt in the soil in some instances and as a means of collecting dissolved salts and expelling them from the irrigated and desalinated areas in others [3,4].

Analyzing the reclamation condition of the irrigated soils in the studied area and studying the chemistry of salts, it was found that the soils in the region are weakly saline. Some cross-section soils were also found to be non-saline and moderately saline. The dominant types of salinity in the soil are sulfate and chloride sulfate. In the weakly saline sulfate salinity soils, the dry residue amounts to 0.848%, with chlorine ion and sulfate ion levels of 0.007% and 0.20%, respectively, in the driving layer. In the plow layer of weakly saline chloride-sulfate salinity soils, the dry residue amount is 0.144%, with chlorine ion and sulfate ion levels of 0.011% and 0.067%, respectively.

For medium saline sulfate salinity soils, the dry residue amount is 1.206% in the plowed layer, with chlorine ion and sulfate ion levels of 0.042% and 0.740%, respectively. If we analyze the salinity status and the dynamic changes of irrigated soils in the Dostlik massif over the years, it can be observed that the salinity level in the region has increased by a significant amount from 2010 to 2023, as shown in Table 1.

1-table Dostlik massif, Furqat district, Fergana region salinity of irrigated soils change in level over the years

Year	Total area, hectare	The degree of salinity, hectare			
		Nonsaline	Less	Average	Strong
2010	1701,2	507,0	888,6	305,6	0,0
2020	1929,6	789,6	751,0	389,0	0,0
2023	1929,6	364,9	1094,2	447,0	0,0

In 2010, the irrigated area of the Dostlik massif was 1701.2 hectares. Of this, 888.6 hectares were classified as having low salinity, and 305.6 hectares were classified as having moderate salinity.

These results indicate that 52.2% of the total irrigated area in the region had low salinity, while 18% had moderate salinity. The non-saline areas in the region amounted to 507.0 hectares, which indicates that 29.8% of the total irrigated area was not affected by salinity. There were no areas in the region affected by strong salinity.

By 2020, the total irrigated area of the region reached 1929.6 hectares. Non-saline areas accounted for 789.6 hectares, making up 40.9% of the total irrigated area. Low-salinity soils comprised 751.0 hectares, which is 38.92% of the massif's soil. Average-salinity soils occupied 389.0 hectares, equivalent to 20.18% of the total irrigated area.

In 2023, the irrigated area of the Dostlik massif remained unchanged at 1929.6 hectares. Non-saline soils covered an area of 364.9 hectares, representing 18.9% of the total irrigated area. Low salinity soils accounted for 1094.2 hectares, or 56.7% of the region's irrigated area. Average saline soils covered an area of 447.0 hectares, representing 23.1% of the irrigated area of the massif (1 - picture).

1-picture Dostlik massif, Furqat district, Fergana region salinity of irrigated soils change in level over the years

The effective use of irrigated lands has been established in the Dostlik massif, and their melioration condition can be considered average, meaning that salinity has not completely taken over the area. Based on the results of the conducted research, the increase in salinity levels in the area can be attributed to global climate change and the deterioration of soil melioration due to improper irrigation practices.

Currently, one of the main reasons for the deterioration of the fertility of irrigated lands in our country is the increase in temperature, which leads to the rise of the groundwater level and the accumulation of salts in the soil and its layers. This affects plant life in the soil, leading to the exposure of the top layer of the soil to direct sunlight.

Improper irrigation practices, such as not determining the degree of mineralization of irrigation water or using water from collector ditches, can lead to soil salinization.

Another reason for the deterioration of soil fertility is the improper use of fertilizers, which can result in changes to the chemical properties of the soil, fluctuations in the groundwater level, and degradation of the biological properties of the soil. Due to the failure of the main part of the collector and drainage networks, as well as vertical wells in the district, the groundwater level is rising in areas close to the surface of the earth, causing a number of problems in irrigated agriculture. This has led to intensified hydromorphism processes, increased salt accumulation in the soil, and more frequent cases of secondary flooding.

Based on the information obtained, it is important to use the soil wisely, choose the appropriate crops, cultivate the land properly, and implement an irrigation system that requires a scientific approach for the effective use of irrigated lands and prevention of their degradation

References:

1. Atoev B., Kaypnazorov J., Egamberdieva M., Makhammadiev S., Karimov M., Makhkamova D. Technology of nutriating winter wheat varieties in variety-soil-fertilizer system. E3S Web of Conferences 244, 02040 (2021).
2. Gafurova L.A, Madrimov R.M, Razakov A.M, Nabieva G.M, Makhkamova D.Yu., Matkarimov T.R. Evolution, Transformation and Biological Activity of Degraded Soils. International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology Vol. 28, No. 14, (2019). Pp. 88-99.
3. Jabbarov O.A. Reclamation status of irrigated soils and their dynamics / "Prospects, problems and solutions of farming in the Fergana Valley". Collection of materials of the Republican online scientific and practical conference - Fergana, 2020. - B.224-227.
4. Jabbarov O.A., Makhkamova D.Yu. Some biodiagnostic aspects of low-productivity, difficult-to-improve gypsum soils / "Problems and prospects of innovative techniques and technologies in agriculture - food chain". Collection of scientific works of the international scientific and scientific-technical conference - Tashkent, 2020. - B. 404-405.
5. Makhkamova D., Gafurova L. Seasonal dynamics of the amount of ammonifying bacteria in soils of Djizzak steppe // European Science Review. Austrian Journal of Technical and Natural Sciences. No. 11-12, November-December. Vienna-2017. -Pp. 3-8.
6. Makhkamova D., Gafurova L., Nabieva G., Makhammadiev S., Kasimov U., July M. Integral indicators of the ecological and biological state of soils in Jizzakh steppe, Uzbekistan. Sustainable Management of Earth Resources and Biodiversity IOP Conf. Series: Earth and Environmental Science 1068 (2022) 012019 IOP Publishing doi:10.1088/1755-1315/1068/1/012019.
7. Pankov M.A. Soils of the Hungry Steppe. In: "The Hungry Steppe", Tashkent, 1957.
8. Pankova E.I., Egorova V.V. -Guidelines for the amelioration of solo network and accounting for soil salinity. Tr. Institute of Soil Science named after V.V.Dokuchaev, M., 1970.

The Place of Abu Ali Ibn Sina (Avicenna) in Present Times

Hakim Darmonov Orif o'g'li

Toshkent Farmatsevtika Inistituti, Farmatsiya Fakulteti 4 bosqich talabasi

Abstract: This article describes the life and contributions of the Persian scientist Ibn Sina, who lived between 980 and 1037, and his contributions to medicine. Ibn Sina is best known for his medical encyclopedia, The Laws of Medicine, which became the standard medical text in the Islamic world and Europe for over 600 years. His medical theories and treatments were advanced and are still used today.

Keywords: Ibn Sina, Avicenna, Persian polymath, Golden Age of Islam, contributions, medicine, Canons of Medicine, medical encyclopedia, standard medical text, anatomy, physiology, diagnosis, treatment, tuberculosis, opiate anesthesia, philosophy, astronomy, literature, Thomas Aquinas, legacy, intellectual thought.

Introduction

Even at the age of 17, Ibn Sina became known as a skilled physician among the people of Bukhara. At that time, the ruler Nuh ibn Mansur was sick, and the palace doctors were powerless to treat him. A young doctor, whose fever has spread throughout the city, is invited to the palace to treat the emir. The patient quickly recovers from his treatment and gets back on his feet. Instead, Ibn Sina will have the opportunity to use the palace library. The library of the Somonites was one of the largest and richest libraries in the Middle East at that time. Ibn Sina studied in this library day and night for several years, became one of the most educated and knowledgeable people of his time, and from that moment began to independently study the philosophy of the Middle Ages. He devotedly read "Metaphysics" by Greek authors, especially Aristotle. But most of what was described in this book was incomprehensible to Ibn Sina. By chance, Abu Nasr Farabi's book "About the goals of metaphysics" fell into the hands of a young scientist, and Ibn Sina was able to master metaphysics only after reading it. Ibn Sina received all the necessary knowledge in Bukhara, and his scientific work began at the age of 18. He published a treatise on spiritual powers dedicated to Nuh ibn Mansur, a medical poetic work called "Urjuza", and at the request of his neighbor and friend Abulhusayn al-Aruzi, a multidisciplinary work "Alhikmat al-Aruzi" ("Wisdom of Aruzi"). In addition, at the request of another friend, the jurist Abu Bakr Albarqi (or Baraqi), the 20-volume encyclopedic work "Alhosil wal-mahsul" ("The End and the Result") and the 2-volume "Kitab al-bir wal-ism" ("Generosity and wrote the crime book"). Ibn Sina, also known as Avicenna, made significant contributions to the field of pharmacy.

Research Methodology. The article examines Ibn Sina's contribution to pharmacology using research methodologies such as literature review, data set study, data analysis, synthesis, review and improvement.

Analysis and results. As a physician and scientist, Ibn Sina conducted extensive research on medicines and their effects on the human body. He wrote extensively on the medicinal properties of plants, minerals and animal substances and used them to develop several important medicines. The Great Allama defined the forms of use of drugs, the methods currently used in modern medicine: that is, showing drugs in solid form (tablets, powders, dragees), liquids (solutions, tinctures, decoctions), at the same time the methods of

injecting into the body were used several centuries ago, and opinions were expressed about its use. At the same time, the ways of administering drugs to the body, their absorption, distribution in the body, and their amount in the blood are of certain importance. Only then, the drug interacts with the body tissue and shows its effect. The effectiveness of these drugs largely depends on the way they are administered to the body. There are drugs that do not have any effect when taken orally, but have a positive effect when administered in another way (injection). There may be cases where the same drug has different effects on the body when administered in different ways. Therefore, it is necessary to correctly choose the way in which the positive effect of each drug is administered to the body. Ibn Sina gave information about the ways of introducing drugs into the body, through the mouth, back (anal), nasal or urinary tract. One of Ibn Sina's most important contributions to pharmaceuticals was his invention of the distillation apparatus. This apparatus allowed him to extract essential oils from plants, thus creating powerful remedies with concentrated active ingredients. This distillation process became widely used in the centuries after Ibn Sina's work and revolutionized the way herbal medicines were produced and administered. In addition to his achievements in drug production, Ibn Sina also wrote extensively on the dosage and proper use of various drugs. His work emphasized the importance of understanding the effects of different substances on the human body and tailoring treatments to the individual needs of patients. At the same time, the great doctor also talked about the use of drugs, that is, the ways of sending them to the body. The forms of use of the Great Alloma drug are classified, and the methods currently used in modern medicine: that is, showing drugs in solid form (tablets, powders, dragees), liquids (solutions, tinctures, decoctions), at the same time the methods of injection into the body were used several centuries ago, and opinions about their use were expressed. At the same time, the ways of administering drugs to the body, their absorption, distribution in the body, and their amount in the blood are of certain importance. Only then, the drug interacts with the body tissue and shows its effect. The effectiveness of these drugs largely depends on the way they are administered to the body. There are drugs that do not have any effect if taken orally, but have a positive effect if given in another way (injection). There may be situations where the same drug has different effects on the body when it is administered in different ways. That's why it is necessary to choose the right way to show the positive effect of each medicine when it is injected into the body. Ibn Sina gave information about the ways of introducing medicine into the body, through the mouth, back (anal), nasal or urinary tract. He knew, used and wrote in his works about the fact that it is possible to send it through the rectum, especially when it is not possible to send it through the mouth, and it is considered useful. Currently, the incidence of cancer is increasing in the period when the negative impact of various man-made factors, especially carcinogenic factors on the human body is increasing. According to the World Health Organization, the world may face cancer in the next 10-12 years. Because obesity, excessive consumption of alcohol and smoking are increasing among the world's population, which creates the basis for the emergence of this disease. According to the prediction of the above organization, it may reach 19 million by 2025, 22 million by 2030, and 24 million by 2035. Eastern medicine had the concept of cancer, and Ibn Sina tried to find a cure for this disease. In "Medical epic", the great Hakim discussed the treatment of bad breath and its symptoms. **Conclusion/Recommendations.** In conclusion, Ibn Sina's contribution to pharmaceuticals had a great impact on the field of medicine both in his time and in the following centuries. His innovations in drug development and administration paved the way for many of the treatments we use today, and his writings are studied. Ibn Sina's works are used as the main guide in the history of medicine.

REFERENCES

1. Sindarovich, U. A., Dilnoza, Q., & Fayzullo o'g'li, B. A. (2023). National Traditions of Interior Architecture of Buildings of Wedding Houses. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF ARTS AND DESIGN*, 4(3), 1-7.
2. Hamrayev, S. (2023). O'ZBEKISTON SHAHARSOZLIGIDA TARIXIY VA ZAMONAVIY SHAHARLARNING BADIY UZVIYLIGI. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(1 Part 4), 85-89.
3. Shodiyeva, M. (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ТАРИХИЙ ШАҲАРЛАРИДА ЭНГ ҚАДИМГИ ВА ИЛК ЎРТА АСР САРОЙЛАРИНИНГ ШАКЛЛАНИШИ ВА РИВОЖЛАНИШ ЭВОЛЮЦИЯСИ. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(6), 243-247.
4. Sindarovich, U. A., & Erkinovich, M. U. (2021). THE ARCHITECTURE OF THE HISTORICAL PALACES OF UZBEKISTAN AND WAYS OF USING THEM FOR MODERN PURPOSES. *World Bulletin of Management and Law*, 3, 31-33.
5. Жураев, Т. Х., Сувонов, О. Ш., & Сапаров, Х. Р. (2020). Разработка концепции курса для учебного процесса геометро-графических дисциплин. *Образование и проблемы развития общества*, (3 (12)), 32-39.

Innovative Technologies in Teaching Vocabulary in Foreign Languages

Jalalova Sevara Janabay kizi

Bachelor degree student Chirchik State Pedagogical University

Abstract: In modern society, foreign languages are becoming an important part of vocational education. Such knowledge is first acquired by people in schools, colleges, lyceums, and later in institutes, training courses, or by familiarizing themselves with basic information sets that help them learn a foreign language independently. This article reveals ways to use innovative technologies in teaching English during today's globalization.

Keywords: Foreign language, schools, colleges, lyceums, step-by-step teaching, The Present indefinite Tense, The Past indefinite Tense, The Future indefinite Tense, Hot Ball game, Talk, Daily English, Learn English.

Today, foreign language skills are becoming an integral part of vocational education. Due to the high level of cooperation with foreign partners in various fields, the demand for language learning is high. In modern society, foreign languages are becoming an important part of vocational education. Such knowledge is first acquired by people in schools, colleges, lyceums, and later in institutes, training courses, or by familiarizing themselves with basic information sets that help them learn a foreign language independently. There is a large collection of teaching materials for people with different levels of language skills. Success in achieving this goal depends on the practical skills and qualifications of the teachers. The ability to use information technology and modern teaching methods helps to quickly grasp new materials.¹ By combining different methods, a teacher is able to solve specific curricula. In this regard, teachers and students need to become familiar with modern methods of teaching foreign languages. As a result, they develop the skills to choose the most effective ways to achieve their goals. Using a variety of teaching and learning methods can be effective. Teaching takes place in small steps and is based on the student's existing knowledge system.² As time goes on, innovation in every field increases. There are also different styles of language teaching. In English language teaching, step-by-step teaching, depending on the learner's potential and level of age, gives good results. Students are divided into groups based on elementary education, intermediate education, and advanced education. A special program will be developed by the teacher for each stage.

At the initial stage, the emphasis is on pronunciation. According to Harmer, the first requirement of a native speaker is pronunciation. At the beginning of the learning process, the teacher should focus on the student's pronunciation. Although grammar and vocabulary are important, it is useless if the speaker mispronounces them. Native speakers can also understand speech with grammatical errors if the speaker pronounces the words correctly.³ Therefore, in teaching, the main focus is on pronunciation. In this case, the use of different audios of native speakers gives good results. The teacher should teach the correct pronunciation of letters and words during the lesson. There is also a strong emphasis on oral and reading skills in the early stages. If we look at the types of speech activities of foreign language teaching, it is necessary to perform the following tasks in their teaching:

- A. Create a reading mechanism;
- B. Improving oral reading techniques;
- C. Teach them to understand what they are reading.

At the elementary level, there is a strong emphasis on reading aloud. Reading texts are also becoming simpler and more complex. However, it should be noted that although the work in the early stages is mainly focused on the development of oral skills, it does not solve the problem of developing oral speech in English. He is only in the process of preparing to work on a real speech. In addition, reading words beautifully and fluently increases a student's love of learning the language.

In addition, students will be introduced to The Present indefinite Tense, The Past indefinite Tense, Are required to be familiar with verb tenses such as The Future indefinite Tense and to be able to use verb forms vividly in these tenses. Students will learn the use of nouns in the singular and plural, the addition of the suffix "s" or "es" to the third person singular form of the verb in the present indefinite tense, and the interrogative, negative, and imperative forms of sentences. during the study period.

At the intermediate stage of teaching English, the focus should be on using techniques that help to increase thinking, speaking, and initiative in reading and understanding larger texts. Students will be given homework assignments. Exercises to check comprehension of the text are given and can be expressed as follows:

Answer the question on the text Samarkand: Why Samarkand is called like this? Where is the ancient center of the city? How many population is there?

Question-answer exercises are used to strengthen the student's speech, improve memory, and repeat. New words from the text are memorized. Questioning and answering will help you to memorize the words and use them in your speech. In addition, a variety of games in the classroom will increase the student's interest in learning the language and speed up the learning process. In the Hot Ball game, students form a circle and say one of the new words to the ball. Participants do not repeat each other's words, are expelled from the game if they repeat or stop speaking. That's the way to play.

In the middle stage, grammar is taught in more depth than in the first stage, and students are given exercises, tests and tests based on the rules of grammar.

Computer and phone language learning programs are also great for elementary and middle school language learning. Examples include Talk (English speaking practice), Daily English, Learn English (English master), How to speak real English. These programs are designed to include reading, listening, and test sections. Recording new words on a phone Dictaphone in your spare time is another great way to repeat. Also, showing more English subtitles and cartoons is an effective way to teach the language. At the advanced level, independent work plays a special role, especially in a foreign language. The course requirements at this stage are different from those at the previous stages. The lesson is no longer based on oral speech, because at this stage most of the language material is studied passively (receptively). That is, reading comprehension plays a key role.⁴ Texts are also large in size and language material is complex. Reading, speaking, listening exercises are held regularly. When organizing a lesson, a separate day is set for Reading, a separate day for Speaking, and a separate day for Listening. Homework is also more complex than previous steps. Speaking lessons include a 2-minute talk with a topic. Alternatively, text cards will be distributed to students. Each student gives their opinion on the topic on the card of their choice. The speech requires the use of previously used phrases, phrases, introductory words, new words, synonyms.

Homework can be used to prepare additional text topics using the press, periodicals, media,

and online materials. Students will be interested to learn about interesting research and scientific discoveries.

In conclusion, modern language teaching is aimed at forming a more cultured individual who has the skills to self-analyze and systematize new knowledge. Innovative methods are an integral part of modernizing the entire system. With this in mind, teachers can become acquainted with the most advanced approaches and then combine them and use them in their work to achieve significant growth in the education system. Many organizations are moving to a new level, using multimedia capabilities to send and receive information. The use of computers and other devices determines the success of the whole educational process.

Adequate attention should be paid to the formation of speech skills and the development of social resilience in educational training. In addition, the success of any lesson in education depends in many ways on the proper organization of lessons. The lesson should be based on the creative collaboration of teacher and student. Only then will students be able to think independently and develop their abilities.

References:

1. Passov E. I. Sociable learning method of foreign conversation. - Moscow., 1985-10p.
2. Johnson, K. E. The Socio cultural Turn and Its Challenges for Second Language Teacher Education. // TESOL Quarterly., - London., 2006: - 235- pages.
3. Harmer J. The Practice of English Language Teaching. - London., 2001: - 64 pages.
4. Jalolov J. Methods of teaching foreign languages. - Tashkent., 2012: - 48 pages.